

APPENDIX A
APPENDIX B
APPENDIX C

APPENDIX A

Reconstruction of the main stages of the «Pitchforks» and «Tractors» movements as of May 2024

The first occurrence of «Pitchforks» (*Forconi*, in Italian) associated with a protest movement in the digital archive of the newspaper *La Stampa di Torino* is in a news article from 17 January 2012: «Trucks on the road against high fuel prices. The Pitchforks revolt blocks Sicily» (*lastampa.it*, 2012). The protest movement formed by farmers and breeders, which the following year will spread nationwide, is founded in 2011 (Ronzoni, 2012). In January 2012, «[t]ogether with the Aias truckers' associations» [*ibidem*], on the barricades over fuel costs and groups of fishermen angry about the export crisis, both converging into the «Forza d'Urto» movement, the «Pitchforks» plan to paralyse the entire island. The hypothesis that behind the unrest were extra-parliamentary far-right formations becomes more than a suspicion as early journalistic investigations reveal a network of personal relationships, ideological alignments and explicit endorsements from *Forza Nuova* (*ilpost.it*, 2012; Ronzoni, 2012) and *Casa Pound* (Froio and Gattinara, 2015).

Between 2012 and 2013, with strong support from far-right circles (Pasqualino, 2013; *ilpost.it*, 2023), (Marinolli, 2013), incorporating «more or less organised groups of farmers, workers, street vendors and football ultras [... while i]n some cities, union organisations and militants of the so-called antagonistic left also participate in the demonstrations» (*ilpost.it*, 2023). In addition to demands supporting agriculture, transport and commerce, the protesters' goals include the fall of the government, the resignation of the President of the Italian Republic, Giorgio Napolitano, the dissolution of Parliament, leaving the Eurozone and new elections (Orrù, 2016).

The climax of the movement's trajectory is reached on 9 December 2013, the date chosen by the Movement's leaders (united under the name «Comitato 9 dicembre» [9 December Committee]) to «stop Italy» or, as some of the more violent factions do, «break everything» (*repubblica.it*, 2014; Coccoresse, 2023). The protests span the entire peninsula and the main islands, but Turin is the epicentre of the revolt, characterised by «urban guerrilla warfare» (Tropeano *et al.*, 2013) involving railway pickets, stone throwing, Molotov cocktails, clashes with the police and tear gas to disperse the crowd; main roads and highways are paralysed, commercial establishments are forced to close under threat, windows are shattered and attempts are made to storm the regional and municipal buildings (AFP, 2013; *ilpost.it*, 2013; Laugeri and Tropeano, 2013; Tropeano *et al.*, 2013; Coccoresse, 2023). Interpreting as a sign of solidarity the fact that some riot police officers remove their helmets in front of the Turin protesters (McCauley, 2013), the next day, Beppe Grillo (founder

and leader of the «5-Star Movement») calls on law enforcement to «no longer protect this political class» and to join the protest (Grillo, 2013).

Despite the echo of the events of 9 December, the anticipated revolution does not take off (Bendinelli, 2017), exhausted by internal leadership conflicts (rainews.it, 2013) and the rapid depletion of the movement's momentum. Yet not without some *coup de théâtre*, namely an unsuccessful march on Rome (Bianchi, 2013) and, three years later, the «popular arrest» of former Forza Italia MP Osvaldo Napoli (ilpost.it, 2016), which results only in an investigation by the Latina prosecutor's office for conspiracy, ending in nothing (latinaoggi.eu, 2019).

Thirteen years after its inception, the «Pitchforks» are once again mentioned in relation to another wave of movementism. On 1 February 2024, 1,300 agricultural tractors and over two thousand people march through the streets of Brussels, catching the local administration and security forces off guard, who had expected a significantly smaller turnout (open.online, 2024). Before 9 a.m., some of the protesters are already clashing with riot police protecting the European Commission near Luxembourg Square (rtl.be, 2024). The contingent, besides locals, includes representatives from agricultural professions from France, Spain, Portugal, and Italy [ibidem]. Tons of manure are dumped on the streets, barricades are set on fire, eggs are thrown and other acts of vandalism occur (Waterfield and Sage, 2024; Whitehead, 2024).

When, on 8 January 2024, the Italian version of the so-called «Tractors» movement enters the Italian public agenda – once again with its epicentre in Sicily, as during the early «Pitchforks» days, because «nothing has changed since then. Politics has proven ineffective» (Minardi, 2024) – its Central European counterparts have already covered many miles on Union roads. The digital version of the German magazine «Der Spiegel» addresses the issue for the first time on 13 December, reporting that the intention to abolish tax benefits for agriculture by the Berlin government, with the consequent increase in diesel prices for tractors, is received by German farming associations as a «declaration of war» (*Kampfansage*) (spiegel.de, 2023). Similar research shows that in the Netherlands, agricultural associations have been in turmoil for at least partially similar reasons since 2019 (reuters.com, 2019), with flare-ups in the summer of 2022 (telegraaf.nl, 2022). Since September 2015, there have been protest marches against Eu's Common agricultural policy (Cap), with a thousand tractors blocking traffic around Eu's institution buildings in Brussels (euronews.com, 2015).

In the early days of 2024, the protest – active for months in Germany – consolidates in France, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Slovenia (Pattueli, 2024), spreading to Romania and Bulgaria (Magnani, 2024). In Italy, a «Tractors» movement only forms two weeks later, driven – among the most active online groups – by the *Riscatto Agricolo* [Agricultural redemption]

committee and the *C.r.a. - Agricoltori Traditi (Comitati riuniti agricoli)* [Betrayed Farmers (United Agricultural Committees)], the latter led by a former «Pitchforks» leader, Danilo Calvani (Alliva, 2024; [repubblica.it](https://www.repubblica.it), 2024). An indefinite state of agitation is declared starting on 22 January, reaching its peak media visibility in two almost consecutive moments: the first in the week of 5 February with the request – initially accepted and then turned into a late-night reading of a statement by the presenter – to accredit a representation of the struggling agricultural professions on the stage of the Sanremo Festival to give visibility to the reasons for the conflict; the second coincides with the national demonstration at the Circus Maximus in Rome on Thursday, 15 February, which gathers about 1,500 people to protest against the Cap, considered detrimental to the sector due to the eco-sustainability restrictions imposed by the European Union. Direct attacks on sector unions and the government are not lacking, identified as accomplices of the supranational impositions ([rainews.it](https://www.rainews.it), 2024).

However, starting in March, the movement wave begins to partially dissipate despite blockades and parades with agricultural vehicles continuing to be organised at several points across Italy and in Brussels (Chiappa *et al.*, 2024). By May 2024, no new events of the scale observed at the beginning of the year are recorded. Nevertheless, the European «Tractors» mobilisation achieves a targeted review with an emergency procedure of the Cap 2023/27, the package of measures that triggered the autumn protest first in Germany (Atzeni, 2024; [consilium.europa.eu](https://www.consilium.europa.eu), 2024).

APPENDIX B

Methodological note.

Following the same expository framework developed by two of the authors in a previous work (Tipaldo *et al.*, 2022), we will here delve into the main methodological choices made in designing the research on «Pitchforks» and «Tractors». Specifically, we will provide details on the phases of i) Data Collection, ii) Preprocessing and iii) Thematic Analysis of Elementary Contexts (TAEC), including an examination of the sub-phases of iv) Clustering and Statistical Analysis; finally, in v) we detail the Sentiment Analysis performed to provide a spectrum of emotions associated to each topic enucleated from the previous phases.

i) *Data Collection*

The empirical material (table 1 in the main paper) was assembled through a combination of semi-automatic and partly supervised data retrieval approach due to Facebook's limitations on its Graph API at the time of analysis. The identification and subsequent extraction of user-generated data on Facebook Italy were conducted using the CrowdTangle search engine (a native service of Meta Inc., officially discontinued in August 2024), based on the following queries:

- «forconi» AND («movimento» OR «protest?» OR «rivolt?») OR «movimento 9 dicembre»;
- «tractors» AND («ammassano» OR «autostrada» OR «bloccano» OR «bruxelles» OR «contestazion?» OR «corteo» OR «marcia*» OR «movimento» OR «PAC» OR «paralizzano» OR «presidi*» OR «protest*» OR «rivolta» OR «proteste» OR «richieste» OR «rivolte»).

As mentioned in the main paper, the Ugc (User-Generated Content) retrieved with the above queries were sorted according to the «overperforming» variable, which we will now discuss to provide additional information for the Reader. According to information provided by Meta Inc. through the CrowdTangle blog (Crowdtangle, 2024c, 2024b, 2024a), «overperforming posts» are content that exceed expected engagement results (i.e., interactions, such as likes, comments, shares, and views) relative to specific benchmark parameters. From a statistical perspective, defining an «overperforming post» involves calculating the ratio between observed interactions and expected interactions:

$$(1) \textit{Overp.Score} = \frac{X_i}{\mu} \quad , \text{ with } X_i \text{ being the observed value of the } i\text{-th interaction and } \mu \text{ the mean}$$

interaction value in the reference dataset (i.e., expected value). As can be easily inferred from

the formula, values equal or close to 1 indicate performance in line with expected values; conversely, a post will be more overperforming the higher its score is relative to 1.

The peculiarities of the procedure lie mainly in the definition of the denominator of the formula, namely the benchmark. CrowdTangle states that it generates a benchmark based on the last 100 posts of an account (e.g., the public page of a person, product/service, media outlet, etc.), then creates homogeneous comparison classes by type of content. Consequently, a new post from an account is compared with the average value calculated from the previous 100 posts of that account belonging to the same content class (textual posts, posts with images, videos, posts containing links). The purpose is to ensure homogeneous comparisons: although the details are confidential, it is indeed well known that the newsfeed algorithms in Meta's products prioritize the visibility of posts differently based on the type of content.

Finally, to mitigate the influence of outliers, the distribution tails, namely the top and bottom 25% of posts, are excluded. The average interactions are then calculated for the remaining 50% of cases, corresponding to the central part of the distribution, at regular intervals from the time the content is published (typically, 15 and 60 minutes, 5 hours, and beyond).

The comments published under the posts selected according to the criteria outlined above were retrieved in a semi-automated process, which also relied on an online scraping service, due to the significant limitations imposed on APIs, even for purely scientific research purposes, by some of the major social media platforms, including those owned by Meta Inc.

ii) *Preprocessing*

Multiple pre-processing activities were carried out. First, the data were anonymised (i.e., deprived of reference to the username and the unique post id) and, during translation from the original language (Italian) to English, were also subjected to a manual process of partial perturbation. Vocative expressions between users involved in conversations were omitted (e.g. Dear [Name]), while particularly vulgar or offensive forms of profanity were partially censored. In addition, references that could have made a post recognisable even after translation were masked (i.e. «with a salary of 1.000 euro» was changed to «with a salary of ##### euro» or similar formulas). Finally, the excerpts included in the main paper and in Appendix C as examples of the content of clusters contain regular expressions (regex), which are sequences of random characters inserted between words and within them, to prevent the textual material reported from being an exact replica of what was retrieved online, despite being public. To balance conflicting requirements – namely, constructing an ethical dataset and preserving the fidelity of the original material – the alterations were introduced post-analysis.

Upon completion of the anonymisation phase, R Studio was employed for normalising the corpora. This included cleaning the texts of spam, links, emojis, and excessively long words (over 50 characters). The processed data were consolidated into two different CSV files.

iii) *Thematic Analysis of Elementary Contexts (Taec)*

The graphs presented in the main paper (Figures 2 and 3) are the visual outputs of the Thematic Analysis of Elementary Contexts (TAEC), a function provided by the T-Lab software. An «elementary context» is defined as «every sequence of words interrupted by a full stop and carriage return, whose dimensions are less than 400 characters» (Lancia, 2024: 269). The technique – a type of combined application of co-occurrence analysis and lexical correspondence analysis (Tipaldo, 2025) – reduces the dimensionality of semantic data to offer a simplified representation of a corpus, identifying the most significant thematic clusters it comprises. In our case, an unsupervised clustering process was chosen (Lancia, 2024: 100). The data processing according to this technique utilised the cosine coefficient as a measure of proximity or distance between vectors, and bisecting K-means as the partitioning method (ivi: 101). The reference coordinates of the procedure are summarised below (table A).

tab. A *Key metrics of the ECs classification made by T-Labs software for «Pitchforks» (N total ECs in corpus = 20.970) and for «Tractors» (N total ECs in corpus = 64.347).*

«Pitchforks»

Cluster N	N of ECs classified	% total classified (% total in the corpus)
1	2.961	28,6 (14,1)
2	2.809	27,2 (13,4)
3	1.408	13,6 (6,7)
4	1.428	13,8 (6,8)
5	1.735	16,8 (8,3)
Total ECs classified	10.341	100,0 (49,3)

«Tractors»

Cluster N	N of ECs classified	% total classified (% total in the corpus)
1	8.678	27,1 (13,5)
2	7.162	22,4 (11,1)
3	9.504	29,7 (14,8)
4	6.682	20,9 (10,4)
Total ECs classified	32.026	100,0 (49,7)

iv) *Clustering and Statistical Analysis*

The identification of the partitions of the two corpora used in the research followed an iterative algorithmic process, which is also part of the Taec. In brief, the software compares the quality of each new partition with the previous one, applying the ICC-rho (Intraclass Correlation Coefficient), which measures the ratio between within-cluster variance and total model variance. Further checks on the validity of each new solution are performed by calculating the Caliński-Harabasz index (the higher the score, the better-separated the clusters) and the Davies-Bouldin index (which operates inversely). By default, the algorithm stops producing new partitions when the gap value decreases, and the software recommends the (n-1) partition as the optimal model from a purely quantitative perspective. Given the nature of the data, which pertain to the realm of Natural Language, we chose to verify each solution proposed by the software through an intensive reading of large extracts from the identified clusters, to qualitatively assess the appropriateness of

tab. B Key metrics of the Taec made with T-Lab using its unsupervised clustering algorithm (N attempts = 7) both for «Pitchforks» and «Tractors».

«Pitchforks»

Partitions/attempts	ICC (rho)	Gap	Caliński-Harabasz	Davies-Bouldin
2	,006	,000	-	-
3	,014	,008	73,692	23,381
4	,025	,011	87,639	9,829
5	,037	,012	99,654	5,186
6	,050	,013	108,314	3,181
7	,065	,015	119,543	2,058
Selected solution: 5 clusters Cosine similarity: ,037				

«Tractors»

Partitions/attempts	ICC (rho)	Gap	Caliński-Harabasz	Davies-Bouldin
2	,010	,000	-	-
3	,027	,017	437,904	12,188
4	,042	,015	468,569	5,695
5	,066	,023	561,407	2,852
6	,088	,022	614,323	1,737
7	,109	,022	654,590	1,165
Selected solution: 4 clusters Cosine similarity: ,042				

the statistical solutions. Considering both quantitative and qualitative aspects, we collectively decided on the 5-partition model for «Pitchforks» and the 4-partition model for «Tractors» (table B). Furthermore, it seems appropriate to dedicate further attention to the interpretation of the axes of the Cartesian spaces generated by the Taec, which we use in the main paper to address Rq2. The visual output of the Taec is an analogue reproduction, on a factorial map, of the distance between occurrences (Lancia, 2024). It is correct, therefore, to assume that clusters appearing far apart are informed by significantly different vocabularies (and vice versa), meaning lists of lemmas for which the probability of observing common co-occurrences is minimal, if not zero (and vice versa). The co-occurrence of terms within a language’s vocabulary is partly due to the syntagmatic rules (formal or customary) prevailing in that language at a given historical moment yet largely depends on the meanings and effects that the authors intended to reproduce by constructing the text *with those particular words*. It follows, therefore, that Cartesian axes can be thought of as *continua* between two pairs of polarities with semantic value (i.e., the horizontal axis $\pm x$; the vertical axis $\pm y$). As in any statistical procedure for data dimensionality reduction, the Cartesian axes, beyond the variability in the data explained by the model, account for latent dimensions – in the case of textual analysis, of a semantic type – to which proximity or distance, concordance or divergence, can be attributed, and whose theoretical interpretation is the responsibility of the researcher(s).

In conclusion, despite the potential for Taec to be interpreted across multiple dimensions, this study restricts the analysis to two factors. Those omitted from discussion in the main article are presented in table C along with their respective Eigenvalues.

tab. C Factors and Eigenvalues of the Taec made with T-Lab.

«Pitchforks»

Factor	Eigenvalues	%	Cum. %
1	,222	33,78	33,78
2	,164	24,95	58,74
3	,138	21,06	79,80
4	,133	20,19	100,00

«Tractors»

Factor	Eigenvalues	%	Cum. %
1	,322	48,87	48,87
2	,177	26,86	75,73
3	,160	24,26	100,00

v) *Sentiment Analysis*

The purpose of this final paragraph is to describe the methodology adopted to carry out Sentiment Analysis. We will provide details on the intermediary steps that led to the result shown in the main article.

v_1) Sentiment: Dictionary Based or Neural Network

The initial question that emerged pertained to the selection of an appropriate model for analysis. Two primary options were considered: dictionary-based models, which are computationally efficient but less accurate, and neural network-based models, which offer higher accuracy but are more computationally demanding. A further consideration in this case study was the linguistic constraint, as not all models support the analysis of Italian text, at least in a scientifically acceptable fashion. The decision-making process was informed by recent studies (Fesenko, 2023a, 2023b) that evaluated various models. Preliminary tests conducted on a subset of our dataset led to the selection of *Pysentimiento*. This Python package was chosen for its high accuracy, compatibility with Italian text, and utilization of models trained on social media content, aligning well with the requirements of our case study.

v_2) Python Script

The Python script developed for this study leverages two key libraries: *Pandas*, for handling CSV files, and *Pysentimiento* (Pérez *et al.*, 2021), for textual analysis. The script takes a CSV file as input, processes a specified text field, and generates a labelled CSV file as output. Three types of analysis are performed:

1. **Sentiment Analysis:** This module, designed for the Italian language, is based on the SENTIPOLC@EvalITA dataset. It employs binary annotations – Positive and Negative – which allow for four possible label combinations: *Positive*, *Negative*, *Positive and Negative*, or *Null*.
2. **Emotion Analysis:** Emotion detection utilizes the FEEL-IT dataset, which includes annotations for four emotions: *anger*, *fear*, *joy*, and *sadness*.
3. **Hate Speech Detection:** This module is trained using the HaSpeeDe@EvalITA dataset. The model applies a multi-label approach with two labels – *Hate* and *Stereotype*. Consequently, content can be labeled as *Hate*, *Stereotype*, *Hate and Stereotype*, or *Null*.
4. For simplicity, this suite of analyses is collectively referred to as *Sentiment Analysis*. Further technical details can be accessed via the [Pysentimiento Colab notebook](#).

v_3) Application on elementary contexts

The input for Sentiment Analysis consists of elementary contexts derived from the Thematic Analysis phase, detailed above. Two datasets are analysed: one pertains to the Pitchforks movement debate, containing 10.341 elementary contexts, and the other relates to the Tractors movement debate, with 32.026 elementary contexts. Each CSV file is organized with three primary fields: a unique identifier for each elementary context, the text field to be analysed, and the cluster label assigned during the earlier Thematic Analysis.

The output retains these original fields and includes three additional fields that present the results of the analyses performed: Sentiment Analysis, Emotion Analysis, and Hate Speech Detection. These new fields contain the respective labels assigned by each analytical module.

Sentiment	Emotion	HateSpeech
Positive	Anger	Hateful
Negative	Fear	Stereotype
Positive & Negative	Joy	Hateful & Stereotype
Null	Sadness	Null

v_4) Analytical Elaboration

The objective of the Sentiment Analysis is to enable *infra* (clusters within the same case study) and *intra* (across the two case studies) comparisons. To ensure the output is presented in a clear and intuitive manner, the analysis reports the percentage of elementary contexts associated with each sentiment for each cluster, rather than using absolute counts. This approach avoids potential misinterpretation caused by the differing sizes of the clusters. To enhance readability, elementary contexts assigned dual labels (e.g., *Positive* and *Negative*) are included in both corresponding simple sentiment categories (*Positive* and *Negative* separately). This reduces the complexity of the labels displayed while retaining interpretability.

Intermediate data processing utilized Pivot Tables, which aggregated the sums of detected sentiments, emotions, and hate speech for each cluster in both the Tractors and Pitchforks datasets. These aggregate values were then used to compute the percentage composition of each sentiment, emotion, and hate speech category within each cluster, providing a standardized basis for comparison. Below are the summary tables of the Pitchforks dataset. In order, the count of Sentiment, Emotion, Hate Speech and finally the overall percentage components are shown for each thematic cluster.

Sentiment Pitchforks	[null]	['neg']	['pos','neg']	['pos']	Total
1 – TOTAL PROTEST	243	2.337	272	109	2.961
2 – NATIONALISM	144	2.134	312	219	2.809
3 – PITCHFORKS POSITIONING	91	1.094	140	83	1.408
4 – DISSENT MANIFESTATION	160	1.059	148	61	1.428
5 – PITCHFORKS & LEADER GRILLO	136	1.282	166	151	1.735
	774	7.906	1.038	623	10.341

Emotion Pitchforks	anger	fear	joy	sadness	Total
1 – TOTAL PROTEST	2.693	24	64	180	2.961
2 – NATIONALISM	2.433	38	132	206	2.809
3 – PITCHFORKS POSITIONING	1.274	20	55	59	1.408
4 – DISSENT MANIFESTATION	1.311	18	28	71	1.428
5 – PITCHFORKS & LEADER GRILLO	1.574	11	93	57	1.735
	9.285	111	372	573	10.341

HateSpeech Pitchforks	[null]	['hateful', 'stereotype']	['hateful']	['stereotype']	Total
1 – TOTAL PROTEST	1.793	517	423	228	2.961
2 – NATIONALISM	1.715	446	491	157	2.809
3 – PITCHFORKS POSITIONING	901	191	235	81	1.408
4 – DISSENT MANIFESTATION	1.037	156	170	65	1.428
5 – PITCHFORKS & LEADER GRILLO	1.134	187	343	71	1.735
	6.580	1.497	1.662	602	10.341

Pitchforks % Components	pos	neg	anger	fear	joy	sad	hate	stereotype
1 – TOTAL PROTEST	12,87	88,12	90,95	0,81	2,16	6,08	31,75	25,16
2 – NATIONALISM	18,91	87,08	86,61	1,35	4,7	7,33	33,36	21,47
3 – PITCHFORKS POSITIONING	15,83	87,64	90,48	1,42	3,91	4,19	30,26	19,32
4 – DISSENT MANIFESTATION	14,63	84,52	91,81	1,26	1,96	4,97	22,82	15,47
5 – PITCHFORKS & LEADER GRILLO	18,27	83,46	90,72	0,63	5,36	3,29	30,55	14,87

Sentiment analysis revealed that 92,52% of the elementary contexts in the Pitchfork dataset exhibited identifiable sentiment, while only 7,48% were classified as «null». In comparison, hate speech was detected in 36,34% of the elementary contexts. It is noteworthy that the emotion detection algorithm mandates assignment to a specific category, resulting in 100% coverage of the elementary contexts.

Below are the summary tables of the Tractors dataset. In order, the count of Sentiment, Emotion, hate speech and finally the overall percentage components are shown for each thematic cluster.

Sentiment Tractors	[null]	['neg']	['pos', 'neg']	['pos']	Total
1 - ANTI-EU	1.252	6.295	751	380	8.678
2 - AGAINST TRACTORS	1.561	4.251	501	849	7.162
3 - PRO-TRACTORS	1.127	3.739	893	3.745	9.504
4 - PRO-EU & PRO-ENVIRONMENT	1.113	4.282	563	724	6.682
	5.053	1.8567	2.708	5.698	32.026

Emotion Tractors	anger	fear	joy	sadness	Total
1 - ANTI-EU	8.171	40	241	226	8.678
2 - AGAINST TRACTORS	6.046	30	737	349	7.162
3 - PRO-TRACTORS	6.068	42	3.036	358	9.504
4 - PRO-EU & PRO-ENVIRONMENT	5.457	46	573	606	6.682
	25.742	158	4.587	1.539	32.026

HateSpeech Tractors	[null]	['hateful' 'stereotype']	['hateful']	['stereotype']	Total
1 - ANTI-EU	5.285	1.459	1.232	702	8.678
2 - AGAINST TRACTORS	4.143	1.267	1.118	634	7.162
3 - PRO-TRACTORS	4.708	1.296	3.179	321	9.504
4 - PRO-EU & PRO-ENVIRONMENT	4.148	1.100	812	622	6.682
	18.284	5.122	6.341	2.279	32.026

Tractors % components	pos	neg	anger	fear	joy	sad	hate	stereotype
1 - ANTI-EU	13,03	81,19	94,16	0,46	2,78	2,6	31,01	24,9
2 - AGAINST TRACTORS	18,85	66,35	84,42	0,42	10,29	4,87	33,3	26,54
3 - PRO-TRACTORS	48,8	48,74	63,85	0,44	31,94	3,77	47,09	17,02
4 - PRO-EU & PRO-ENVIRONMENT	19,27	72,51	81,67	0,69	8,58	9,07	28,61	25,77

Sentiment analysis revealed that 84,22% of the elementary contexts in the Pitchfork dataset exhibited identifiable sentiment, while only 15,78% were classified as «null». In comparison, hate speech was detected in 57,09% of the elementary contexts. It is noteworthy that the emotion detection algorithm mandates assignment to a specific category, resulting in 100% coverage of the elementary contexts.

v_5) Data Visualization

Bar charts were created with the Flourish software (Flourish, n.d.). To streamline the analysis and focus on the most relevant factors, sentiments and emotions with multiple labels were excluded from the graphical representations. However, these omitted components are detailed in the tables provided above for reference.

The final output does not include hate speech and stereotype detection, as a closer qualitative analysis of the labeled results revealed several instances of false positives and false negatives (see the table below), which led us to conclude that this part of the procedure was insufficiently reliable. Consequently, it was not incorporated into the research design presented and discussed in the main paper. Nonetheless, we decided to retain the complete working pipeline in this appendix, as originally structured.

DOC_ID	SEG_ID	CONTEXT	Hate_Speech	Evaluation
15720	15775	DO not mak3 the mist@ke of mixing Grillo with thosÈ scumbags. Grillo is a movem3nt, like y0u, and c@me to parliament with th3 people You don't wànt flags of p@rties or movements, but what do you th1nk, that the M5S will càrry your bãnner of "f0rcôni"? Oh, plêase! Grillo súpports the "forconi," pérhaps someone hasn't understoød that!	[]	FALSE NEGATIVE
436	436	... This is à pr0test that sh0uld hav3 started°°° a few^^ years ago. Since joining Europe, OUR POLITICIANS h@ve never pr0t3cted made in italy... Italy hás been °°°sold ^^off piéce by piéce, and now°°° we're at§§ the breaking ^^point. Anyway, °°°better lâte than nêver...	[]	FALSE NEGATIVE
98	98	"Burini" (bumpkins), g°o to Br^ussels... Wh@t does R_om_e have t^o do with it???? R0me??????	[]	FALSE NEGATIVE
15772	15827	Let our l3ad3r Gr1llo come ^^down with °°us and give us môre str3ngth than h°e al0ne has been°° able to give; l3t this b3 the r1ght time f0r change. ^^Strength to the °forconi° strength to my 9th of December °mov°ement, str°ngth to Grillo—^don't disappoint °^us, give a de^cisive push.	['hateful']	FALSE POSITIVE
41945	41954	Me to°, however^^, the problem is: - r3tires, dis^^abled citizens, an°d the p8or who dèpend on state subsidies... These aforementioned social cl°asses, combined, represent ###% of the Italian people... Therefore, before le3aving Europ3 and the 3uro, we should 3nsure the economic safety of that ###% of needy peo°ple!!! Oth3rwise, °thè inflation resulting from leaving°^ the European Üion would cause SIGNIFICANT social clashes in It@ly!!!	['hateful', 'stereotype']	UNCERTAIN
21	21	You @re °ur prlde. The "grilli" (Grillo supporters) w-ill hàndle it.	['hateful']	FALSE POSITIVE
207	207	Don't g1ve up, guys—the maïority of Italians are with you!	['hateful']	FALSE POSITIVE
302	302	"What ^^am I lea°ving to my °°children, to my grandchildren?!" We are wit^^h you! Our h3roes!	['hateful']	FALSE POSITIVE
922	923	Unlike äbroad, where p^eople go in front of government buildings and spread manùre.	['stereotype']	FALSE POSITIVE

1136	1137	We need to go to Rome! But all together, us too with trucks!	['hateful']	FALSE POSITIVE
------	------	--	-------------	-------------------

Statement: This Appendix has been translated by the authors, also with the support of Artificial Intelligence-based digital translators, following a semi-automated and supervised process.

APPENDIX C

«Pitchforks»

Cluster 1: “Total” protest

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via Deepl Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"You can't take it anymore [...] Specially because you still need to find money to pay for car insurance, road tax, the RAI fee, and everything else related to living in this housing complex."</i>	<i>you can't take it anymore [...] @lso because I don't have to take money to pay car insurance road tax rai fee and everything else involvd in the housing complex ...</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"The lives of citizens you have disrupted by driving Italian families into starvation—how can a state keep piling tax after tax on people who can't even make it to the end of the month with food? Where do they get the money? Meanwhile, the money going to those who govern us remains untouched."</i>	<i>the lives of citizens you have disrupted by bringing IT@LIAN families to starvation, how can a state continue to put tax on tax on people who do not even make it to the end of the month with food? Where do they get the money?? Inst@d the money [going]to those who govern us is not touched.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"They have allowed banks to profit off our backs through usurious rates without sanctions. Gold pensioners that cry out for justice."</i>	<i>They have allowed banks to enrich themselves on our shoulders with un sanctioned usury rates. Gold pensioners that cry out for vengeance.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Yesterday, on TV during 'La Gabbia,' a pitchfork was complaining that with taxes and other increases, they had to pay ##### euros a month. Well, I, as a regular worker, have been paying that for quite some time now. Welcome to the losers' club. Does it burn now? Where were you when you weren't paying taxes?"</i>	<i>y^esterday on TV at "la gabbia" a pitchfork was complaining that between contributions and various tax increases he had to pay ##### euros a month. Well, I as a worker employee have been paying them for quite a while. Welcome among the losers. It burns you now? Where were you when you were not paying taxes?"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"No Italian chose Europe—it's being imposed on us as a dictatorship to ruin us!"</i>	<i>no Italian chose europe is being imposed as a dictatorship to ruin us!</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"If you want to change things—from the extremely high taxation to other forms of legalized European oppression—you must not divide yourselves. It's the people, the common people, who must demand change."</i>	<i>If you want to change things from very high taxation and other forms of legalized European and other forms of dictatorship. You don't have to divide yourselves—it's the people commonly, the People who demand it.</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger

<p>"That is oppr3ssion. 3ur0pe and especia@lly the Euro, is making us st@rve."</p>	<p>That is oppr3ssion 3ur0pe especia@lly the euro makes us st@rve to de@th</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"I'm ### years old, and I've alw@ys worked. I h@ve both a higher education and a unIversity education, and I enjoy working. I wak3 up at flve in the morning to w0rk ## hours a day. [...] P0litically, I'm not left-wing, but that doesn't even matter @nymore. I demand that the lady who owns the fruit @nd vegetable shop, myself, you, and everyone else stop living in fear. I demand th@t those in power p@y f0r what they've done. I demand fair t@x@tion, and I no longer want t0 support fre3loaders. The pr0p3rty tax t3rrifies us. W3 pay ###% in t@x3s t0 support this corrupt system while remaining und3r Merkel's thumb, destr0ying all our resourc3s. FascIsm, communism... those were labels. Now there's us, ordinary p3ople—w3'r3 finally individu@ls, n0t just lab3ls. Myself, the shopk33per, th3 employ3e, the w0rker: we are the c0mmon people, united. Our flag Is the trIcolor. Am I a 'pitchfork'? If that's what it takes, then y3s, I @m a 'pitchfork'. Or better yet, we ar3 the pitchforks.'</p>	<p>I'm ### years old, and I've alw@ys worked. I h@ve both higher and unIversity education, and I enjoy working. I wak3 up at flve in the morning t0 d0 so @nd w0rk ## hours. [...] P0litically, I'm not left-wing, but that doesn't matter @nymore. I demand that the lady who owns the fruit @nd vegetable shop, myself, you, and others stop living In fear. I demand th@t those In power p@y f0r what they've done, I demand fair t@x@tion, and I no longer want t0 support fre3loaders. The pr0p3rty tax t3rrifies us. W3 pay ###% in t@x3s t0 support this bunch while staying und3r Merkel's thumb, destr0ying all our resourc3s. FascIsm, communism... those were us3d. Now there's us, ordinary p3ople—w3'r3 finally individu@ls, n0t just lab3ls. Myself, the shopk33per, th3 employ3e, the w0rker: we c0mmon people. T0geth3r, and our flag Is the trIcolor. Am I a 'pitchfork'? If this is how it works, then y3s, I @m a 'pitchfork'. Or better yet, we ar3 the pitchforks.'</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"I'm a constructi0n w0rker. To w0rk, I MUST pay into INPS (socIal securIty), INAIL (Insur@nce), @nd the construction w0rkers' fund; Without those, I can't get the paperwork I need. But there's no work, and wh@t I 3arn is barely enough to survive, whil3 these politicians keep lining their pockets. I didn't prot3st In Rome because I f0und flve days of work. Th3 choice was to protest or make a little money. I d0n't care if the movement is from the rIght, the left, the pitchf0rks,' or the 'Martelli.' I'll join the prot3st, and then... we'll see. [...] I'm tir3d of this p0lltIcs."</p>	<p>I'm a constructi0n w0rker. To w0rk, I MUST pay into INPS (socIal securIty), INAIL (Insur@nce), @nd the construction w0rkers' fund; otherwis3, I won't have the d0cumentati0n I need. But there's no work, and wh@t I 3arn is just enough to survive, whil3 these politicians keep stuffIng themselves. I didn't prot3st In Rome because I f0und flve days of work. Th3 choice was to protest or 3arn a lIttle som3thing. I d0n't care if they're from the rIght, left, pitchf0rks,' or 'martelli.' I'll join the prot3st, and then... we'll see. [...] I'm tir3d of this p0lltIcs."</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"it's 3@sy to talk @b0ut protests staying within the bounds of legality when you're sitting In a</p>	<p>it's 3@sy to talk @b0ut protests staying within the bounds of legality while sitting In a</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>comfortable armchair. Perhaps in your carefully curated world, you don't know what a crisis actually means. At best, you've read about it on Wikipedia, but you've never experienced it. You don't know what it means to make decisions like: Do I pay this damned tax and leave my employees unpaid, or do I pay their wages and then deal with the consequences? You politicians don't deserve anything you're receiving—or rather, stealing."</i></p>	<p><i>comfortable armchair. Perhaps in your carefully crafted world, you don't know what crisis means, or at best, you only know it through Wikipedia, not through experience. You don't know what it means to make decisions like: do I pay this damned tax and not pay wages, or do I pay wages and then see what happens? You politicians don't deserve anything you're receiving (STEALING).</i></p>		
<p><i>"There are people like me who have pride and great respect for you and your work! Thank you so much..."</i></p>	<p><i>There are people like me who have pride and great respect for you and your work! Thank you so much...</i></p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>
<p><i>"stealing to survive is one thing, stealing out of greed is another. But above all, driving people to suicide, as the politician class is doing, hand in hand with the bankers, is something else entirely. Of course, I have unpaid back taxes (either I was paying the house mortgage or I was paying VAT... I preferred the former), but I have every right to go to the politicians and call them thieves and murderers. Because if I couldn't pay what I didn't pay, it's because with their taxes, they would have taken even the crumbs from me. And above all I have the right to choose who should go to parliament and make laws for everyone, not just for a specific party or movement."</i></p>	<p><i>stealing to survive is one thing, stealing out of greed is another. . . but above all, it's another thing to drive people to suicide, as the politician class is doing, hand in hand with the bankers. Of course, I have unpaid back taxes (either I was paying the house mortgage or I was paying VAT . . . I preferred the former), but I have the total right to go to the politicians and send them away as thieves and murderers. Because if I could not pay what I did not pay, it is because with their taxes they would have taken even the crumbs away from me. And above all I have the right to choose who should go to parliament and make laws for everyone, not just the party/movement.</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"The malaise of the people can be felt everywhere. I, for one, am angry because, at the age of ##, after having worked so hard, I find myself without a job, and my children are forced to go abroad to work after making so many sacrifices to study. I, too, have gone to a protest with my children, but I've seen many Italians pass by muttering—people who perhaps still have a job and therefore feel safe in their comfortable positions."</i></p>	<p><i>The malaise of the people can be felt everywhere, I for one am angry because at the age of ##, after having worked so hard, I find myself without a job, my children are forced to go abroad in order to work after having made so many sacrifices to study. I too have gone with my children to a garrison, but I have seen many Italians pass by muttering, people who perhaps still have a job and therefore feel that they are in a barrel of Iron ...</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p><i>"Our politicians are too well off to understand! For them, ## euros</i></p>	<p><i>Our politicians are too well off to understand! ! ! For them ##</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>for the garbage tax or ### euros for an Instalment at Christmas means nothing. But f0r @ family of four or five, that's money taken away from food, clothing, and basic n3cessIties! And all the taxes w3 h@ve already paid @nd will continue to pay..."</i></p>	<p><i>euros of rubbish tax ### Instalment In full Christmas wh@t is that? Nothing . But f0r @ family of 4 / 5 people it is money taken away from food, clothing, basic n3cessIties! ! And all the taxes w3 h@ve paid @nd will stIll pay...</i></p>		
<p><i>"w3 are tired of this politics th@t imposes tax after tax after tax. Ther3's no work, and people are selling 3everything they have... those who have som3thIng to sell. The politicIans we're paying to run the country are governing only for themselv3s! They're always flghting for th3 biggest seat while the peopl3 are starving. We want @ president, not a puppet. We w@nt the lira back. th3 euro h@s driven us to st@rvation. We want politicIans who care about the people. p30ple are committIng suic1d3 every day, and no one notices! The return to the lIra will be traumatIc, but it is necess@ry. I could write much more, but I'll stop here. Good day!"</i></p>	<p><i>w3 are tired . . of this politIcs th@t puts taxes . . taxes and taxes ther3 is no work people are selling 3everything . . . [who has som3thIng to sell] . . the politicIans we're paying to run the country Inste@d they g0vern themselv3s! They're always flghting for th3 biggest chair and the peopl3 are starving we want @ president . . . not a puppet we w@nt the lira . . th3 euro h@s led us to st@rvation . . we want politicIans who think Of the people the p30ple are committIng suic1d3 . . every day and n0body notices ! ! ! ! The return to the lIra will be traumatIc, but it is necess@ry I can write much more, but I'll end here good day! ! ! !</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"The protests Of the last few d@ys @nd the pe0ple who have spoken out have for the flrst tIme fought against the r3al p0wer groups @nd denounced the true reasons why we ar3 starving: mon3y issued as debt and all that it entails. Dear misInformers Of Radio C@pital: unjust taxes, d3prIvatI0n of fundamental human rights, lack of w0rk, inadequate wages, incitement to suicide, @nd much more. So, @ll thos3 people who took to the streets des3rve RESPECT! Shame On those who don't see it."</i></p>	<p><i>The protests Of the last few d@ys @nd the pe0ple who have spoken out have for the flrst tIme fought against the r3al p0wer groups @nd denounced the r3@l reasons why we ar3 starving. . that is, mon3y issued in debt and all that this entails, dear misInformers Of Radio C@pital: unjust taxes, d3prIvatI0n of fundamental human rights, lack of w0rk and work for a decent wage, incitement to suicide @nd much more. So @ll thos3 people who took to the streets des3rve RESPECT! Shame On them!</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Same here: either I pay for 3lectricity, or I pay my taxes. We're all in th3 same boat, ready t0 shut d0wn. But I don't think the pIтчforks @re fascists. On the contrary, th3y ar3 pe0ple lIke us—and like the sweet old lady who was quoted earlier. @ hug, and may everything turn out f0r the b3st."</i></p>	<p><i>idem, or I pay the 3lectricity or I pay my taxes, we are all in th3 same boat. ready t0 close d0wn, but I don't think the pIтчforks @re fascists, on the contrary, th3y ar3 pe0ple lIke us and NonnIna, who was swe3tly quoted, @ hug and may it @ll work out f0r the b3st.</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>"I refer to th3 protesters from the north: tax evaders—or r@ther, those who try not to pay taxes. Breeders who have not respect3d m1lk qu0tas: the Italians pa1d 3ur0p3 for the violation, and now th3y're trying again. They would like to toppl3 the government b3c@use they long for th3 good Old days of Berlusconi, the Leghists, and so on."</p>	<p>I refer to th3 protesters from the north . Tax evaders, or r@ther they try not to pay taxes, breeders who have not respect3d m1lk qu0tas, the Italians have pa1d 3ur0p3 the Infraction and now th3y try again. They would like to toppl3 the government b3c@use they regret th3 good Old days of Berlusca, the Leghists, etc. .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Behind the prot3sts ar3 exhausted people, tired of having no rights and of paying more and more tax3s to sustain a political class that has bec0me n0thing mor3 th@n a money-s*****g machine."</p>	<p>Behind the prot3sts ar3 exhausted people tired of having no rights and having t0 pay more and more tax3s to maintain a political class that has bec0me n0thing mor3 th@n a money-s*****g one.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"W3 @re all in th3 same boat—@ boat steered by unscrupulous or incompet3nt peopl3 wh0 have set it adr1ft. A drift called Europe, which we all, to s0me extent, believed in. The people who ste3red the boat have jumped into 11f3b0ats. Now, 31ther we take th3 boat back, or th3 Germans will sink it for good."</p>	<p>W3 @re all in th3 same boat, @ boat driven by unscrupulous or incompet3nt peopl3 wh0 have set it adr1ft. A drift called Europe, in which @ll of us, s0me more, some less, believed. From th3 boat those people who ste3red it have jumped into the 11f3b0ats. Now 31ther we take th3 boat back or th3 Germans will sink it for good.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"As Opposed to europ3—at least f0r what it 1s now—we we hav3 th3 right to r3m0ve It fr0m Italy. And then, what's the po1nt of having @ European p@rli@ment s3at In Rome? This truly is th3 Europ3 of thieves and bureaucrats, cucumber measurers!"</p>	<p>as Opposed to europ3, at least f0r what it 1s now, we hav3 th3 right to r3m0ve It fr0m italy. and then what's the po1nt of having @ european p@rli@ment s3at In rome? This really is th3 Europ3 of thieves and bureaucrats, cucumber measurers!</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"I believe we must immed1at3ly l3ave 3urope and the eur0!"</p>	<p>I believe that we must immed1at3ly l3ave 3urope and the eur0!</p>	<p>[]</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The decadence 1s there for all t0 see: 3lderly peopl3 in mis3ry going to eat at Caritas, stealing food in superm@rkets Or worse, rumm@g3 through th3 garbage. ####% Of y0ung peopl3 are officially unempl0yed, and the other ####% are no longer looking for work. study1ng at univ3rsity, getting medical tr3atm3nt at the h0spital, or having a specialist visit has b3come @ luxury that few can aff0rd. [...] At the sam3 time, Italian p0litic1@ns hav3 privileges high3r than those in any other nat1on in the world, and recently the President of the Republic [...] even had h1s sal@ry Increased!</p>	<p>The decadence 1s there for all t0 see: 3lderly peopl3 in mis3ry go to eat at Caritas or steal food in superm@rkets Or worse still rumm@g3 through th3 rubbish, ####% Of y0ung peopl3 are officially unempl0yed and the other ####% are no longer looking for work, study1ng at univ3rsity, getting tr3atm3nt at the h0spital or a specialist visit has b3come @ luxury that few can aff0rd, [...] at the sam3 time Italian p0litic1@ns hav3 privileges high3r than any other nat1on in the world and recently the President of the Republic [...] has had h1s sal@ry Increased! d3spit3 all this @nd</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>d3spit3 all this, @nd d3spite the fact that electoral reimbursem3nts to parties have b3en declared unconst1tut1on@l @nd Illegitim@te, the political cast3 makes no effort to reduce the costs of politics but keeps inventing n3w taxes for the cit1zens."</i></p>	<p><i>d3spite the fact that electoral reimbursem3nts to the parties have b3en defined as unconst1tut1on@l @nd Illegitim@te, the political cast3 does not treat to reduce the costs of politics but is always inventing n3w taxes for the cit1zens</i></p>		
<p><i>"Fine words, Mr. Minister, but none of you could live @ year on what you take home in @ single month. Try lowering y0urselves to our level and living only on taxes, and th3n go cry about it 0n TV. You were elected to govern us, not to bleed us dry @nd throw us in jail f0r allegedly or not payIng t@xes. Pensioners in no other country pay IRP3F (income tax), but we pensioners, after paying taxes for all our working years, @re still paying IRPEF along with r3gi0nal and loc@l taxes. I only s@y—and sorry if it's not enough—SHAME ON YOU."</i></p>	<p><i>Fine words Mr . Minister, but none of you live @ year on a salary th@t y0u take in @ month . Try t0 lower y0urselves to our level and liv3 on taxes @lone , and th3n go lick your wounds 0n TV . . you were elected to govern us , not to bleed us , @nd thrown in jail f0r allegedly , or not payIng t@xes . Pensioners in no other state pay IRP3F , because WE pensioners after paying for all our working years , @re still paying IRPEF and r3gi0nal and loc@l taxes . . . I only s@y, and sorry if It is little, SHAME ON YOU.</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"[...] But there ar3 als0 m@ny, many ordinary people who @re fed up and, evidently, hav3 found no int3rlocutors in the parties or inst1tuti0ns. They've taken to the streets to mak3 their d1scomf0rt heard. If, instead of p@rticipating in such shows, politicians worked t0 solve problems instead of making cuts, maybe th3r3 wouldn't be so much ang3r. I don't und3restim@te the protest—I listen to it."</i></p>	<p><i>[...] But there ar3 als0 m@ny, many ordinary people who @re fed up and evidently hav3 found no int3rlocutors In the parties and inst1tuti0ns @nd have taken to the streets to mak3 their d1scomf0rt heard. If, instead of p@rticipating in such shows, they were to work t0 solve problems and not just cuts, perhaps th3r3 would not be so much ang3r. I do not und3restim@te the protest I listen to . . .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"th@t's fine with me; go ahead and say that I'm far-right. Don't c0mpl@in later when th3re are only Chinese sh0ps, when VAT rises to ####%, when you hav3 to pay for your house again and overpay for IMU/TARSU or whatever the hell it's c@ll3d now, when deductions from your salary keep fluctuating, when you go to the emergency room and face miles of queu3 with no one working, when you have to pay for ambulance services, when you can't m@k3 it t0 the end of the m0nth b3c@use the shopkeep3rs, in addition to their (s0metimes 3xaggerat3d) increases, are</i></p>	<p><i>th@t's fine with me, go ahead and say that I'm far-right ... don't c0mpl@in later if th3re will be only Chinese sh0ps, if VAT will go up to ####%, if you hav3 or are paying for your house, you will overpay for IMU / TARSU or whatever the fuck it's c@ll3d now / etc., If when y0u get your salary th3 deducti0ns keep fluctuating, if when you go to the emergency room th3re are miles of queu3 @nd no on3 works, if when the ambulance g0es out you pay for it, if you can't m@k3 it t0 the end of the m0nth b3c@use the shopkeep3rs in addit1on to their (s0metimes 3xaggerat3d)</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>drowning in taxes without earning a living, when your 730 refunds get smaller @nd smaller, and when petrol costs ### cents..."</i></p>	<p><i>increases have to pay and repay only t@xes w1thout a living, if the 730 refunds are less and less @nd you give more and more, if petrol costs ### cents ...</i></p>		
<p><i>"[...] IMU is Monti's Infamy—he wasn't ev3n voted in by th3 p3ople. ABOLISHING IMU is a duty; otherwise, all hom3owners will l0se their r1ght to their hom3s, and we'll have t0 join the list too. Fine, everyone sleep under the bridge then!"</i></p>	<p><i>[...] IMU is the Infamy of MONTI, who w@s n0t ev3n voted in by th3 p3ople. ABROG@TE THE IMU is a duty otherwise all own3rs will have the right to hav3 a h0use and we put ourselv3s on th3 list also no . COME ON 3V3RYBODY SLEEP UNDER THE BRIDGE! ! ! ! ! ! i</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"[...] Wh@t hav3 the pol1tici@ns b3en doing all these months? In a fam1ly, when th3re's a cr1sis, the flrst thing y0u do is cut absurd expenses and r0ll up your sl3eves. [...] They only w0rk on talk and lies, well-distributed through the med1a and all the Information channels that, contrary to what one of you said earlier, are mostly controlled by those who g0vern us. A very high percent@ge of y0u are uninformed, and to counter what was s@id before, let me inform y0u that even today, another Italian committed suicid3 because h3 was evicted—while de@r ill3gal imm1grants are staying in hotels, with 3ven their phone bills paid for."</i></p>	<p><i>[...] Wh@t hav3 the pol1tici@ns b3en doing all these months? In a fam1ly, when th3re 1s a cr1sis, the flrst thing y0u do is to cut absurd expenses and r0ll up your sl3eves. . . . w0rk only talk and f@lseho0ds well distributed through the med1a and all the channels of Information that, contrary to what was said befor3 by on3 of you, are In the hands of those who g0vern us in a very high percent@ge since m@ny, almost all of y0u are uninformed, without prejudice to what was s@id before, I inform y0u that even today an Italian committed suicid3 because h3 was evicted while the de@r ill3gal imm1grants are staying in hotels, 3ven paid for the telephone . .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>The thing that, unfortuately, you don't understand is that by making these protests, the politicians are Only laughing at us. believ3 me, if we really want to make @ r3al protest, let's start by no longer paying taxes. Let's stop going to b@nks or post Office, stop p@ying fines or Insurance comp@nies, and hand the IMU back to them. Let's r3bel by proposing laws in Our fav0ur. Let's take f0od vouchers @nd fu3l vouchers away from those with state jobs and giv3 th3m to those without an inc0me, and so on."</i></p>	<p><i>The thing that unfortuately you don't understand is that by making these protests the politicians are Only having @ laugh, believ3 me, if we really want to make @ r3al protest, let's start by not paying any mor3 taxes, let's not go into the b@nks or the post Office, l3t's n0t p@y fines or Insurance comp@nies, let's put the Imu In their hands. . and so on< let's r3bel by pr0p0sing laws in Our fav0ur, let's h@ve f0od vouchers @nd fu3l vouchers t@ken away from those with state jobs and giv3 th3m to those without inc0me etc</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Since January [...] one can no long3r cope [...] and perhaps, withOut a doubt, I won't pay anymore. @ls0 because I don't</i></p>	<p><i>since January . . . one can no long3r cope . . and perhaps withOut perhaps . . . I won't pay any more . . . @ls0 because I</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<i>have the money to pay for c@r insuranc3, ro@d t@x, the r@i licenc3 fee, and everything else that comes with the housing c0mplex . I'v3 decided that what littl3 money I manage to bring home, I'll spend it t0 support my family."</i>	<i>don't have the money to pay c@r insuranc3 ro@d t@x r@i licenc3 fee and everything else that the housing c0mplex 3ntails . . . I hav3 decided . . . what littl3 money I manage to take home I'm spending it t0 bring my family forward . . .</i>		
<i>"I do not like you, although I am with you. You must protest in Rome. That's where you m@ke an impact by sending Rome into cr1sis. In S1cily, you're only harming and Inconv3niencing Sicillans, who already h@v3 plenty of problems of the1r own."</i>	<i>I do not like you, although I am with you . . you must protest in Rome th3r3 you m@ke an impact by sending Rome into cr1sis . . in S1cily, you only harm and Inconv3nience the Sicillans . . who h@v3 many problems of the1r own</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"The ones who made the mistake when the Euro was intr0duc3d were thos3 who c@us3d prices to rise from one day to the next. Merchants were th3 first to mak3 us pay tw1c3 as much for food as we us3d to pay in lire. In any case, th3r3 are two Italies: one that is c0ll@psing more and m0re, and anoth3r that lives well—with luxury c@rs, families dining out in restaurants on Sundays, sh0pping In large centers, and ch@nging m0bile phones every week!"</i>	<i>The ones who made a mistake when the euro was intr0duc3d were thos3 who c@us3d prices to rise from one day to the next. Merchants were th3 first to mak3 us pay tw1c3 as much for fo0dstuffs th@n we us3d to pay in lire. In any case, th3r3 are two Italies: one that is c0ll@psing more and m0re, anoth3r that lives well with luxury c@rs, th@t goes t0 restaurants with the whole family on Sundays, always buys In large sh0pping centres and ch@nges m0bile phones every week!!!!!!!!!!!!</i>	['neg']	anger

Cluster 2: Nationalism

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via Deepl Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"ITALI@NS!!! We are ITALIANS, this is us! Italy runs thr0ugh our v3ins, from North to South, fr0m East t0 West! Lov3 for Italy must move 3very h3art and 3very person who has the luck and skill to sit in @ high seat. Whoever does not lov3 Italy to the point of weeping with em0tion at just hearing its n@me, the @nthem, or seeing its landscapes and w0rks of art—thos3 people don't deserve to be sen@tors or h0n0urables and don't ev3n d3serve t0 be called ITALIANS!"</i>	<i>ITALI@NS!!! We are ITALIANS, this is us! Italy runs thr0ugh our v3ins, from North to South, fr0m East t0 West! Lov3 for Italy must move 3very h3art and 3very person who has the luck and skill to sit on @ high seat. Who does not lov3 Italy to the point of weeping with em0tion 3v3n at just hearing its n@me, the @nthem, in seeing its landscapes, its w0rks of art ... there, thos3 don't deserve to be sen@tors and h0n0urables and don't ev3n d3serve t0 be called ITALIANS!!!</i>	['pos', 'neg']	joy
<i>"befor3 Europ3, there is ITALY!"</i>	<i>befor3 Europ3 there is ITALY!!!</i>		anger

<p>"As far as I am concerned, there is no longer a political color—they're all the same—and the only flag I respect and want to continue respecting is that of ITALY!"</p>	<p>as far as I am concerned there is no longer a political colour, they all agree, and the only flag that I respect and want to continue to respect is that of ITALY!</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p>"IT@LY SINGS ITS DI3S IRAE. ITALY IS DYING, A PEOPLE B3TR@YED AND ABANDONED, SQUEEZED @ND HUMILIATED. THE TIM3 OF RECKONING WILL COM3, THE D@Y WHEN WE, TH3 CHILDR3N OF OUR BE@UTIFUL ITALY, WILL MARCH, CLUTCHING YOUR FLAG, DEF3NDING FREEDOM AGAINST TH3 TAXES AND UNEMPLOYMENT THAT OPPRESS US. W3 YOUNG PEOPLE WILL FIGHT FOR CH@NGE."</p>	<p>IT@LY SINGS ITS DI3S IRAE. ITALY TH@T IS DYING, A PEOPLE B3TR@YED AND ABANDONED, SQUEEZED @ND HUMILIATED. THE TIM3 OF RECKONING WILL COM3, THE D@Y WHEN WE, TH3 CHILDR3N OF OUR BE@UTIFUL ITALY, WILL MARCH, CLUTCHING YOUR FLAG, DEF3NDING FREEDOM AGAINST TH3 TAXES AND UNEMPLOYMENT THAT OPPRESS US. W3 YOUNG PEOPLE WILL FIGHT FOR CH@NGE.</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"yOu might have a point, but unfortun@tely, th3 facts prov3 you wrong bec@use the averag3 Itali@n doesn't want to k1ck anyon3 out. In Febru@ry, ### m1lli0n It@lians voted to maIntain the status qu0, r3presentIng the worst of Italy. The It@lians who want to g3t rid of politic1ans ar3 th3 m0st honest Ones."</p>	<p>yOu might have a point, but unfortun@tely, th3 facts prov3 you wrong bec@use the averag3 Itali@n doesn't want to k1ck anyon3 out. In Febru@ry, ### m1lli0n It@lians voted to maIntain the status qu0, r3presentIng the worst of Italy, thos3 It@lians who want to g3t rid of politic1ans ar3 th3 m0st honest Ones.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"I completely @gree wIth your fruit vendor. My d@ughter 3xp3riences the same thing. Th3 problem is that th3 state no lOnger represents us. Ev3n In th3 last two days, we've seen the kinds of stunts th3y're capable of f0r the so-called 'go0d' of the country. Lobbies, banks, and themselves—th3se @re the only issu3s they care @b0ut. It's cl3ar th@t such a strong pr0test as the One by the 'pitchforks' gives @ voic3 to 3veryone, absolut3ly ev3ry0ne."</p>	<p>I completely @gree wIth your fruit vendor. My d@ughter 3xp3riences the same thing. Th3 problem is that th3 state no lOnger represents us. Ev3n In th3 last two days, we've seen the kinds of stunts th3y're capable of f0r the so-called 'go0d' of the country. Lobbies, banks, and themselves—th3se @re the only issu3s they care @b0ut. It's cl3ar th@t such a strong pr0test as the One by the 'pitchforks' gives @ voic3 to 3veryone, absolut3ly ev3ry0ne."</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Finally! It's about time the people rose up, but I hope the only flag waving in the squares is Italy's—the TRICOLOR! People must understand that it's no longer time for ideological divisions."</p>	<p>Finally! It's about time the people rose up, but I hope the only flag waving in the squar3s Is Italy's—the TRICOLOR! P3ople must und3rstand that it's no longer time for ideological dIvisions.</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>WELL DONE! Many police officers toOk off their h3lmets and marched with the prot3sters. The chant that</p>	<p>WELL DONE! Many police officers toOk off their h3lmets and marched with the prot3sters. The</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>

<p><i>ech03d was 'ITALY!' If we m@nage t0 k3ep this tone and determin@tIon when taking to the streets, avoidIng the violence that has h@ppened in EVERY OTHER COUNTRY, then h1story books will s@y that ITALIANS @RE GREAT, even when It comes to rev0lutions! We d0 them better!</i></p>	<p><i>chant that ech03d was 'ITALY!' If we m@nage t0 k3ep this tone and determin@tIon when taking to the streets, avoidIng the violence that has h@ppened in EVERY OTHER COUNTRY, then h1story books will s@y that ITALIANS @RE GREAT, even when It comes to rev0lutions! We d0 them better!</i></p>		
<p><i>This is a unique pr0test in Italy. Hon3st people from @ll social class3s @re pr0testing against @st@te that oppresses h0nest p3ople. It's a demonstration by a c1vil population with which law enforc3ment can also st@nd in solidarity, as it sh0uld b3 in a country where honest p3opl3 demand to be governed by serious Individuals d1rectly 3lected by th3 sov3reIgn p30ple.</i></p>	<p><i>This is a unique pr0test in Italy. Hon3st people from @ll social class3s @re pr0testing against @st@te that oppresses h0nest p3ople. It's a demonstration by a c1vil population with which law enforc3ment can also st@nd in solidarity, as it sh0uld b3 in a country where honest p3opl3 demand to be governed by serious Individuals d1rectly 3lected by th3 sov3reIgn p30ple.</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>[Pitchforks] They certainly do not represent th3 Italy of the castes, no, but at th1s hist0ric moment Italy is the one on the streets, in the squares, demanding s@cr0sanct rights for themselv3s and their children!</i></p>	<p><i>[Pitchforks] They certainly do not represent th3 Italy of the castes, no, but at th1s hist0ric moment Italy is the one on the streets, in the squares, demanding s@cr0sanct rights for themselv3s and their children!</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>[...] They h@v3 r3duced Rome t0 the capit@l of a 3uropean province. Rom3 is Caput Mundi! We will rem@ke @ differ3nt Italy, but a r3publican One that r3sp3cts Its anti-f@sc1st constitut10n. W3 will take back the South—its h1st0ry, our frequenc1es, our industries, our commerce, our banks—all n0w in the hands of th3 North.</i></p>	<p><i>[...] They h@v3 r3duced Rome t0 the capit@l of a 3uropean province. Rom3 is Caput Mundi , We will rem@ke @ differ3nt Italy , but a r3publican One that r3sp3cts Its anti-f@sc1st constitut10n . W3 will take back the South , its h1st0ry , our frequenc1es , our industries , our commerce , our banks . n0w all of th3 North .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>[...] The reasons for the protest @re sh@red by all (also by th3 forces of law and ord3r) bec@use in It@ly, th@nks to th3 EUROP3 Of the bureaucrats el3cted by no one, we no longer have a situation of normality, w3 have left the margins of civillsat10n @nd have ent3red fiscal oppression and ec0nomic dictatorship. The b@nking system Oppr3s3s th3 3uropean States with seIgnorage, which was creat3d w1th the cess10n of monetary sover3ignty and the birth of the 3URO. The European Stat3s @re</i></p>	<p><i>[...] The reasons for the protest @re sh@red by all (also by th3 forces of law and ord3r) bec@use in It@ly, th@nks to th3 EUROP3 Of the bureaucrats el3cted by no one, we no longer have a situation of normality, w3 have left the margins of civillsat10n @nd have ent3red fiscal oppression and ec0nomic dictatorship. The b@nking system Oppr3s3s th3 3uropean States with seIgnorage, which was creat3d w1th the cess10n of monetary sover3ignty and the birth of the</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>subject3d to the decis10ns and controls of th3 EUROPE@N BANKING OLIGARCHY and are forc3d to pursue policies ag@inst citizens and business3s and In p@rticular against the weaker cl@sses, ab0llshing services, reducIng publ1c investments, and increasing taxation In all forms (direct and ind1r3ct) to the point Of makIng taxes and services unpayable, r3ducIng citizens of all social categor1es to p0verty. In this c0ntext, companies go bankrupt bec@use of t0o many t@xes (ov3r ###% On 3arnings) and close down, or reloc@te their fact0ri3s or sell them and pass them On to Intern@tional groups who, thanks to their headquart3rs in tax hav3ns and fre3 zones, pay no taxes to anyOne.</p>	<p>3URO. The European Stat3s @re subject3d to the decis10ns and controls of th3 EUROPE@N BANKING OLIGARCHY and are forc3d to pursue policies ag@inst citizens and business3s and In p@rticular against the weaker cl@sses, ab0llshing services, reducIng publ1c investments, and increasing taxation In all forms (direct and ind1r3ct) to the point Of makIng taxes and services unpayable, r3ducIng citizens of all social categor1es to p0verty. In this c0ntext, companies go bankrupt bec@use of t0o many t@xes (ov3r ###% On 3arnings) and close down, or reloc@te their fact0ri3s or sell them and pass them On to Intern@tional groups who, thanks to their headquart3rs in tax hav3ns and fre3 zones, pay no taxes to anyOne.</p>		
<p>"Do not forget that th3se polit1cians were v0ted In by the Itallans. Ch@nging politicians is useless if th3 mental1ty Of th3 Itallans does not change first."</p>	<p>do not forget that th3se polit1cians were v0ted In by the Itallans. Ch@nging politicians is of n0 use if th3 mental1ty Of th3 Itallans is not changed first.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"it@ly is a slave to the ignorant cret1ns who think like him, people who dr@gged us @long with bossi, b3rlusc0ni, grillo, and others, most of whom only want t0 protect their posit1ons to the face of italians and ITALY."</p>	<p>it@ly is a slave to the ignorant cret1ns who think like him, people who dr@gged us @long with bossi, b3rlusc0ni, grillo, etc., most of whom only want t0 protect their posit1ons to the face of italians and ITALY</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"[...] The government is non-existent, capabl3 only Of making continuous declarations of Opt1mism that are immediately disproven by the f@cts th3 n3xt day. The p@rt1es have occup1ed every space— fr0m th3 ec0nomy, to information to the alloc@tion of public m0ney to feed the lobbies fr0m which their memb3rs often c0me. Italy h@s lost its monetary sover1gnty, its fisc@l sover3lgnty and is preparIng to soon lose Its ec0nom1c s0ver1gnty @s well, with the highly likely poss1bility of being strangled by the recessi0nary polici3s Of the International M0net@ry Fund."</p>	<p>[...] The government is non-existent, capabl3 only Of continuous declarations of Opt1mism immediately belied by the f@cts th3 n3xt day. The p@rt1es have occup1ed every space, fr0m th3 ec0nomy, to information, to the destin@tion of public m0ney to feed the lobbies fr0m which their memb3rs often c0me. Italy h@s lost its monetary sover1gnty, its fisc@l sover3lgnty and is preparIng to soon lose Its ec0nom1c s0ver1gnty @s well, with the more than likely poss1bility of being strangled by the</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

	<i>recessiOnary polici3s Of the International M0net@ry Fund.</i>		
<i>"It is useless to s@y that th1s mov3ment @nd this protest is apol1tical . It cle@rly is a protest l3d by the Itali@n r1ght, trying to take action but hiding behind the trivialities that Bepp3 Grillo has b3en repe@ting for months and months . [...] S0 It 1s unnec3ssary f0r you t0 block the streets of the c0untry, cla1ming th@t all Italians @re lik3 you . Start expl@ining clearly wh0 you are made up of @nd what y0u want . Ther3 are no self-org@nised movements; there is always som3one pulling th3 strings, and here, you just have to find the puppeteer."</i>	<i>it is useless to s@y that th1s mov3ment @nd this protest is apol1tical . It cle@rly is a protest l3d by the Itali@n r1ght who tries to take act1on but hid3s behind the trivialities that Bepp3 Grillo has b3en repe@ting for months and months . [...] S0 It 1s unnec3ssary f0r you t0 block the streets of the c0untry say1ng th@t all Italians @re lik3 you . Start expl@ining well wh0 you are made up of @nd what y0u want . Ther3 are no self-org@nised things, there is always som3one behind th3 game, and here you just have to find the puppeteer</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"fi0rella, it really hurts to see p30ple who sacrifice th3mselves, who h@v3 w0rk3d their whole lives, making so m@ny s@cr1f1ces, and still have to struggle just to e@rn their bread, while in the palaces of power rivers Of money flow freely. Even the most incompetent pol1tician—elected not by the citiz3ns but by the s3cretariats—is in a p0sition to take adv@ntage of th3m. Self1sh opportunists, they continuously demand s@crif1ces from Italians, who have already been struggling for so many y3ars. Meanwhile, they keep their privileg3s and wast3fulness, even inventing vote-buying schemes. People are already fed up with vot1ng, and now they're also being asked for money to vote for a p@rty that will only increas3 their taxes. It's all simply ridiculous."</i>	<i>fi0rella, it really hurts to see p30ple who sacrifice th3mselves, who h@ve m@de so m@ny s@cr1f1ces that they still have to mak3, just to e@rn their bread, while in the palaces of power rivers Of money circulate, which even the last imbec1le of a pol1tician elected not by the citiz3ns but by the s3cretariats in a p0sition to take adv@ntage of th3m, Self1sh, opportunists, they cont1nually ask for s@crif1ces fr0m the Italians who have already been in difficulty for so many y3ars, then they continue w1th their privileg3s, with their wast3, they have ev3n inv3nted pay-as-you-go votes, th3 people are already fed up with vot1ng, n0w they also demand money and then vot3 for a p@rty that increas3s their taxes more and m0re, all this 1s simply ridiculous.</i>	['neg']	sadness
<i>"This rabble, the scum of Italy, wants to proh1bit the d3monstrations of real Italians. They disguise th3mselves as trade un1onists, magistr@tes, pol1ticians, but It's they who h@ve brought Italy to this state. Now that they se3 others waking up, the 'good comrades' don't like</i>	<i>This rabble , the mud of Italy want to proh1bit the d3monstration of real Italians . They disguise themselv3s as trade un1onists , magistr@tes , pol1ticians , but It is they who h@ve brought Italy into this condition , se3ing th@t others wake up , the good comrades , . . . don't like it and invent ev3rything , thr3atening</i>	['neg']	anger

<p><i>it and invent all sorts of thr3ats, warning of reprisals if roads are blocked. These scoundrels, wh0 allow th3mselves everything when it suits th3m—dishonest th1eves, scoundr3ls—help the peopl3 in misery! Stop pretending to pl@y dumb; you are the rot Of Italy. Come on, pitchforks, d0n't be @fraid Of these cowards!"</i></p>	<p><i>reprisals if you block the roads . These scoundrels , wh0 when they act for them everything is @llowed dishonest th1eves , scoundr3ls help the peopl3 who are in misery , don't pl@y dumb , you are the rot Of Italy . Come on pitchforks d0n't be @fraid Of these cowards.</i></p>		
<p><i>"It r3ally makes me feel s@d. I am an Italian-Australi@n living In M3lbourne, and I was in Italy for a month in October. I s@w how hard life has b3come for Italians, and I feel sorry for them. Italy is s0 beautiful, and Italians are so kind—they don't deserve what is happening. It hurts me @lso because I would like to liv3 In Italy with my family. I have two daughters, tw0 and four ye@rs old, and I would love for them to discover and truly know the1r roots, but with the current situation in Italy, it's n0t possible. So cheer up, guys—I love you."</i></p>	<p><i>It r3ally makes me feel s@d. I am Italian Australi@n living In M3lbourne @nd I was in Italy for a month in October. I s@w how hard life b3comes for Italians and I feel sorry for them. Italy is s0 beautiful and Italians are so nice and they don't deserve what is happening. It hurts me @lso because I would like to liv3 In Italy with my family, I have two girls, tw0 and four ye@rs old, t0 discover and get to know the1r roots well, but with Italy it's n0t possible. So cheer up guys, I love you.</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p><i>"You can spin it all you want, but @s long as th3r3 are people Id3ntifying with this or that flag, Italy will always be in the shit! I'm reading comments: 'I l0ve M5S,' 'the communists will fix it,' [...] still t@lking about th3se flags? 'I'm a communist, you're a fascist!' Don't y0u r3@lize that It's the flags that are screwing us over? ITALIANS AND NOTHING ELSE! No commun1sts, no fascists, no centrists, etc. WE ARE IT@LIANS UNITED TO TAKE BACK OUR SOVER3IGNTY! ENOUGH WITH THE FLAGS!"</i></p>	<p><i>You can spin all you want, but @s long as th3r3 are people wh0 Id3ntify with this or that flag, Italy will always be In the shit! I'm reading comments: "I l0ve m5s" , "the communists will be there" ag@in with th3se flags? ? ? "Me communist, you fascist! !! But don't you realise or don't y0u r3@lize that it Is the flags that fuck us up? ITALIANS and NOTHING! No commun1sts , no fascists , no centrists etc. etc. . WE ARE IT@LIANS UNITED TO TAKE BACK OUR SOVER3IGNTY! AND ENOUGH WITH THE FLAGS!"</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"I agr33 with you; th3 problem h@s always been the people themselves! Th3 growing ignorance only makes them see the evil in others but not their own faults. T@ke th3 wo0d3n mirrors out of the house! Italian politic1ans hav3n't done anything abnormal—they @r3 It@lians! Many would</i></p>	<p><i>"I agr33 with you, th3 problem h@s only ever been that of the people! Th3 growing ignorance that only makes them see the evil of others but not their own! T@ke th3 wo0d3n mirrors Out of the house! The Italian politic1ans hav3 done nothing abnormal, b3cause they @r3 It@lians! Many</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>h@ve done the same if g1v3n the opportunity. Already on a small scale, people are thieves—imagine on a large scal3! With the big 3xcuse: 'I'v3 suffered until now; now I's my turn to t@ke as much as I can.' Best wishes, It@ly and Itali@ns. You c0uld stop paying taxes, but what w0uld that l3ad to? Either @ war br3aks Out, washing the streets with blood, or th3 pe0pl3 change."</i></p>	<p><i>would h@ve done as they did if th3y h@d been g1v3n such an opportunity ! Already in the small One thieves, let alone in the big on3 ! With the big 3xcuse : "I hav3 suffered until now , now It's my turn to e@t as much as I can" . Best wishes It@ly and Itali@ns . You c0uld stop paying taxes but what w0uld that l3ad to ? Oh @ war br3aks Out washing the streets with blood or th3 pe0pl3 change</i></p>		
<p><i>"Grillo is right. @ll the @rmed f0rc3s Of Italy should arrest our politicians, t@ke the Bastille! The It@lian people ar3 all in your hands. Help us so that we ar3 not suppressed l1ke lambs. W1th their trafficking of human liv3s, they are po1soning us, and worse still, they @re poison1ng Our childr3n and yours. Pol1tic1ans only care f0r themselves—they are maf1osi and corrupt."</i></p>	<p><i>grillo is right @ll the @rmed f0rc3s Of italy arrest our politicians t@ke the bastille the it@lian people ar3 all in your hands help us not to b3 suppressed l1ke lambs w1th their trafficking of human liv3s they are po1soning us come down is worse they @re also poison1ng Our and your childr3n pol1tic1ans f0r yourselves maf1osi and corrupt ...</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"[...] H0w3ver, it w@s devastating as w3ll as danger0us to be @t the mercy of these "politicians" (more th@n r0gue p0liticians). Revolts are wars and no war is won or lost w1th0ut a shot fir3d! A P3aceful rev0lution does not exist, none Of thos3 g3ntlemen will move their heavy beh1nds from their se@ts. We will do a lot of blà blà . . . and then get fooled ag@in with phr@s3s like "The crisis is 0v3r" (se3 Saccomanni yesterday). Th1ngs h@v3 to change @nd immediately! We should rath3r worry ab0ut the aftermath . Who's going to le@d th1s country? . . . but it doesn't matter . . . Revolut1on at once and let the blood of p@rli@mentarians flow, because ours is already gone! W the Itallian p3ople, W Lib3rty, W the Revolution!"</i></p>	<p><i>[...] H0w3ver, it w@s devastating as w3ll as danger0us to be @t the mercy of these "politicians" (more th@n r0gue p0liticians). Revolts are wars and no war is won or lost w1th0ut a shot fir3d! P3aceful rev0lution does not exist, none Of thos3 g3ntlemen will move their heavy beh1nds from their se@ts. We will do a lot of blà blà . . . and then get fooled ag@in with phr@s3s like "The crisis is 0v3r" (se3 Saccomanni yesterday). Th1ngs h@v3 to change @nd immediately! We should rath3r worry ab0ut the aftermath . Who's going to le@d th1s country? . . . but it doesn't matter . . . Revolut1on at once and let the blood of p@rli@mentarians flow because our . . . is already finished! ! ! ! ! W the Itallian p3ople , W Lib3rty , W the Revolution ! ! ! ! !</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Hello everyone. The question that aris3s for me is: if all th3 Italians' lar1es and pensions were divided for @ f3w years @mong all Italians—and I rep3at, Italians—do you think they wouldn't b3 able to</i></p>	<p><i>Hello everyone . The question that aris3s for me is: if all th3 Italians' s@lar1es and pensions were divided for @ f3w years @mong all Italians, and I rep3at</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>get ### euros p3r p3rson to live with dignity? Then the Other questiOn is: why is it alw@ys the same people who have to tighten their belts? Why don't the assholes in government try living on ### euros? In my opinion, in a time of crisis, ev3ryone has t0 lend a hand to Italy; otherwise, a rev0lution is the Only alt3rnative."</p>	<p>wouldn't b3 able to get ### 3uros p3r p3rson to live with dignity? Then the 0ther questiOn is: why sh0uld it alw@ys b3 the same people who have to pull on their thighs? Why don't the assholes in government try to live on ### euros? In my 0pinion, at a time of crisis, ev3ryone has t0 lend a hand to Italy, otherwise a rev0lution is the Only alt3rnative.</p>		
<p>"[...] In ### y3ars, 11b3ral Masonic gov3rnm3nts have destroyed th3 South, desert1fied it, and mass@cred 1t, just as they have massacred Our people. [...] Th3 South must rise again, give its3lf autonomy and independence, and f0und @ ONE and THREE Italy. GIVE AUTONOMY TO TH3 COMMONS, M@KE MODERN AND 3FFICIENT T@X LAWS, LIKE THE INCOME OR TONNAGE TAX3S IN @MERICA."</p>	<p>[...] In ### y3ars, 11b3ral Masonic gov3rnm3nts have destroyed th3 south, desert1fied it, mass@cred 1t. As they have massacred Our people . [...] th3 South that must rise aga1n , give its3lf autonomy and independence , f0und @ ONE and THREE Italy . GIVE AUTONOMY TO TH3 COMMONS , M@K3 MODERN AND 3FFICIENT T@X LAWS , LIKE THE INCOME OR TONNINE TAX3S IN @MERICA .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"I @m h@ppy that finally, som3thing is truly moving. Come on, men and women, there must be m@ny of you, from th3 North to the S0uth—mak3 your v0ices h3ard! At last, we want to se3 the squares filled with ITALIAN people. YOU WILL ALL BE IT@LI@NS WITH ON3 HEART AND TH3 DUTY TO GIVE OUR P3OPLE BACK THEIR LAND AND M@KE IT SO THAT ITALY CAN RECONSTRUCT ITSELF WITH LOVE @ND R3STOR@TION FOR ALL, L3AVING A BETTER FUTURE FOR ALL YOUNG PEOPLE."</p>	<p>I @m h@ppy finally som3thing is really moving, Come on, men and women, there must be m@ny of y0u, from th3 north to the s0uth, mak3 your v0ices h3ard, at last we want to se3 the squares full of ITALIAN people. YOU WILL ALL BE IT@LI@NS WITH ON3 HEART AND WITH TH3 DUTY TO GIVE OUR P3OPLE BACK THEIR LAND AND M@KE IT SO THAT ITALY CAN RECONSTRUCT ITSELF WITH LOVE @ND R3STOR@TION FOR ALL AND L3AVE A BETTER FUTURE FOR ALL YOUNG PEOPLE ...</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>
<p>"But they do represent 1t! But not the real Italy, b3c@use you politici@ns h@ve d3stroyed that One, and it no longer 3x1sts. The 'Pitchf0rks' @re try1ng to s@ve what is left of Italy, also for the future of our children (s1nce it h@s been st0len from them), and certainly not for yours, whose future is already assur3d."</p>	<p>But they do represent 1t! ! ! ! ! But not the real Italy b3c@use you politici@ns h@ve d3stroyed that One and it no longer 3x1sts. The 'Pitchf0rks' @re try1ng to s@ve the Italy that is left, also for the future of our children (s1nce it h@s been st0len from them) and certainly not for yours who's future is assur3d.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Poor Italy [...] and po0r elderly people! The more I h3ar and s33 on TV, the more afraid I am to come to Italy, ev3n for a week!"</p>	<p>Poor Italy . . And po0r Old people! The more I hear and see on TV, the more I s33 and h3ar</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>

	@bout It. I'm afraid to come to Italy ev3n for a week!		
"The r3@l sadness Is that Italians are not united—and I'm not talking about violence and revoluti0n. There is no solidarity. If we wer3 all unit3d in a sIngl3 battle—to make these gentlemen underst@nd th@t if they don't give us a br3ak, w3 will completely stop ev3rythIng for days, weeks, and m0nths—until they d0 something concret3 t0 s@ve the c0untry. As far as I am concerned, there is no longer a political color; they are all the same. The only fl@g I respect @nd want to continu3 resp3cting is th@t of ITALY!"	The r3@l sadness Is that Italians are not united, and I'm not talking about violence and revoluti0n, there is no solidarity, if we wer3 all unit3d for a sIngl3 battle and that is to make these gentlemen underst@nd th@t if they don't give us a br3ak w3 will completely stop ev3rythIng for d@ys, weeks and m0nths until they d0 something concret3 t0 s@ve the c0untry. As far as I am concerned, there is no longer a political colour, they all agree, and the only fl@g I respect @nd want to contInu3 to resp3ct is th@t of ITALY!	['pos', 'neg']	sadness
"What a mess thIs It@ly is! Now, even this peaceful but determIned initIatIve faces its first obstacle. W@r or peace? The good or the bad to get back our rigorous Italy? Oh God, I'm confused."	What a mess thIs It@ly is!! Now even this peaceful but dertemIned initIatIve . . . finds its first obstacle . . . w@r or peace? ? . . . the good or the bad to get back our rigorous Italy? Oh God, I'm confused . . .	['neg']	anger
"[...] Th3 m3asure is full; it will only g3t worse, unfortunately. Between ### and ### will be the years of t0tal collapse for It@ly. What will you tell th3 It@lian people? Will you tell us: 'Europe is asking for it'? 'It's Berlusconi's f@ult'? Will you dr@w on the same Old p0pul1st and prop@g@ndistic clichés? These excuses are beginning to wear thin even today, let alone in a couple of years."	[...] Th3 m3asure is full, it will g3t worse @nd worse unfortunately. Between ### and ### will be the years of t0tal collapse for It@ly, what will you tell th3 Itali@n peopl3? Will y0u tell us: is Europe asking for it? Is it Berlusconi's f@ult? Will you dr@w on Old p0pul1st and prop@g@ndistic war hors3s? These questI0ns are beginning not to work even today, let alon3 in a couple of years .	['neg']	anger
"In my opini0n, it is useless t0 talk about the right or the left @nd t0 engage in p0lemIcs. Our aim, and that of th3 Italians, is t0 take back our rights and what is ours, to take b@ck It@ly and send th3 pigs of pollticians away."	In my opini0n, it is useless t0 talk about the right or the left @nd t0 make p0lemIcs. Our aim, and that of th3 Italians, is t0 take back our rights and what is ours, to take b@ck It@ly and send th3 pigs of pollticians away. . . .	['neg']	anger
"The protest shOuld be extended throughout Italy; otherwise, it makes no sense. Our politicI@ns alr3ady don't care about @ll Itallans, let @lon3 just some Of them!"	The protest shOuld be extended throughout Italy, otherwise it makes no sense . . . alr3ady our politicI@ns don't glve a damn @bout @ll Itallans, let @lon3 some Of them! ! !	['neg']	anger
"W3 freed ourselves from the m0narchy, and these p3ople are w0rse than tyrants... The fact that w3 p@y while th3y pocket money	W3 freed ourselves from the m0narchy and these p3ople are w0rse than tyrants ... the fact that w3 p@y @nd that th3y pocket	['neg']	anger

<p><i>and privileges ev3n aft3r their legislatures is vomit-inducing. When I think of those who have worked their whole llves hoping t0 enjoy a bit of welfare In ret1r3ment, only to find themselves starvIng, I feel s1ck. This is an uncivil1z3d c0untry. We’ve gone b@ck centuries, even if th3 glitter of this llfe dazzles. We’re back t0 the rich g3tting r1cher and the p0or getting p0orer. It’s like something out of th3 French R3volution— except that we ar3 in Italy, and in a Republic, no less! What a shame... how we have be3n reduc3d."</i></p>	<p><i>money and privileges ev3n aft3r legislatures is vomit0us . Wh3n I think of those who have worked a lifet1me hoping t0 enjoy a bit of welfare In ret1r3ment and see themselves starvIng, I feel s1ck . . it's an uncivil1s3d c0untry . . we've gone b@ck centuries even If th3 glitter of this llfe dazzles . . we're back t0 the rich g3tting r1cher and richer and the p0or getting p0orer . . the stuff of th3 French r3volution . . except that we ar3 in Italy, and in a Republic to boot! ! What a shame . . how we have be3n reduc3d .</i></p>		
--	--	--	--

Cluster 3: Positioning of the “Pitchforks”

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via Deepl Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<p><i>"I can only s@y one thing: I will never d3fend 'd3monstr@tions like this one,' as they are organiz3d by what is most subversive, illegal, and unconstitutional that can exist. The disc0mfort and difficulties of the people @re as re@l as they were In the 1920s... ev3n th3n, fasc1sm rode on the suff3rings of the pe0ple, and we all know how that turned out."</i></p>	<p><i>I can only s@y one thing: I will never d3fend "d3monstr@tions like this one" as they are organiz3d by what is most subversive illegal and unconstitutional that can exist. The disc0mfort, and the difficulties of the people @re as re@l, as they were In the 1920s ... ev3n th3n fasc1sm rode on the suff3rings of the pe0ple, and we all know how that turned out.</i></p>	['neg']	sadness
<p><i>"But do you @lways have to break the b####s of fascists? Think of th3 s0cial centers and black blocs— th3re should b3 c0mmunist @p0l0gia. Enough is enough with the parties. We @re a people, and as a people, we must fight."</i></p>	<p><i>but do you @lways have to break the b####s of fascists? Think of th3 s0cial centres and black blocks th3re should b3 c0mmunist @p0l0gia ... enough is enough with the parties, we @re a people and as a people we must fight</i></p>	['neg']	anger
<p><i>"I d0n't think th3 "p1tchforks" ar3 f@scists... I think they are tired p30ple, just like we all are, tired 0f being h@rassed by this stat3 that is blind t0 the p3opl3."</i></p>	<p><i>I d0n't think th3 "p1tchforks" ar3 f@scists ... I think they are tired p30ple as we all are ... 0f being h@rassed by this stat3 that is blind t0 the p3opl3.</i></p>	['neg']	anger
<p><i>"Brunett@, you @r3 a tr3acher0us and evil dw@rf. Just l0oking at you makes m3 nause0us—you ar3 a cr##p."</i></p>	<p><i>brunett@ you @r3 a tr3acher0us and evil dw@rf, just l0oking at you makes m3 nause0us, y0u ar3 a cr##p</i></p>	['neg']	anger
<p><i>"Dwarf of s###t... you should g0 to w0rk. I would lik3 to know wh0 put you there, paras1te!"</i></p>	<p><i>Dwarf of s###t... you g0 to w0rk I would lik3 to know wh0 put you there paras1te!</i></p>	['neg']	anger
<p><i>"The PD no long3r knows how to justify the fact that f0r 20 y3@r it h@s b33n @llied with th3 dwarf</i></p>	<p><i>the pd no long3r knows how to justify its3lf ab0ut the fact that f0r 20 [y3@rs] it h@s b33n @llied</i></p>	['neg']	anger

<p>wh#####er. Now, any @rgument is g00d against those who @re m@king the people see what the PD sh0uld have done for the people who voted for them."</p>	<p>with th3 dwarf wh#####er, now any @rgument is g00d against those who @re m@king the people see what they sh0uld have done for th0se who voted for them.</p>		
<p>"And ev3n the delinqu3nt dwarf do3sn't give a damn about their pr0blems, merely riding the wav3."</p>	<p>and ev3n the delinqu3nt dwarf wh0 do3sn't give a damn about their pr0blems by merely riding the wav3.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p>"[Berlusc0ni] n0w supp0rts the pitchforks movement??? What one doesn't do to scrap3 t0gether s0m3 consensus...."</p>	<p>[Berlusc0ni] n0w supp0rts the pitchforks movement??? what one does n0t do to scrap3 t0gether s0m3 consensus....</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The governm3nt continues to turn a de@f 3ar and d0esn't want to hear th3 people's pr0tests. Those who v0ice the1r @nger @r3 label3d as fascists, terrorists, Or subversives. But h1story teaches us that only @fter revolutions has the people 3ver @chieved justice! The people are fed up with th3 fiscal pr3ssur3 they're under and th3 sacrific3s they have to endure. The Government should listen to the p3ople's cry bef0re it's t0o late."</p>	<p>The governm3nt continues to turn a de@f 3ar and d0esn't want to hear th3 people's pr0tests. Those who v0ice the1r @nger @r3 label3d as fascists, terrorists, Or subversives. But h1story teaches us that only @fter revolutions has the people 3ver @chieved justice! The people are fed up with th3 fiscal pr3ssur3 they're under and th3 sacrific3s they have to endure. The Government should listen to the p3ople's cry bef0re it's t0o late.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The people? What peopl3? Alongsid3 justifiably angry peopl3—unemployed, underpaid, and so on, with ev3ry right to pr0test—I see Cas@Pound, fascists, pr0vocateurs, shopkeep3rs wh0 Only give receipts under threat, right-wing @gitators who'd be delighted t0 see everything collapse. Unf0rtunately, those who ar3 right have chosen the wr0ng and danger0us comp@nions for their journ3y."</p>	<p>The people? What peopl3? Alongsid3 justifiably angry peopl3—unemployed, underpaid, and so on, with ev3ry right to pr0test—I see Cas@Pound, fascists, pr0vocateurs, shopkeep3rs wh0 Only give receipts under threat, right-wing @gitators who'd be delighted t0 see everything collapse. Unf0rtunately, those who ar3 right have chosen the wr0ng and danger0us comp@nions for their journ3y.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"[...] I believe, perhaps wr0ngly, that y0u'r3 not small business Owners burd3ned with a m0untaIn Of taxes, 3tc. Not t0 blame y0u, no! But out there, a b1t Of every0ne 1s r3present3d, perhaps even some0ne 3lse in additi0n to us."</p>	<p>[...] I believe, perhaps wr0ngly, that y0u'r3 not small business Owners burd3ned with a m0untaIn Of taxes, 3tc. Not t0 blame y0u, no! But out there, a b1t Of every0ne 1s r3present3d, perhaps even some0ne 3lse in additi0n to us.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"[...] Possible you don't realize [...] when non-f@scists go down into the square and smash ev3rything—are those okay? Just because they say they are anti-fascists and pacifists? I would say fake! Or why—because they h@ve Che on their shirts or rainbow or red flags? Fiorella, excuse me, I don't</p>	<p>... possible, you do not realise . . . when non-f@scists go down into the square and smash ev3rything . . . are those OK? . . . just because, they say they are anti-fascists and pacifists . . . I would say fake! ! . . . or , why , do they h@ve the che on their shirts or rainbow or red flags ?</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>kn0w how many fascists there are, but they are people wh0, so far, h@ven't smashed or burned @nything! They are people whose patience has run out with 'empty words'!"</i></p>	<p><i>Fiorella , excuse me , I don't kn0w how many fascists are but, they are people wh0, so far, h@ven't smashed or burnt @nything! ! ! are people whose boxes are full of "empty words" ! ! !</i></p>		
<p><i>"But the p1tchforks are not fasc1sts. unfortun@tely, the CasaPound peopl3 have joined their demonstration, and th@t's why th3y are called fascists. But inst3ad, they are just desperate people who h@ve lost their j0bs, exodus hold3rs, farmers, entrepreneurs pers3cuted by the Italian tax auth0rit13s, unemployed pens1oners, pr3c@rious workers, students—in short, they are all the people who @re hungry. So, they are n0t 'PITCHFORKS'; th3y ar3 the people from the December 9 demonstration. We should all join them and send these criminals who have b3en fooling us for ### y3ars home and leave only the y0ung p3opl3 of M5S!"</i></p>	<p><i>But the p1tchforks are not fasc1sts . . . unfortun@tely, the casa pound peopl3 have joined their demonstration and th@t's why th3y are told th3y @re fascists, but inst3ad they are just desperate people who h@ve lost their j0bs, who are exodus hold3rs, farmers, entrepreneurs, pers3cuted by the Italian tax auth0rit13s, unemployed pens1oners, pr3c@rious workers, students, in short, they are all the people who @re hungry. . . then they are n0t the PITCHFORKS th3y ar3 thos3 of the 9 december demonstration . . . we should all join them and send these delinquents who have b3en taking us around for ### y3ars home and leave only the y0ung p3opl3 of the M5S! ! !</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Stop, all of you, shouting 'To the fascist, to the f@scist,' as in the fable of the wolf. It is pr3cisely bec@use of your scaremong3r1ng that people stayed hom3 yesterd@y, giving up on legitimately protest1ng against what is ALRE@DY @ d1ctatorship!"</i></p>	<p><i>Stop, all of you, shouting "To the f@scist, to the f@scist" as in the fable of th3 wolf it is pr3cisely bec@use of your scaremong3r1ng that people stayed at hom3 yesterd@y, that they gave up legitimately protest1ng against what is ALRE@DY @ d1ctatorship! ! !</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"And calling th0se wh0 fight f0r freedom fasc1sts, while One masqu3rades as @ communist, is sh@meful! If being dictators and false for you 1s call3d fascism, for me it's called Z1onism. Those are the ones y0u want t0 deal with in th3 elected governm3nt."</i></p>	<p><i>And to call th0se wh0 fight f0r freedom fasc1sts, when One 1s a f@scist masqu3rading as @ communist is sh@meful! ! ! Fascists, if being dictators and false for you 1s call3d fascists, for me it is called Z1onists . . . are the ones y0u want t0 deal with in th3 elected governm3nt . . .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"The government c0ntinu3s to turn a deaf ear to th3 protests Of the people. wh0ev3r cries out their @nger is called a fascist, @ terrorist, or a subv3rsive. But hist0ry teaches us that only after revolut1ons have the p30ple ever succeeded in obt@1n1ng justice! The p30ple are tired of the f1scal pressure th3y endure and the</i></p>	<p><i>The government c0ntinu3s to turn a deaf ear to th3 protests Of the people, wh0ev3r cries out their @nger is called a fascist, @ t3rrorist or a subv3rsive, but hist0ry teaches us that only after revolut1ons have the p30ple succeeded in obt@1n1ng justice! ! ! The p30ple are tired of the f1scal pressure th3y are</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<i>I @m seriously worried not @bOut the p3ople wh0 ar3 in revolt but about those who cunningly take the reins. We must all do som3thing together."</i>	<i>listens to th3 people, I @m seriously worried not @bOut the p3ople wh0 ar3 In revolt, but those who cunningly take the reins, we must all do som3thing together.</i>		
<i>"I don't understand if Fiorella is afraid Of th3 socio-3con0mic s1tuat1on or of th3 fact that the "cry of the pe0pl3" bel0ngs to th3 "fascists" What does the p0lit1c@l curr3nt matter? We're in deep shit, so the important thing is th@t someone starts making themselves heard!"</i>	<i>I don't understand if Fiorella is afraid Of th3 socio-3con0mic s1tuat1on or of th3 fact that the "cry of the pe0pl3" bel0ngs to th3 "fascists" . . . What does the p0lit1c@l curr3nt matter? We're in deep shit so the important thing is th@t someone starts to make him3lf he@rd! !!</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Dear Fiorella Mann0ia, the p3ople want facts! They are t1red Of words and prom1ses"</i>	<i>Dear Fiorella Mann0ia, the pe0ple of the p3ople want facts! They are t1red Of words and prom1ses .</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"I d0 not believe that the 'pitchforks' are fascists. I think they are tired p3ople, just like we all are, tired Of beIng harassed by this stat3 that is bl1nd to th3 people."</i>	<i>I d0 not believe that the "pitchforks" are fascists . . . I think they are tired p3ople like we all are . . . Of beIng harassed by this bl1nd stat3 towards th3 people</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"And you—are you one of Forza It@lia? How much d0es the d###f p@y you?"</i>	<i>and you are one of Forza It@lia ? how much d0es the d###f p@y you ?</i>	[]	anger
<i>"Fiorella wh3n th3r3 is hung3r for work and dign1ty, there are no politic@l flags—we Only th1nk about the futur3. Wake up. This is coming from young pe0ple who are tired Of not s3eIng a tom0rrow. Feeding p1gs? Fascists @nd communists no long3r exist; there is only the PEOPL3."</i>	<i>Fiorella wh3n th3r3 is a hung3r for work and dign1ty there are no politic@l flags but we Only th1nk of the futur3 . . . wake up . . . and this is coming from young pe0ple who are tired Of not s3eIng a tom0rrow for feeding p1gs fascists @nd conunists no long3r exist there is the PEOPL3</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"Fi0rella, 'the leftist pitchforks' d0 not exist. The pitchforks are not the pe0pl3. Wh3n Berlusconi ruled, they were watching football m@tch3s. Th3y @re just four f@scist losers. That's enough."</i>	<i>Fi0rella "the leftist pitchforks" d0 not exist . The pitchforks are not the pe0pl3. Wh3n Berlusconi ruled, they watched the m@tch3s. Th3y @re four f@scist losers. And that's enough.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"I may be sick of diatribes, but this boist3rous and Overb3aring protest makes me think Of the fascist and subv3rsiv3 M@fia. And this Grillo donkey wh0 rides th3m is the m0st fasc1st and subversive of all!"</i>	<i>I may be sick of diatr0logy, but th1s boist3rous and Overb3aring protest makes me think Of the fascist and subv3rsiv3 M@fia. . . and this Grillo donkey wh0 rides th3m is the m0st fasc1st and subversive of all!</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"@ baseless compl@int—n0 one h@s threatened them. They are also p@rt of the p3ople. And Wh@t about everything the GOV3RNMENT incites and does to us?"</i>	<i>@ baseless compl@int n0 one h@s threatened them. They are also p@rt of the p3ople . Wh@t about everything the GOV3RNMENT instig@t3s t0 do to us? ? ? ? ? ?</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"There was a t1me when th3 people were defend3d by communists. But</i>	<i>There was a t1me when th3 peopl3, the pe0ple, were defend3d</i>	['neg']	anger

<i>today, the commun1sts @r3 all well-to-do, rich, very rich. And they despise the people, calling them populists, and calling the leaders of the p3opl3 popul1sts."</i>	<i>by communists. But today the commun1sts @r3 all well-to-do , rich , very rich . @nd the people they despise by calling them populists and the leaders of the p3opl3, popul1sts.</i>		
<i>"The duty of communists 1s to speak to the oppressed, to peopl3 who are struggling—n0t to the radical chic, who 1n t1mes of prosperity find it fashionable to bec0me left-w1ng. We h@ve compl3t3ly l0st our c0mp@ss."</i>	<i>The duty of communists 1s to speak to the oppressed , to peopl3 who ar3 hav1ng a hard time , n0t to radical chic who 1n t1mes of prosperity find it v3ry nice to bec0me left-w1ng . We h@ve compl3t3ly l0st our c0mp@ss .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"th3 communists in power ar3 w0rs3 than th3 f@sc1sts."</i>	<i>. . . th3 communists in power ar3 w0rs3 than th3 f@sc1sts .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Envy is an ugly thing, especially knowing that the left has done nothing for th3 people for ### years! You d0n't w@nt to st1ck to terms lik3 'fascists.' th3 left has failed on all fronts, @nd these ar3 the consequenc3s! What are you complaining ab0ut n0w?"</i>	<i>The envy is ugly knowing that the left has done nothing for th3 people for ### years! . . You d0n't w@nt to st1ck to terms lik3 "fascists" . . . th3 left has failed on all fronts @nd these ar3 the consequenc3s! . . . What are you complaining ab0ut n0w? . . .</i>	['neg']	anger

Cluster 4: Demonstration of dissent

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"W3 will all tak3 to the stre3ts on Dec. 9 to demonstrate @gainst the corrupt politic1ans and th3 s##t p0llt1cs that 1s choking us!"</i>	<i>W3 will all tak3 to the stre3ts on Dec. 9 to demonstrate @gainst the corrupt politic1ans and th3 s##t p0llt1cs that 1s choking us!!!</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"l@w enforcement stands with th3 weak3st and @gainst th1s polit1cs of th13ves"</i>	<i>l@w enforcement stands with th3 weak3st and @gainst th1s polit1cs of th13ves</i>	['pos']	anger
<i>"IN TURIN IN_v1a PO THE POLICE MARCH WITH US ARE ALL SHI3LDED IN FRONT."</i>	<i>IN TURIN IN_v1a PO THE POLICE MARCH WITH US ARE ALL SHI3LDED IN FRONT.</i>		anger
<i>"T@king off the helmet, that's wrong in @ riot uniform. So I do think they took 1t off out of solidarity."</i>	<i>T@king off the helmet, that's wrong in @ riot uniform. So I do think they took 1t off out of solidarity.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Galactic hoax as always..... the c0ps removed their helmets because all was quiet [...] and certainly not to sympathize with the protesters."</i>	<i>Galactic hoax as always..... the c0ps removed the helmets as all was quiet [...] and certainly not to sympathize with the protesters.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"m@ybe if,—not everyone, but @t least half 0f th0se who are in the streets protest1ng had paid tax3s as</i>	<i>m@ybe if, I do not s@y @ll, but @t least half 0f th0se who are in the streets protest1ng had paid</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger

<i>they should, w1thout evading a single penny, Italy would not b3 in the situation it is."</i>	<i>tax3s as they should, w1thout evading a single penny, Italy would not b3 in the situation it is.</i>		
<i>"Unfortun@tely, politics is a big business. T0o much money is Involved, @nd many get into politics pur3ly for p3rson@l ga1n or, at most, to help out a relative. Unless money is removed from politics and political p@rti3s, things will Only get worse and worse."</i>	<i>Unfortun@tely, politics is a big business. T0o much money is Involved, @nd many get into politics pur3ly for p3rson@l ga1n or, at most, to help out a relative. Unless money is removed from politics and political p@rti3s, things will Only get worse and worse.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"And wher3 were you when the oppon3nts of th1s so-called 'freetr@d3' l1beral economic policy—what th3n-M1n1ster Of the Econ0my Giulio Tremonti call3d 'cr3@tive economy'—w3re prot3st1ng in the streets?"</i>	<i>And wher3 were you when the oppon3nts of th1s so-called 'freetr@d3' l1beral economic policy—what th3n-M1n1ster Of the Econ0my Giulio Tremonti call3d 'cr3@tive economy'—w3re prot3st1ng in the streets?"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Those who say protests @re for slackers. Those who call protesters wreckers. Those who th1nk t@king to the streets 1s only to destroy things. Those who think going to th3 streets is p0intless. Those who just 'mind their own bus1ness.' Thos3 wh0 say immigrants should go home. Th0se who say it's your fault if your factory clos3s. Thos3 who say d3al with it. And n0w... th0se very people ar3 1n the str3ets themselv3s. What should all the people you abandoned for ye@rs say to you n0w, after you 3lected crim1nals for years?"</i>	<i>Those who say protests @re for slackers. Those who call protesters wreckers. Those who th1nk t@king to the streets 1s only to destroy things. Those who think going to th3 streets is p0intless. Those who just 'mind their own bus1ness.' Thos3 wh0 say immigrants should go home. Th0se who say it's your fault if your factory clos3s. Thos3 who say d3al with it. And n0w... th0se very people ar3 1n the str3ets themselv3s. What should all the people you abandoned for ye@rs say to you n0w, after you 3lected crim1nals for years?"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Simpl1fication is an art... but the probl3m is mor3 s3rious. Pollt1cs brought us to this point. It's tim3 f0r pollt1cians to do their duty by giving back what they'v3 illegally taken from @ll of us. Otherwise, It's l3gitimate f0r the 1t@lian people to get @ngry."</i>	<i>Simpl1fication is an art... but the probl3m is mor3 s3rious. Pollt1cs brought us to this point. It's tim3 f0r pollt1cians to do their duty by giving back what they'v3 illegally taken from @ll of us. Otherwise, It's l3gitimate f0r the 1t@lian people to get @ngry.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Polit1cs really n3eds a symbol1c slap from the people. The politic@l tactic of d0wnplaying popular protests 1s @ rule, but today it's starting to fail. Sooner or later, they'll r3ally h@ve to chang3 bec@use when th3 people revolt, it's truly fr1ghten1ng."</i>	<i>Polit1cs really n3eds a symbol1c slap from the people. The politic@l tactic of d0wnplaying popular protests 1s @ rule, but today it's starting to fail. Sooner or later, they'll r3ally h@ve to chang3 bec@use when th3 people revolt, it's truly fr1ghten1ng.</i>	['neg']	fear

<p><i>“Honor to the police who stand with th3 people. This is true justice. Th@nks fr0m my entire family.”</i></p>	<p><i>Honor to the police who stand with th3 people. This is true justice. Th@nks fr0m my entire family.</i></p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>
<p><i>“this was possibl3 thanks to the f@ct that the dem0nstrators were peaceful, if they h@d thrown molovs , stones , extinguish3rs and whatever at th3 cops, th3y would not have removed the1r helmets and w0uld just1fiably have charged th3m, so thank them and the demonstr@tors who h@ve been b3en civilized”</i></p>	<p><i>this was possibl3 thanks to the f@ct that the dem0nstrators were peaceful, if they h@d thrown molovs , stones , extinguish3rs and whatever at th3 cops, th3y would not have removed the1r helmets and w0uld just1fiably have charged th3m, so thank them and the demonstr@tors who h@ve been b3en civilised</i></p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“why d0n't you @lso t@ke Off yOur helmets when it Is the n0 tav d3m0nstrators? In any case, it was known that th3re were f@scist infl1trati0ns into this demonstrati0n (see the participation of cas@p0und) @nd th1s is clear proof.”</i></p>	<p><i>why d0n't you @lso t@ke Off yOur helmets when it Is the n0 tav d3m0nstrators . . . ? ? In any case, it was known that th3re were f@scist infl1trati0ns into this demonstrati0n (see the participation of cas@p0und) @nd th1s is clear proof.</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“th3y ke3p writing that it is a h0ax that policemen took off their helmets in sol1darity with the pr0testers”</i></p>	<p><i>th3y ke3p writing that it is a h0ax that policemen took off their helmets in sol1darity with the pr0testers</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“Ahahah@ah n0t true !!! The Preccint of Turin denied it today , they were not m@rching for id3ological support , but for the defense of the demonstrators @gainst possible v1olence. They d1d n0t remov3 their h3lmets out of solidarity but because th3re was no longer any r3ason to wear th3m when the dang3r was Over.”</i></p>	<p><i>Ahahah@ah n0t true !!! The Preccint of Turin denied it today , they were not m@rching for id3al support , but for the defence of the demonstrators @gainst possible v1olence . They d1d n0t remov3 their h3lmets out of solidarity but because th3re was no longer any r3ason to wear th3m when the dang3r was Over .</i></p>	<p>[]</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“Confirmed. Same for the people I spoke t0 yest3rd@y . I g0t in touch with M11@nese coordinators. V3ry serious pe0ple. We c0uldn't express ourselv3s bett3r . I @m trying to bring CITIZENS to the str33ts tomorrow to DO without bann3rs other than the tric0lour . TO DO POLITICS me@ns BEING WHERE THE HEART BEATS . The wrong th1ngs pe0ple think d0 not Inter3st m3 for n0w. There will als0 be @ time to talk and explaIn . Now is anoth3r t1me.”</i></p>	<p><i>Confirmed. Idem the people I spoke t0 yest3rd@y . I g0t in touch with M11@nese coordinators. V3ry serious pe0ple. We c0uld not express ourselv3s bett3r . I @m trying to bring CITIZENS to the str33ts tomorrow to DO without bann3rs other than the tric0lour . TO DO POLITICS me@ns BEING WHERE THE HEART BEATS . The wrong th1ngs pe0ple think d0 not Inter3st m3 for n0w . There will als0 be @ time to talk and explaIn . Now is anoth3r t1me .</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>“Even in the pollc3, as in @ll Italians, une@s3 is felt . Demonstrat3 yes but withOut violence on 3ither side . Great pollce.”</p>	<p>Even in the pollc3, as in @ll Italians, une@s3 is felt . Demonstrat3 yes but withOut violence on 3ither side . Great pollce.</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p>“### is r1ght . . that's why it would be g00d for everyone t0 take to the streets in the1r own city . . without forming groups @nd paying dues if we demonstr@te and because we are hungry. mob11s3 the squares f0r months @nd never leave your post .”</p>	<p>### is r1ght . . that's why it would be g00d for everyone t0 take to the streets in the1r own city . . without making groups @nd dues if we demonstr@te and because we are hungry mob11s3 the squares f0r months @nd never leave your post</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>“solid@rity with the protesters who ar3 moving to change Italy, because it is n0t f@1r that the money is only there f0r polit1cs and politicians while schools, healthcare and services ar3 be1ng cut back - enough is en0ugh!”</p>	<p>solid@rity with the protesters who ar3 moving to change Italy, because it is n0t f@1r that the money is only there f0r polit1cs and politicians while schools, health and services ar3 be1ng cut back - enough is en0ugh! ! !</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>“The police are like us! W3 demonstr@te pe@cefully . . without using violenc3 against the police because they are suffering from the crisis lik3 us! !”</p>	<p>The police are like us! ! W3 demonstr@te pe@cefully . . without using violenc3 against the police because they are suffering from the crisis lik3 us! !</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>Do3s it seem normal to y0u that in a civilised country ###% Of young people are unemployed? Or that th3 main activity of accountants today is liquidating compan1es or preparing bankruptcies? I h0p3 that y0u, who @mong other things because of the exper1ence we have in c0mm0n sh0uld be s3nsitiv3 to the solidarity/ch@rity asp3ct and have a genuine rel@t10nship with President Letta, can do a lot, first of all by w0rking to bring polit1cs b@ck into contact w1th soc1ety (in this regard, @s I h@ve alre@dy had the opp0rtun1ty to @sk you, giv3 us b@ck the chanc3 to choose who to send t0 parliam3nt, ev3n if it is the l@st p3rson on the el3ctoral list, and forget about alchemy such as single-member c0nstituencies, which would greatly reduce the possibility of popular 3xpression), tackling th3 problems and n0t pretending nothing is happening.</p>	<p>Do3s it seem normal to y0u that in a civilised country ###% Of young people are unemployed? Or that th3 main activity of accountants today is t0 liquidate compan1es or prepare bankruptcies? I h0p3 that y0u, who @mong other things because of the exper1ence we have in c0mm0n sh0uld be s3nsitiv3 to the solidarity/ch@rity asp3ct and have a genuine rel@t10nship with President Letta, can do a lot, first of all by w0rking to bring polit1cs b@ck into contact w1th soc1ety (in this regard, @s I h@ve alre@dy had the opp0rtun1ty to @sk you, giv3 us b@ck the chanc3 to choose who to send t0 parliam3nt, ev3n if it is the l@st p3rson on the el3ctoral list, and forget about alchemy such as single-member c0nstituencies, which would greatly reduce the possibility of popular 3xpression), tackling th3 problems and n0t pretending nothing is happening.</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>“I don't feel represented by th3se people e1ther, wh0 are going to th3 stre3ts with the sole objective Of sending Parliam3nt home, putting good people, b@d p3ople, h0n3st pe0ple, dish0nest peopl3, in a single cauldron, and strang3ly 3nough, now th@t Berlusconi has also gone. When there w3re hundreds of thousands of peopl3 in the streets (work3rs, pensioners, students, empl0yees), On some Occasi0ns even more than a milli0n, weren't people tired? Or does it have something to do w1th the fact that the media did not devote even a qu@rter Of the space to those people? And if "the p3ople" no l0nger feel represented, wh0 d0 we send to govern the c0untry? The military as propos3d by the Venet0 l3ader of the m0v3ment? I'll even tell y0u If y0u don't w@nt to hear it : it's populist talk”</i></p>	<p><i>I don't feel represented by th3se people e1ther, wh0 are going to th3 stre3ts with the sole objective Of sending Parliam3nt home, putting good people, b@d p3ople, h0n3st pe0ple, dish0nest peopl3, in a single cauldron, and strang3ly 3nough, now th@t Berlusconi has also gone. When there w3re hundreds of thousands of peopl3 in the streets (work3rs, pensioners, students, empl0yees), On some Occasi0ns even more than a milli0n, weren't people tired? Or does it have something to do w1th the fact that the media did not devote even a qu@rter Of the space to those people? And if "the p3ople" no l0nger feel represented, wh0 d0 we send to govern the c0untry? The military as propos3d by the Venet0 l3ader of the m0v3ment ? I'll even tell y0u If y0u don't w@nt to hear it : it's qualun1st talk .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"I share Puglia's thoughts, just on3 recomb3ndation: If you take to the streets with the "pitchforks" (this one went OK, but there w1ll be Other demonstrati0ns anyway : -) , say so that you @re n3w to p0l1tics! @nd abov3 all . . . w0rkers .”</i></p>	<p><i>"I share Puglia's thoughts, just on3 recomb3ndation: If you take to the streets with the "pitchforks" (this one went OK, but there w1ll be Other demonstrati0ns anyway : -) , say so that you @re n3w to p0l1tics! @nd abov3 all . . . w0rkers .</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“And we must understand th@t th3 era of chattering is Over, th@t p0l1tics won't listen to us if we don't start rebelling ser1ously, that we can't just keep chattering us3l3ssly among ourselves. I repeat, let us go on television (as Boldr1n r1ghtly d1d this even1ng) but not only the l3@d3rs, WE too! If p0l1tics does not have @ gl0bal vis1on of the times it will fail, that's for sure. What I criticis3 ab0ut Fare at the moment 1s th3 w@it-and-se3 attitude in the face of the country's n3eds .”</i></p>	<p><i>And we must understand th@t th3 era of chattering is Over, th@t p0l1tics won't listen to us if we don't start rebelling ser1ously, that we can continue chattering us3l3ssly among ourselves. I repeat, let us go on television (as Boldr1n r1ghtly d1d this even1ng) but not only the l3@d3rs, WE too! If p0l1tics does not have @ gl0bal vis1on of the times it will fail, that's for sure. What I criticis3 ab0ut Fare at the moment 1s th3 w@it-and-se3 attitude in the face of the country's n3eds .</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>“But that in my op1nion . . . we sh0uld have dem0nstrated in Rom3, made @n irruption and arrest3d these b@stards for high treason! You w@nt to demonstr@te @nd be</i></p>	<p><i>But that in my op1nion . . . we sh0uld have dem0nstrated in Rom3, made @n irruption and arrest3d these b@stards for high treason! You w@nt to</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<i>prom1s3d again that things will ch@ng3 and then go back to squar3 on3 . . . or bring in r3nzi, who, if you haven't understo0d, h@s been put in just as @ front for the motto 'the new that advances'...</i>	<i>demonstr@te @nd be prom1s3d again that things will ch@ng3 and then go back to squar3 on3 . . . or bring up r3nzi, who, if you haven't understo0d, h@s been put in just as @ front for the motto the new that advances . . .</i>		
<i>"traffic has not b33n paralys3d, but d1ff1culties have certainly been cr3ated. What pr1c3 are you willing to pay for your future ? How do you th1nk y0u c@n mak3 your vo1c3 heard WHERE IT IS NEEDED, not her3 on FB . Letta doesn't read us On FB and wh@t you @nd I say doesn't matt3r. But th3 square does not."</i>	<i>traffic has not b33n paralys3d, but d1ff1culties have certainly been cr3ated. What pr1c3 are you willing to pay for your future ? How do you th1nk y0u c@n mak3 your vo1c3 heard WHERE IT IS NEEDED , not her3 on FB . Letta doesn't read us On FB and wh@t you @nd I say doesn't matt3r. But th3 square does not.</i>	['neg']	anger

Cluster 5: The “Pitchforks” and the leader Grillo

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"With wh@t face do you call Grillo @ sc0undrel? True, you COMMUNISTS h@ve blink3rs, but take a go0d look ins1de the PD and PDL or FI - c0mpared to what's inside them, Grillo is more candid than a sw@n."</i>	<i>with wh@t face do you call Grillo @ sc0undrel? True that you COMMUNISTS h@ve blink3rs, but take a go0d look ins1de the PD and PDL or FI what is ins1de, c0mpared Grillo is more candid than a sw@n.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Come down with us our l3ad3r Gr1ll0 [...] Go pitchforks go Grillo don't let us d0wn"</i>	<i>come down with us our l3ad3r Gr1ll0 [...] Go pitchforks go Grillo don't let us d0wn</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"DO not make the m1stake of mixing Grillo w1th thos3 s##ts. Grillo is a movem3nt, like y0u, and c@me to parliament with th3 people"</i>	<i>d0 not make the m1stake of mixing Grillo w1th thos3 s##ts. Grillo is a movem3nt, like y0u, and c@me to parliament with th3 people</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"Surely beh1nd the thugs of the so-called pitchforks are fasc1sts and Nazis, casa pound @nd th@t pr3judiced thug Grillo"</i>	<i>surely beh1nd the thugs of the so-called pitchforks are fasc1sts and Nazis, casa pound @nd th@t pr3judiced thug Grillo</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Renz1 is als0 prejudiced, just lik3 his crony Berlusconi."</i>	<i>Renz1 is als0 prejudiced, lik3 his crony Berlusconi.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>Ahah@ I am pleased, the caste has not yet realized that the more they grope in the dark, th3 more the FSM g@ins support... onward l1k3 this - 3v1dently, is th3 right way to remove the rot...</i>	<i>ahah@ I am pleased, the caste has not yet realized that the more they grope in the dark, th3 more the FSM g@ins support... onward l1k3 this 3v1dently is th3 right way to remove the rot...</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"Let m3 assure y0u, Presid3nt, that if all th3 pr0testers had jobs and earn3d ev3n @ th1rd of your</i>	<i>"Let m3 assure y0u, Presid3nt, that if all th3 pr0testers had jobs and earn3d ev3n @ th1rd of</i>	['neg']	anger

<p><i>salary, th3re would be no p1tchforks,' no Gr1llo, and no 5-Star M0vement. If th3 pitchf0rks,' Grillo, and the 5-Star Mov3ment ex1st, it's because of you, wh0 are impov3rishing Italy @nd stealing th3 future of the next gen3rations. We've3 reached th3 p01nt 0f no r3turn: it's either you or us."</i></p>	<p><i>your salary, th3re would be no p1tchforks,' no Gr1llo, and no 5-Star M0vement. If th3 pitchf0rks,' Grillo, and the 5-Star Mov3ment ex1st, it's because of you, wh0 are impov3rishing Italy @nd stealing th3 future of the next gen3rations. We've3 reached th3 p01nt 0f no r3turn: it's either you or us."</i></p>		
<p><i>"T0morrow, peopl3 will @lso pr0test against you... sellouts!"</i></p>	<p><i>T0morrow, peopl3 will @lso pr0test against you... sellouts!</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"grillo @nd activists have always been on_the_road, it s3ems unwise of y0u t0 s3nd them to_that_c0untry too . . . Grillo (people) and on the str3ets th3re are not Only you dear pitchforks . . ."</i></p>	<p><i>grillo @nd activists have always been on_the_road, it s3ems unwise of y0u t0 s3nd them to_that_c0untry too . . . Grillo (people) and on the str3ets th3re are not Only you dear pitchforks . . .</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Their t3rror 1s that Grillo will run f0r the Europ3@n elections , so they prepare the ground , a specious denunciat1on @nd then @ttack him by claiming th@t h1s cand1dacy only serves to @void a c0nvict1on . That he is a profit33r1ng thug like the 0thers . But what th3y don't know, Or rather they don't say, is that Grillo, having been convicted of a car accident 30 years ago (which h@s nothing to do with pol1t1cs) 1s in any case not a candidate. H3 isn't, but @bove all he doesn't want to be , because if he did, he w0uld have created rules to allow it, 3v3n in defiance of this conv1ct1on . P0or country , where those who g0vern instead of addressing the pr0bl3ms that drive citiz3ns t0 suicide Only th1nk @bout how to 0ust honest citizens (I speak of the M5S c@ndidates) from politics ."</i></p>	<p><i>Their t3rror 1s that Grillo will run f0r the Europ3@n elections , so they prepare the ground , a specious denunciat1on @nd then @ttack him by claiming th@t h1s cand1dature only comes to @void a c0nvict1on . That he is a profit33r1ng thug like the 0thers . But what th3y don't know, Or rather they don't say, is that Grillo, having been convicted of a car accident 30 years ago (which h@s nothing to do with pol1t1cs) 1s in any case not a candidate. H3 is n0t , but @bove all he h1mself d0es not want to be , bec@use in_the_c@se_of_the_contrary he w0uld have created rules to be so in defiance 3v3n of this conv1ct1on . P0or country , where those who g0vern instead of th1nking about the pr0bl3ms that lead citiz3ns t0 suicide Only th1nk @bout how to 0ust honest citizens (I speak of the M5S c@ndidates) from politics ."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"F##k stupid comments. People h@ve their ##### full and nobody d03s a damn thing. Everyone's talking @bout pitchforks th1s and crickets that. But realize how r1dicolous you ar3 t0 still defend pe0ple who have been screwing us f0r more th@n twenty years. ENOUGH 3NOUGH ENOUGH</i></p>	<p><i>F##k stupid comments. People h@ve their ##### full and nobody d03s a damn thing. All talking @bout pitchforks th1s and crickets that. But realise how r1dicolous you ar3 t0 still defend pe0ple who have been screwing us f0r more th@n twenty years. ENOUGH</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>ENOUGH ENOUGH . STOP TAKING IT OUT ON PEOPLE WHO ARE AT LEAST TRYING AND F@ILING. YOU PLAY THE GAME OF THE CORRUPT. YOU PREF3R TO DEFEND PEOPLE LIKE THAT AND CRITICIZE GRILLO FORCONI AND ### . STOP IT YOU ARE P@THETIC . WAKE UP YOU STUPID IDIOTS AND INSTE@D OF CRITICISING DO YOUR PART."</p>	<p>3NOUGH ENOUGH ENOUGH ENOUGH . STOP TAKING IT OUT ON PEOPLE WHO ARE AT LEAST TRYING AND F@ILING. YOU PLAY THE GAME OF THE CORRUPT. YOU PREF3R TO DEFEND PEOPLE LIKE THAT A`CRITICISING GRILLO FORCONI AND ### . STOP IT YOU ARE P@THETIC . WAKE UP YOU STUPID IDIOTS AND INSTE@D OF CRITICISING DO YOUR PART.</p>		
<p>"These p@r@sites no longer kn0w how and wh3re to climb. . . they blam3 Grillo on b#####t. If I were the cops, I would be Off3nd3d, they aren't ### to be c0nvinc3d by Grillo, It is clear that th3y are afra1d that Gr1llo will tak3 away the1r v0tes, these ### b#####s . "</p>	<p>These p@r@sites no longer kn0w how and wh3re to climb. . . they blam3 Grillo on b#####t, in the place of th3 cops I would be Off3nd3d, they are not ### to be c0nvinc3d by Grillo, It is clear that th3y are afra1d that Gr1llo will tak3 away the1r v0tes, these ### b#####s</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"ridiculous- but since they can't find anything b3tter, now the @tt@ck 1s on grill0. flrst ther3 was berluscon1 now instead 1t's all chow mein: renzi, berluscon1 then they go to gr1ll0"</p>	<p>ridiculous but they can't find anything b3tter now the @tt@ck 1s on grill0 flrst ther3 was berluscon1 now instead 1t's all chow mein renzi berluscon1 then they go to gr1ll0</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Se3Ing that they can n0 longer stop him 3ven w1th boorish propagand@, th3y are now trying t0 intimidate him through denunciations. If they don't succ3ed with that, wh@t w1ll they do next? By the way, if they hope t0 st0p the m5s by d3nouncing Grillo, they still haven't underst0od that the m5s is not like Forza It@1la with Berlusconi, and they run the risk (for them) of making figur3s like Di Battista, Di M@io and T@verna grow 3ven m0re. They @re so much desperate now that they're 'shooting' blindly and without thinking."</p>	<p>Se3Ing that they can n0 longer stop him 3ven w1th boorish propagand@, th3y are now trying t0 d0 s0 with intimidation through denunciations. If they don't succ3ed 3v3n w1th those, wh@t w1ll they do next? By the way, if they hope t0 st0p the m5s by d3nouncing Grillo, they still haven't underst0od that the m5s is not like Forza It@1la with Berlusconi, and they run the risk (for them) of making figur3s like Di Battista, Di M@io and T@verna grow 3ven m0re. By n0w they @re so much @t the brink that they "shoot" blindly and without thinking.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"You have l0st the @bility and ideals of the left, you @r3 pond and sw@mp in unison. m5s has und3rst0od the people and unmm@sked the system. and what @bOut tox1c waste? You h@ve turned the south int0 an open-sky toxic bomb. . . congratulat1ons V3ndola . one Of the many st@te</p>	<p>You have l0st the @bility and ideals of the left, you @r3 pond and sw@mp in unison. m5s has und3rst0od the people and unmm@sked the system. and what @bOut tox1c waste, you h@ve turned the south int0 a toxic bomb in open skies. . . congratulat1ons V3ndola . one</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>secr3ts Of th1s country . this is state secret politics . Shut up or they'll eat us aliv3! Grillo didn't give in. The palace and all of you are eating your ###."</i></p>	<p><i>Of the many st@te secr3ts Of th1s country . this is state secret politics . Shut up or else they'll eat us aliv3! Grillo didn't give in. The palace and all of you are eating your ###.</i></p>		
<p><i>"Shall we s3e that Grillo is n0w to be condemned? @nd all the others who @re still out there despite the1r m1sdeeds and 3mbezzlem3nts —what should we do with them? Give them th3 death sentenc3? If so , th3n I agr3e , Otherw1se , g0 Grillo and M5S, you h@ve my vote guaranteed."</i></p>	<p><i>Shall we s3e that Grillo is n0w to be condemned? @nd all the others who @re still ahead of the despite the1r m1sdeeds and 3mbezzlem3nts what do they do , give them th3 death sentenc3 ? If so , th3n I agr3e , Otherw1se , g0 Grillo and M5S wh0 h@ve my vote guaranteed</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"So Renzi isn't go0d, neither 1s Gr1llo. Don't tell me B3rlusconi 1s go0d because I'll vomit, s0 what should we d0 in your opin1on? Go al0ng with those from casa_pound who certainly d0n't care about the veget@ble gr0wer under the house wh0 doesn't make it t0 the end of the m0nth, but only about punching someone and taking_the_plac3_of_those of those in power now? Beware of being s0 defeatist, there is a gr3at risk hov3ring over our heads, those of casa_pound are the evil not the solution."</i></p>	<p><i>So Renzi is not go0d, neither 1s Gr1llo go0d, don't tell me that B3rlusconi 1s go0d because I'll vomit, s0 what should we d0 in your opin1on? Go al0ng with those from casa_pound who certainly d0n't care about the veget@ble gr0wer under the house wh0 doesn't make it t0 the end of the m0nth, but only about punching someone and taking_the_plac3_of_those wh0 hav3 it n0w . Beware of being s0 defeatist, there is a gr3at risk hov3ring over our heads, those of casa_pound are the evil not the solution.</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Whoever thinks that c@ging Grillo will block the movement has understood noth1ng. The movem3nt 1s not a party. Its leaders are b0rn out of fug1t1ves and the path is already mapped out, just foll0w it . By blocking Bepp3 you do n0thing but comp@ct but compact the movement and make th3 shock wave grow 3ven str0ng3r and more devastating. They want to hand the country over to us on a silver platter let us win ."</i></p>	<p><i>Whoever thinks that c@ging up Grillo blocks the movement has understood noth1ng. The movem3nt 1s not a party, but in method the leaders are b0rn as fug1t1ves and the way is mapped out just foll0w it . By blocking Bepp3 you do n0thing but comp@ct and make th3 shock wave grow and it w1ll be 3ven str0ng3r and more devastating. They want to hand the country over to us on a silver platter let us win .</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"but who is resp0nsible for the pitchforks? the malapolitics of thes3 years of both national @nd l0cal government, c0rrupti0n, think1ng of one's own personal interests instead Of those of all c1tiz3ns. i don't know if there will be a remedy for all this rot, certainly n0t with th3 p1tchforks</i></p>	<p><i>but who is resp0nsible for the pitchforks? the malapolitics of thes3 years of both national @nd l0cal government, c0rrupti0n, think1ng of one's own personal interests instead Of those of all c1tiz3ns. i don't know if there will be a remedy for all this rot, certainly n0t with</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>st1rr3d up by grill0 and berlusca. . . ."</p>	<p>th3 p1tchforks st1rr3d up by grill0 and berlusca. . . .</p>		
<p>"putting italy in renz1's hand? Are you joking? Napolitano? It m@kes me sick just pronounc1ng his name , h3 gav3 himself the j0b , he's colluded and dirty up to his ears Pitchforks ? more_than_cool_pick3ting_poles, solidarity from Milan I only say ' ' Vadavialcù ' ! ! ! ! ! Only Grillo and M5S . . say and speak with full knowledge of the facts and data at hand, not four pre-packaged m@ver1cks"</p>	<p>putting italy in renz1's hand? Are you joking? Napolitano? It m@kes me sick just pronounc1ng his name , h3 gav3 himself the j0b , he's colluded and dirty up to his ears Pitchforks ? more_than_cool_pick3ting_pole s, solidarity from Milan I only say ' ' Vadavialcù ' ! ! ! ! ! Only Grillo and M5S . . say and speak with full knowledge of the facts and data at hand, not four pre-packaged m@ver1cks</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Se3 you at the next polls dear well-meaning #### . W the M5S and W the great @nd immens3 Beppe Grillo"</p>	<p>Se3 you at the next polls dear well-meaning #### . W the M5S and W the great @nd immens3 Beppe Grillo</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>
<p>"But I wonder? Shouldn't you also be angry . since you put all the bl@me on th3 r1ght-w1ng governm3nt . You were asleep. How On earth did Grillo get all th0se vot3s? Thos3 votes sh0uld have been ours . . But you slept and supported the F0rnero l@w with0ut batting an eyelid @nd stol3 everything that could be stolen. We'll ch@nge. We'll change. . . w0rds in the w1nd . . you ar3 tir3d. I am on the left and I w1ll always be on the left, I didn't vote for Grillo . . but you pe0ple are pitiful . ."</p>	<p>But I wonder? Shouldn't you also be angry . since you put all the bl@me on th3 r1ght-w1ng governm3nt . You were asleep. How On earth did Grillo get all th0se vot3s? Thos3 votes sh0uld have been ours . . But you slept and supported the F0rnero l@w with0ut batting an eyelid @nd stol3 everything that could be stolen. We'll ch@nge. We'll change. . . w0rds in the w1nd . . you ar3 tir3d. I am on the left and I w1ll always be on the left, I didn't vote for Grillo . . but you pe0ple are pitiful . .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Usual d1scourse from th0s3 who hav3 no @rguments, first you launch slogans 4_money se3 car grillo or ' 5s xs how did it start? with vaffaday? Did it have proposals? " th3n wh3n you are contradicted you disappe@r and br@nd it all as hooey or bullshit rath3r th@n admit to having said n0nsense, I cringe when they compare the movement to you f@sc1sts, useless pe0ple who have never studi3d history. And when it comes t0 your be@utiful strong and tough Mussolini, be thankful they hung him in a public square!"</p>	<p>usual d1scourse Of th0s3 who hav3 no @rguments, first you launch slogans 4_money se3 car grillo or ' 5s xs how did it start? with vaffaday? h@d the proposals? " th3n wh3n you are contradicted you disappe@r and br@nd it all as hooey or bullshit rath3r th@n admit to having said n0nsense, I cringe when they compare the movement to you f@sc1sts, useless pe0ple who have never studi3d history a when partit comes t0 th3 be@utiful strong and tough Mussolini, thank_much_that_th3y_have_hung_h1m_in_the_public_place !</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Brilliant . . now a holy alli@nce berlusconi , grillo , forconi @nd</p>	<p>Brilliant . . now holy alli@nce berlusconi , grillo , forconi @nd</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>fear</p>

<i>casa_pound . . Italy wake up b3f0re_it's too late , I'm g3tting re@lly worried"</i>	<i>casa_pound . . Italy wake up b3f0re_it's too late , I'm g3tting re@lly worried</i>		
<i>"They want to stop Grillo @t_all_c0sts? Well go ahead , h3 predict3d 3veryth1ng . The more they @ttack him, the m0re M5S gr0ws. Thank y0u."</i>	<i>They want to stop Grillo @t_all_c0sts? Well go ahead , h3 predict3d 3veryth1ng . The more they @ttack him, the m0re M5S gr0ws. Thank y0u.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Fine w0rds, you ar3 th3 se3n ones, study hist0ry and you will understand that the great revolutions were n0t made with kindness but rath3r with the h@rd3st struggle. You h@v3 to t@ke them out even by forc3 b3cause with fin3 words you don't get anywhere. You are showing yourselves to be weak @nd cow@rdly."</i>	<i>Fine w0rds, you ar3 th3 se3n ones, study hist0ry and you will understand that the great revolutions were n0t made with goodness but rath3r with the h@rd3st struggle. You h@v3 to t@ke them out even by forc3 b3cause with fin3 words you don't get out Of th3r3 @nd you are showing yourselves to be weak @nd cow@rdly.</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"But why does M5S still lean on Gr1llo's crutch? You have grown @s a political form@t1on , you hav3 good id3as and the people's syst3m , y0u no longer ne3d th@t "megaphone-man" who creat3s more problems than he solves . I hop3 this doesn't le@d to things like "save-Grillo decr3e" or oth3r similar nonsense."</i>	<i>But why does M5S still st@nd on Gr1llo's crutch? You have grown @s a political form@t1on , you hav3 good id3as and the people's syst3m , y0u no longer ne3d th@t "megaphone-man" who creat3s more problems than he solves . I hop3 this doesn't le@d to things like "save-Grillo decr3e" or oth3r similar @menities . . .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"The words th@t Beppe Grillo is p0sting as w3ll as the letter he has written are clear and aimed at supporting the prot3st_of_th3_forconi t00, and I really b3liev3 that voters who care ab0ut the m5s @ls0 fully embrace th3 protest that y0u ar3 enthusiastically l3ading. Let's continue In th1s way for the goal that unites us, "freedom and dignity". I don't und3rstand a th1ng @bout politics, but I believe that the current politici@ns know as much as I do, sSo let's send them home, and as a final liqu1dation g1ft, let them be g1ven an el3ctronic bracelet f0r their misdeeds."</i>	<i>The words th@t Beppe Grillo is p0sting as w3ll as the letter he has written are clear and aimed at supporting the prot3st_of_th3_forconi t00, and I really b3liev3 that th3 voters who care ab0ut the m5s @ls0 fully espouse th3 protest that y0u ar3 enthusiastically l3ading. Let's continue In th1s way for the goal that unites us, "freedom and dignity". I don't und3rstand a th1ng @bout politics, but I believe that the current politici@ns know as much as I do, so let's send them home as I am In my plac3, and as a l@st liqu1dation g1ft, let them be g1ven an el3ctronic bracelet f0r their misdeeds.</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"So y0u @re not being paid by Berlusconi but by Renzi . . . It's @ll the same in the 3nd ! ! !"</i>	<i>So y0u @re not being paid by Berlusconi but by Renzi . . . It's @ll the same in the 3nd ! ! !</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"If w3 w@1t for R3nzi we're done for! A n3w Berlusc0ni in disguise . . ."</i>	<i>If w3 w@1t for R3nzi we're fresh! A n3w Berlusc0ni in disguise . . .</i>	['neg']	anger

«Tractors»

Cluster 1: anti-Eu

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
"Europe kills..... □□□□□□□□... Italex1t... □□□□□□□□"	Europe kills..... □□□□□□□□... Italex1t... □□□□□□□□	['neg']	anger
"Since joining Europe, OUR POLITICIANS h@ve never pr0t3cted made in italy."	Since joining Europe, OUR POLITICIANS h@ve never pr0t3cted made in italy.	['neg']	anger
"(...) Europe has something to do with It in sofar as the demand to not cultivate l@nd and to decid3 what is cultiv@ted in a natlon @nd what is not is its responsibllity, th3 Italian governm3nt is even m0re gully b3cause it h@s endorsed these policies by sIgning them and, furthermore, by raIasing taxes and taking away Incentives and aid from farmers! [...] In @dditi0n, it dares to deceive f@rmers by pretending to fight for them"	(...) Europe has something to do with It in sofar as the demand to not cultivate l@nd and to decid3 what is cultiv@ted in a natlon @nd what is not is its responsibllity, th3 Italian governm3nt is even m0re gully b3cause it h@s endorsed by sIgning these p0llcies and for more to raise taxes and tak3 away Incentives and aid from farmers! [...] In @dditi0n, it allows itself to t@ke_in_f@rmers by saying It is fighting for them	['neg']	anger
"###% of th3ir [the Tractors protestIng] demands ar3 about the agricultural tax reinstated by Giorgia, t@x-breaks on fuels that Giorgia took @w@y , (...) on th3 us3 0f pesticides, they [the Tr@ctors]ar3 NOT right, remember th@t m@ny canc3r p@thologies derive pr3cisely from these "	###% of th3ir [the Tractors protestIng] demands ar3 the agricultural tax put back by giorgia, t@x-breaks on fuels, taken @w@y by giorgia, (...) on th3 us3 0f pesticides, they [the Tr@ctors]ar3 NOT right, remember th@t m@ny canc3r p@thologies pr3cisely from these derlv3.....	['neg']	anger
"we didn't say this government is to blame... the prlv@tizations actually start3d b@ck in th3 #####s under the l3ft1st government. How3v3r, this government is following the same p@th @s the prevIous ones, and the minIster's words are outrageous! The issue isn't about parties but about sne@ky inter3sts th@t ev3ryone bows to for their own gain! Italian parties, foreign ones, pollticians, multinationals, banking systems,	we didn't say this government is to blame... the prlv@tizations actually start3d b@ck in th3 #####s under the l3ft1st government. How3v3r, this government is following the same p@th @s the prevIous ones, and the minIster's words are outrageous! The issue isn't about parties but about sne@ky inter3sts th@t ev3ryone bows to for their own gain! Italian parties, foreign ones, pollticians,	['neg']	anger

<p>@nd shady Individuals @r3 a monstrous problem! ..."</p>	<p>multinationals, banking systems, @nd shady Individuals @r3 a monstrous problem! ...</p>		
<p>"What Europe? The current state of this empty shell—this Europ3 of merchants—is und0ubt3dly serious, especially bec@us3 it @ffects the anthropological @nd cultural f@bric, and thus Europe’s inn3r consci0usness itself. The serious cr1s1s hitting Europe st3ms from the d3sire to elimin@te Chr1stian @nd human values from its life and conscience. We await the upcoming European 3lect1ons w1th h0pe, eager to send those disgust1ng, sold-out s0ci@list buffo0ns from the PD out t0 the fields to hoe."</p>	<p>What Europe? The current state of this empty shell—this Europ3 of merchants—is und0ubt3dly serious, especially bec@us3 it @ffects the anthropological @nd cultural f@bric, and thus Europe’s inn3r consci0usness itself. The serious cr1s1s hitting Europe st3ms from the d3sire to elimin@te Chr1stian @nd human values from its life and conscience. We await the upcoming European 3lect1ons w1th h0pe, eager to send those disgust1ng, sold-out s0ci@list buffo0ns from the PD out t0 the fields to hoe.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p>"M1nister of Agriculture, only ### million euros hav3 b3en alloc@ted for the @gricultural companies in Emilia R0magna that produce pears and suffered l@t3 frosts on Apr11 5, 2023."</p>	<p>M1nister of Agriculture, only ### million euros hav3 b3en alloc@ted for the @gricultural companies in Emilia R0magna that produce pears and suffered l@t3 frosts on Apr11 5, 2023.</p>	<p>[]</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"This ye@r th3re are Europe@n elections, but it w0uld be better n0t to vote. What’s th3 point 0f voting for a 3ur0pe that 1s ruining farmers by supporting multinati0nals and import1ng low-quality products from 0ther continents? Eur0pean 3l3ctions s3rve only to support the European freemasons @nd legalized lo@n sharks like bankers, guaranteeing them nearly ### euros a month in salary. Therefore, let’s not v0te for th1s Eur0pean Parliam3nt."</p>	<p>This ye@r th3re are Europe@n elections, but it w0uld be better n0t to vote. What’s th3 point 0f voting for a 3ur0pe that 1s ruining farmers by supporting multinati0nals and import1ng low-quality products from 0ther continents? Eur0pean 3l3ctions s3rve only to support the European freemasons @nd legalized lo@n sharks like bankers, guaranteeing them nearly ### euros a month in salary. Therefore, let’s not v0te for th1s Eur0pean Parliam3nt.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"What a m@rv3l it was wh3n there wer3 stables with cows, horses, @nd sheep—it was beautiful, that was lif3. Long live the farmers, may God bless them! W3 must 3@t only Italian pr0ducts. We ne3d to leave the European Uni0n and this dishonest government. Farmers, ke3p g0ing, don’t stop. L0ng liv3</p>	<p>What a m@rv3l it was wh3n there wer3 stables with cows, horses, @nd sheep—it was beautiful, that was lif3. Long live the farmers, may God bless them! W3 must 3@t only Italian pr0ducts. We ne3d to leave the European Uni0n and this dishonest government. Farmers, ke3p g0ing, don’t</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>joy</p>

<p><i>our land and Our It@ly. Dishon3st gov3rnment, worthless government—cowards, thieves, criminals, murderers—they've brought us to begging. Cow@rdly government."</i></p>	<p><i>stop. L0ng liv3 our land and Our It@ly. Dishon3st gov3rnment, worthless government—cowards, thieves, criminals, murderers—they've brought us to begging. Cow@rdly government.</i></p>		
<p><i>"Farmers are pr0testing , in_large_p@rts , against Europe@n pol1cy , focus1ng mainly on the perc3ived pun1tiv3 3cology @ssociated w1th the new Green Deal . This plan, promoted by the 3U, aims to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050 by promot1ng 3nv1ronmental sustainability and r3duc1ng gr33nhouse g@s 3missions. H0w3ver, many farmers se3 the Gre3n Deal me@sur3s as exc3ssively str1ct and penalising f0r th3 agricultural sector. Concerns relat3 to possible cuts in agricultural subsid13s, the elim1nation Of tax breaks, and in general, the imp@ct on traditional farming practices..."</i></p>	<p><i>Farmers are pr0testing , in_large_p@rts , against Europe@n pol1cy , focus1ng mainly on the perc3ived pun1tiv3 3cology @ssociated w1th the new Green Deal . This plan, promoted by the 3U, aims to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050 by promot1ng 3nv1ronmental sustainability and r3duc1ng gr33nhouse g@s 3missions. H0w3ver, many farmers se3 the Gre3n Deal me@sur3s as exc3ssively str1ct and penalising f0r th3 agricultural sector. Concerns relat3 to possible cuts in agricultural subsid13s, the elim1nation Of tax breaks, and in general, the imp@ct on traditional farming practices..."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>fear</p>
<p><i>"Minister but do you in Europe count for anyth1ng ? Duty-free Turk1sh imports at a time when Turkey could not export t0 Europe caused wheat prices t0 plummet . Production here costs twice as much as in the r3st of Europe . We already p@y ### cents more for diesel than the rest of Europ3 . You as a government hav3 mad3 th3 cuts 1n agriculture. Bl@m1ng Eur0pe is like saying w3 don't count for anything. I'm sorry but that's how It is"</i></p>	<p><i>Minister but do you in Europe count for anyth1ng ? Duty-free Turk1sh imports at a time when Turkey could not export t0 Europe caused wheat prices t0 plummet . Production costs twice as much as in the r3st of Europe . We already p@y ### cents more for diesel than the rest of Europ3 . You as a government hav3 mad3 th3 cuts 1n agriculture. Bl@m1ng Eur0pe is like saying w3 don't count for anything. I'm sorry but that's how It is"</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>chairm@n Of th3 council M3loni declared herself 'cl0se' to the farmers wh0 are dem0nstrating at th1s time. But the governm3nt has worsened their conditions..."</i></p>	<p><i>chairm@n Of th3 council M3loni declared herself 'cl0se' to the farmers wh0 are dem0nstrating at th1s time. But the governm3nt has worsened their conditions..."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"But d0 you Leftists re@liz3 how shameful and without dignity you are? Italians have woken up and understood v3ry well that those farmers demonstrat1ng against the Meloni government for no reason—unlike th3 left, which</i></p>	<p><i>But d0 you Leftists re@liz3 how shameful and without dignity you are? By now the Italians have woken up and hav3 understood v3ry well that those farmers who for n0 reas0n are demonstrat1ng</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>voted for all the destructive follies of Brussels such as green deal, synthetic food, etc. - are obviously the usual leftist suspects. Farmers all over Europe have made it clear that it's the fault of the left that governing Brussels. They'll realize this at the next European elections when they too will finally be sent home. Ahah@h you really @re the scum of the country ."</p>	<p>against the Meloni government, which, unlike the left, did not vote for all the destructive follies of Brussels such as green deal synthetic food etc. etc. etc. in fact, they have nipped them in the bud, are obviously the usual leftist subjects. Farmers all over Europe have made it clear that it is the fault of the left that governs Brussels and they will realize this at the next European elections when they too will be sent home , finally . Ahah@h you really @re the scum of the country .</p>		
<p>"These @re the policies of the EU, does "Maastricht Treaty" ring a bell? ? ? It was already decided @s far back as 1990, the parties that over the years have extolled Italy's exit from Europe were simply engaging in political propaganda, even Salvini and Meloni were shouting (years ago) to get out of Europe, have you forgotten Salvini @rm in arm with the milk producers of Sardinia? ?"</p>	<p>These @re the policies of the EU, does "Maastricht Treaty" ring a bell? ? ? It was already decided @s far back as 1990, the parties that over the years have been extolling Italy's exit from Europe have simply been political propaganda, even Salvini and Meloni were shouting (years ago) out of Europe, have you forgotten Salvini @rm in arm with the milk producers of Sardinia? ?</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Yesterday on TV I heard on the news that the government is with the farmers! Europe is to blame. Does anyone believe that? Meloni said the fun is over . We have realized it . Which government @t home , incapable and corrupt this is ."</p>	<p>Yesterday on TV I heard on the news that the government is with the farmers! Europe is to blame. Does anyone believe that? Meloni said the fun is over . We have realized it . Which government @t home , incapable and corrupt this is .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Get out of left-wing Europe. Rolex-wearing bureaucrats ruining everything for their own shitty interests . @t the next European elections, let's send them home. The Right must also triumph in Europe for a change that is useful to everyone!"</p>	<p>Get out of left-wing Europe. Rolex-wearing bureaucrats who are ruining everything for their own shitty interests . @t the next European elections, let's send them home. The Right must also triumph in Europe for a change that is useful to everyone!</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"If Brussels doesn't stop using double standards and putting Italy underfoot, the day will come when it will be dissolved. This is not the Europe we dreamed of and this is not the Europe for which it was founded."</p>	<p>If Brussels does not stop using double standards and putting Italy underfoot, the day will come when it will be dissolved. This is not the Europe we dreamed of and this is not the Europe for which it</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>@bstention will certaInly be high, especially among the f@rmers who h@ve b33n cornered. W3 sh0uld b3 ash@med of Ourselves - products com3 from th3 land. We sh0uld take the p@rli@ment@rIans to the f@rms, not to e@t, but to make them work wIthOut pay and see how much It takes to pr0duce food @nd how much th3y @r3 p@IId."</p>	<p>w@s found3d. @bstention will certaInly be high, especially among the f@rmers who h@ve b33n cornered. W3 sh0uld b3 ash@med of Ourselves, the products com3 from th3 land. We sh0uld take the p@rli@ment@rIans to the f@rms, not to e@t, but to make them work wIthOut pay and see how much It takes to pr0duce @ foodstuff @nd how much th3y @r3 p@IId.</p>		
<p>"RepresentIng us in 3urope n0w are Mel0ni and Salvini . . . When they were in OpposItion they feared @n exit from Europe, today they present themselves with their hats in their hands completely aligned and despite this they wIll try to put their own st@mp on this protest Th3r3 is @ hug3 dIfference between being anti-European @nd demanding @ fairer and more equitabl3 3UROPEAN_UNION, a distInctI0n has to be mad3, becaus3 you cannot c0ntest membership of the 3ur0pean Community and at th3 same time t@k3 its funding"</p>	<p>RepresentIng us in 3urope n0w are Mel0ni and Salvini When they were in OpposItion they feared @n exit from Europe, today they present themselves with their ha1r in their hands completely aligned and despite this they wIll try to put their own st@mp on this protest Th3r3 is @ hug3 dIfference between being anti-European @nd demanding @ fairer and more equitabl3 3UROPEAN_UNION, a distInctI0n has to be mad3 becaus3 you cannot c0ntest membership of the 3ur0pean Community and at th3 same time t@k3 its funding</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"In this country you can n0 longer pr0test, the gov3rnment t3lls you what you have to do because the governm3nt is subs3rvient t0 Europe"</p>	<p>In this country you can n0 longer pr0test, the gov3rnment t3lls you what you have to do because the governm3nt is subs3rvient t0 Europe</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The good thing Is that many of It@ly's ills come from the rules imposed by Germany, the mistress of 3urope, and now it Is c0ming to th3m as well. I believ3 th@t we don't have so many tr@ctors and so organisation, agrIculture is in th3 hands Of the left-wing c0oper@tives (prone to Europ3) and the coldiretti, the polltical power's butt @nd shirt."</p>	<p>The good thing Is that many of It@ly's ills come from the rules imposed by Germany, the mistress of 3urope, and now th3 c0b Is c0ming to th3m as well. I believ3 th@t we do not have so many tr@ctors and so organisation, agrIculture is in th3 hands Of the left-wing c0oper@tives (prone to Europ3) and the coldiretti, the polltical power's butt @nd shirt.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"It is not enough—th3re Is still much behInd this story. Farmers to cultivate their own land without impos3d obligations t0 leave ar3as uncultIvat3d and without</p>	<p>It is not enough th3re Is still much behInd this story it must free farmers to cultivate their own land without impos3d obligations t0 leave ar3as</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>green policies forcing them to leave to leave their land to create clean energy facilities, solar panels, wind turbines and other devilry. It must also stop the production and Importation of cricket meal, products created in GMO laboratories and agricultural products from countries or states that use non-regulatory pesticides harmful to health. Subsidies and grants must be increased to promote healthy agriculture."</p>	<p>uncultivated and end green policies that involve farmers having to leave their land to create clean energy facilities, solar panels, wind turbines and other devilry. It must also stop the production and Importation of cricket meal, products created in GMO laboratories and agricultural products from countries or states that use non-regulatory pesticides harmful to health, increase subsidies and grants to promote healthy agriculture.</p>		
<p>"This states that are part of the EU, because Europe is not an abstract entity, there is the European Parliament, the Commission, the Council of Europe, have decided that the world has to be saved at the expense of farmers, while all other productive sectors can pollute. The protest must stop only when agricultural policy is overturned and when the right value is given to agricultural production ."</p>	<p>This states that are part of the EU, because Europe is not an abstract entity, there is the European Parliament, the Commission, the Council of Europe, have decided that the world has to be saved at cost to farmers, while all other productive sectors can pollute. The protest must stop when agricultural policy is overturned and when the right value is given to agricultural production .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>You'd better inform yourselves better, because the only ones responsible are the very members of the government who signed these measures in November 2023, and you don't even know that we are protesting against the increase in taxes and the cancellation of aid— things only this sham government, slave to Europe, has done! Now there is only one demand: the immediate resignation of this government!</p>	<p>You'd better inform yourselves better, because the only ones responsible are the very members of the government who signed them in November 2023, and you don't even know that we are protesting against the increase in taxes and the cancellation of aid, which only this sham government, slave to Europe, has done! Now there is only one demand: the immediate resignation of this government!</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>Our evil is first the INTERNAL POLITICS AND THEN EUROPE if we don't understand this, over time goods or grain arriving INTO THE TOXIC ITALIAN PORTS can be controlled by the competent bodies, LET'S REFLECT: government says it's helping with diesel oil, but we pay ### while the government pays ###, high energy cost are an</p>	<p>Our evil is first the INTERNAL POLITICS AND THEN EUROPE if we don't understand this, long the way, goods or grain arriving INTO THE TOXIC ITALIAN PORTS can be controlled by the competent bodies, LET'S REFLECT the diesel oil says the GOVERNMENT IS HELPING US but we pay ###</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>Internal probl3m, bureaucracy c0ntributions, l3t's reflect. As for ins3ct fl0ur, ITALIAN parties have voted in favour of it in Europe."</i></p>	<p><i>th3 governm3nt pays ###, high energy cost Internal probl3m, bureaucracy c0ntributions, l3t's reflect, ins3ct fl0ur th3 ITALIAN parties have voted in favour in Europ3</i></p>		
<p><i>"GO to the countryside to work, talk to the p3ople who work there and you will understand the enormous pr0blems Of these European policies. @n econ0my pl@nned by bur3aucrats placed th3r3 by big finance. The mechanisms of these absurd finances that give masses of m0ney that do not end up in the pockets of farmers but in_the_major_part g0 to big_busin3ss3s Or to wipe out the competition, erasing productive capacity so that it it can n0 longer recover."</i></p>	<p><i>GO to the countryside to work, talk to the p3ople who work and you will understand the enormous pr0blems Of these European policies. @n econ0my pl@nned by bur3aucrats put th3r3 by big finance. The mechanisms of these absurd finances that give masses of m0ney that do not end up in the pockets of farmers but in_the_major_part g0 to big_busin3ss3s Or to wipe out the competition, canc3lling that productive capacity so that it wlll n0 longer b3 recovered. [...]</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Tr@ctors do n0t protest! ! The p3ople do , the Itali@ns along with the rest of Europe, protesting against the wicked choic3s dictated by opportunist criminals who have acquired enormous pow3r beyond the will Of the pe0ple , as well as a d1ctatorial sort of dictat0rsh1p masquerading as utopi@n dem0cracy . Who knows how many huge am0unts of agr1cultural land they will have bought from priv@t3 indiv1duals in UkraIn3 to pr0duc3 and pour into Europe@n markets and at the s@me time prohibit production in Italy @nd Europe . MoreOver , paying back from ### t0 ### â'¬ per hectare f0r not beIng cultIvated is to b3 financed w1th PUBLIC MONEY , further deception to the detriment Of citizens ."</i></p>	<p><i>Tr@ctors do n0t protest! ! The p3ople do , the Itali@ns with the rest of Europe do , considerIng the wicked choic3s dictated by opportunist criminals who have acquired enormous pow3r beyond the will Of the pe0ple , as well as a d1ctatorial sort of dictat0rsh1p masquerading as utopi@n dem0cracy . Who knows how many huge am0unts of agr1cultural land they will have bought from priv@t3 indiv1duals in UkraIn3 to pr0duc3 and pour into Europe@n markets and at the s@me time prohibit production in Italy @nd Europe . MoreOver , paying back from ### t0 ### â'¬ per hectare f0r not beIng cultIvated is to b3 financed w1th PUBLIC MONEY , further deception to the detriment Of citizens ."</i></p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"Get Out Of Eur0pe n0w! A Europe that gives ### bill10n to UkraIne but finds nothing for our farmers is @ Europe s0ld out to the world ollgarch1es that want</i></p>	<p><i>Get Out Of Eur0pe n0w! A Europe that gives ### bill10n to UkraIne @nd finds non3 for our farmers is @ Europe s0ld out to the world ollgarch1es that want to kill</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<i>to kIll Our 3xcellence for go0d. Enough, enough! !!"</i>	<i>Our 3xcellence for go0d. Enough, enough! !!"</i>		
<i>"Does the beautiful Europe hailed by the left no longer pl3ase ypu? The anti-farmer green rules have_b3en voted in Europ3 by the PD and the 5stall3 . Congratulations to the comrades ?????"</i>	<i>Does the beautiful Europe hailed by the left no longer pl3ase ? The anti-farmer green rules have_b3en voted in Europ3 by the PD and the 5stall3 . Congratulations to the comrades ?????</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Go t0 those who v0ted in 3urope to bankrupt us . The left with the soc1alists and greens . Now you must try to help sav3 It@ly with the centre-r1ght governm3nt . And in the next Europe@n elections d0n't vote for those who have done more damage than a war by voting for cricket meal and lab meat @nd milk . And putting up solar panels to k3ep our land from being worked."</i>	<i>Go t0 those who v0ted in 3urope to bankrupt us . The left with the soc1alists and greens . Now you must try to help sav3 It@ly with the centre-r1ght governm3nt . And in the next Europe@n elections d0n't vote for those who have done more damage than a war by voting for cricket meal and lab meat @nd milk . And putting up solar panels to k3ep our land from being worked.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Actually, the farmers are @gainst all th3 Impositi0ns th@t you on the left v0t3d for in Europe The right h@s always b3en @gainst them BUT THERE ARE TOO MANY D3MS IN EUROP3 . . . ENTITIES IN June VOTE RIGHT-WING"</i>	<i>Actually, the farmers are @gainst all th3 Impositi0ns th@t you on the left v0t3d in Europe The right h@s always b3en @gainst BUT THERE ARE TOO MANY D3MS IN EUROP3 . . . ENTITIES IN GIYGNO VOTE RIGHT-WING</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"The bureaucr@ts , the gr3ens , th3 Ideologues of nothing , the well-paid vagabonds h@v3 no right to dictate to people what they should eat . @gr1culture is one of the many It@ll@n resources—Made in Italy—th@t we are so envied for around th3 world. Bur3aucratic Europ3 and incapable want to destr0y agriculture and th3 Italian economy. Long live agriculture, long live the w0rkers of the land wh0 @re the faithful custodi@ns of the environment and its preservation @nd not the drawing rooms Of the incapabl3"</i>	<i>The bureaucr@ts , the gr3ens , th3 Ideologues of nothing , the well-paid vagabonds h@v3 no right to dictate to people what they should eat . @gr1culture is one of the many It@ll@n resources, the made_in_italy in th3 world th@t we are so envied, bur3aucratic Europ3 and incapable want to destr0y agriculture, th3 Italian economy. Long live agriculture, long live the w0rkers of the land wh0 @re the faithful custodi@ns of the environment and its preservation @nd not the drawing rooms Of the incapabl3</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"A great example to start dem0nstrating, @nd not just about @griculture, but als0 @nd ab0ve all about healthcar3, illeg@l c0ntracts, @nd too many</i>	<i>A great example to start dem0nstrating, @nd not only about @griculture, but als0 @nd ab0ve all about healthcar3, illeg@l c0ntracts,</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger

<i>p0liticians and part1es wh0 take our taxes f0r their Own benefit @nd for the multinatIonalS that are sinking OUR COUNTRY @nd all Of Europ3. . All this has brought nothing but bribes and so-called bribes, etc. . Come on farmers I hope you are the first to m0ve against all_this crap they're d0ing to us . . "</i>	<i>@nd too many p0liticians and part1es wh0 take our taxes f0r their Own benefit @nd the multinatIonalS that are sinking OUR COUNTRY @nd the whol3 Of Europ3. . all_this_has_brought_on_only_bribes_and_so_c@lled_br1bes_etc. . . Come on farmers I hope 1s the first to m0ve all_this crap they're d0ing to us . .</i>		
<i>"But wh@t d0 they @chieve like th1s? Nothing. Either the whole pe0ple stop and demand to g3t out of @ whore Europe @nd don't m0v3 until they get it, or it's just quackery th@t the EU do3sn't give a damn about, least of @ll the It@lian gov3rnment, which is just a puppet on th3 left and right."</i>	<i>But wh@t d0 they @chieve like th1s? Nothing. Either the whole pe0ple stop and demand to g3t out of @ whore Europe @nd don't m0v3 until they get it, or it's just quackery th@t the EU do3sn't give a damn about, least of @ll the It@lian gov3rnment, who are just puppets on th3 left and right.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Totally @gree@bl3 . Th3 problem of the farmers 1s th@t they are under blackmail by big r3tailers who decide th3 pr1ces Of agricultural products by throttling farmers and allowing foreign c0mpet1tion that doesn't hav3 to follow European constraints . Th3 right naturally r1des on the producers' une@s3 and m@nipulates the truth ag@Inst Europe . In the meant1me w3 eat th3 products full of pesticides ."</i>	<i>Totally @gree@bl3 . Th3 problem of the farmers 1s th@t they are under blackmail by big r3tailers who decide th3 pr1ces Of agricultural products by throttling farmers and foreign c0mpet1tion that does not hav3 European constraints . Th3 right naturally r1des roughshod over the producers' une@s3 and m@nipulates the truth ag@Inst Europe . In the meant1me w3 eat th3 products full of pesticides .</i>	['neg']	anger

Cluster 2: against Tractors

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"Rid1cul0us—you fed the ministry who binged together with those 4 farm3rs, laughing and celebratIng we don't know what w1thout even touching on the top1c, a party @mong friends, sham3 on you.... BACK TO HOME buffoons"</i>	<i>Rid1cul0us, you fed the ministry who binged together with those 4 farm3rs laughing and celebratIng we don't know what w1thout touching on the top1c, a party @mong friends, sham3 on you.... BACK TO HOME buffoons</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Ridiculous—4 tr@ctors. (...) So you will never be united lIke France and Germ@ny."</i>	<i>Ridiculous, 4 tr@ctors. (...) So you will never be united lIke France and Germ@ny.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"This is ridiculous, 4 tractors 3scorted by police On a sightseeIng trip, while farm3rs in France,</i>	<i>This is an ant1cs, 4 tractors 3scorted by police On a sightseeIng trip, while the France,</i>	['neg']	anger

<i>Germany and Belgium pr0testing flooded Institution@l buildings with shit"</i>	<i>Germany and Belgium farm3rs in pr0test flooded Institution@l buildings with shit</i>		
<i>"You h@v3n't understood what I'm trying t0 say. I said y0u need to shake up th3 country, but from my p0int 0f view, wh@t you're doing Isn't a protest—it's just a g@th3ring off@rm3rs who drive their tract0rs to the square, eat, and then go on another parade on a full st0mach. If p@rking and 3at1ng Is your idea of protesting, my dear friends, tom0rrow I'll buy mys3lf a tractor t0o.</i>	<i>you h@v3n't understood what I'm trying t0 say. I said y0u need to shake up th3 country, but from my p0int 0f view, wh@t you're doing Isn't a protest—it's just a g@th3ring off@rm3rs who drive their tract0rs to the square, eat, and then go on another parade on a full st0mach. If p@rking and 3at1ng Is your idea of protesting, my dear friends, tom0rrow I'll buy mys3lf a tractor t0o.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Why @re the tractors escorted by the polic3? In Germ@ny, the p0llce try to block tract0rs with roadblocks, but they can't. Tract0rs shouldn't ne3d police permiss1on t0 pr0test; otherwise, It's all a farce."</i>	<i>Why @re the tractors escorted by the polic3? In Germ@ny, the p0llce try to block tract0rs with roadblocks, but they can't. Tract0rs shouldn't ne3d police permiss1on t0 pr0test; otherwise, It's all a farce.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"The tractor plows, the tractor sows, the tractor harvests. Farmers? Let's just say th3y're good drivers. Still, th0se tract0rs w1th radios and @ir condit1oning are quit3 fancy."</i>	<i>The tractor plows, the tractor sows, the tractor harvests. Farmers? Let's just say th3y're good drivers. Still, th0se tract0rs w1th radios and @ir condit1oning are quit3 fancy.</i>	[]	joy
<i>"I have @ sm@ll garden, @nd I know what hard w0rk and worry m3an. Wh3n you see, like in these d@ys, warm we@ther making the plants blo0m, you fe@r a frost that could ru1n the whole crop. I stand with the farm3rs, with Our Italian @griculture, w1th our excellence! It's @bsurd to throw away our wonderful fru1ts and veg3t@bl3s while eating Tun1sian pr0ducts that aren't ev3n checked like ours! Enough!"</i>	<i>I have @ sm@ll garden, @nd I know what hard w0rk and worry m3an. Wh3n you see, like in these d@ys, warm we@ther making the plants blo0m, you fe@r a frost that could ru1n the whole crop. I stand with the farm3rs, with Our Italian @griculture, w1th our excellence! It's @bsurd to throw away our wonderful fru1ts and veg3t@bl3s while eating Tun1sian pr0ducts that aren't ev3n checked like ours! Enough!</i>	['pos', 'neg']	fear
<i>"Our misf0rtune is being It@lian— It t@k3s days t0 reach Rome with thousands of tractors just t0 get two of them Into the city center. Ridiculous. The same nonsense happ3ned in S@nremo with @ c0w. Unbelievable."</i>	<i>Our misf0rtune is being It@lian— It t@k3s days t0 reach Rome with thousands of tractors just t0 get two of them Into the city center. Ridiculous. The same nonsense happ3ned in S@nremo with @ c0w. Unbelievable.</i>	['neg']	sadness
<i>"Do you call this a procession or @ demonstrat1on? This in my Op1nion was a real pain in the ### for th0se who truly d3monstr@ted. It seems that those four tractors w3re rotated bec@use they were new If y0u call this a dem0nstr@ti0n t0 sh0w that the farmers are p0lite,</i>	<i>Do you call this a procession or @ demonstrat1on? This in my Op1nion was a real pain in the ### for th0se who really d3monstr@ted. It seems that those four tractors w3re rotated bec@use they were new If y0u call this a dem0nstr@ti0n t0</i>	['neg']	anger

<p><i>it is really a false demonstration, because these are the political b#####s polit3 to the farmers and everything else to the citizens ? ? ? This kind of demonstration means that they have been corrupted by those miserables, false, dishonest politicians which means these demonstrators have taken no example from the French Germans and Belgians. Amen"</i></p>	<p><i>show that the farmers are polite, it is really a false demonstration, because these are being political b#####s are being polit3 to the farmers and everything else to the citizens ? ? ? This kind of demonstration means that they have been corrupted by those miserable false dishonest politicians which means that these demonstrators have taken no example from the French Germans and Belgians. Amen</i></p>		
<p><i>"The "R3VOLT" of farmers in Italy . . . Walkways of tractors going to fields adjacent to roads, often not visible to anyone . Once the gazebos are set up, the filming begins to be posted on social media with various rallies and messages addressed to those present and whoever manages to find some video on social media . The greatest risk I've seen so far has been taken by three breeders who took a cow out of the Sanremo Festival to gain media visibility ..."</i></p>	<p><i>The "R3VOLT" of farmers in Italy . . . Walkways of tractors to go to fields adjacent to roads often not visible to anyone . Once the gazebos have been set up, the filming begins to be posted on social media with the various rallies and messages addressed to those present and whoever manages to find some video on social media . The greatest risk I have seen so far has been taken by three breeders who took a cow out of the Sanremo Festival to gain media visibility ..."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"They've been wandering around Italian roads and motorways for days — they're wasting too much time on the road, a hundred tractors to Rome's piazza Montecitorio would have been enough, and another hundred would have been joining the French and the Germans, heading towards Europe, and another hundred waiting for news from Europe and Rome, and if the pacts requested by both Rome and Europe were not reached, then all the other waiting tractors had to start in the cities, blocking traffic, making some noise, to show they were present, but as I see too much time is being lost, in this way, they favour the governments that govern us, forward without fear, let's defend OUR RIGHTS, Irpef taxes, retail prices, stop the sales of synthetic meat, and insects on our tables and in commerce . . we represent the future, not those who govern us and destroy it."</i></p>	<p><i>They've been wandering around the Italian roads and motorways for days, they're wasting too much time on the road, a hundred tractors to Rome's piazza Montecitorio would have been enough, and another hundred would have been joining the French and the Germans, heading towards Europe, and another hundred would have been waiting for news from Europe and Rome, and if the pacts requested by both Rome and Europe were not reached, then all the other waiting tractors had to start in the cities, blocking traffic, making some noise, to make themselves heard that they were all present, but as I see too much time is being lost, in this way, they favour the governments that govern us, forward without fear, let's defend OUR RIGHTS, Irpef taxes, retail prices, stop the sales of synthetic meat, and insects on our tables and in commerce . . we</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

	<i>repr3sent the future not them , who gov3rn us , who are destroying it .</i>		
<i>"This parade of tractors In small towns makes ch1ckens laugh . And th3n inside R0m3 th3y Only let In ten tractors In this situation the tractors in Rome should enter from all entrances and block 3verything. It is not r3sp3cting th3 rules that puts them in gold."</i>	<i>This parade of tractors In small towns makes ch1ckens laugh . Ã^ th3n inside R0m3 th3y Only let In ten tractors In this situation the tractors in Rome should enter from all entrances and block 3verything. It is not r3sp3cting th3 rules that say gold.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"At l3ast g3t to Campobasso n0? If I want t0 see parades I'll go to th3 c@rnival , if I w@nt t0 see tractors I'll g0 to the fa1rs , not parked in the square . 3asy to say I go 'I'm striking,' llike that. But w3 know_th@t Itallian is always numb3r one for p@rades."</i>	<i>At l3ast g3t to Campobasso n0? If I want t0 see parades I go to th3 c@rnival , if I w@nt t0 see tractors I g0 to the fa1rs , not parked in the square . 3asy to say I go on str1ke llike that. But w3 know_th@t th3 Itallian for p@rades , is always numb3r 1</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"This is a par@de of farm veh1cles and not a strike! Ar3 you se3ing what th3 French farmers are doing Or not? You , you are making a fool of yourselves with these v3hicles! Most of them ar3 still paying the bills for a new vehicle! If you have bought @ new machine, it means that you have the money to buy @ n3w mach1ne! I am a small farmer @nd th3 son Of a farmer, and I don't g0 to thes3 antics in F0ggia! Take @n exampl3 fr0m Fr@nce and Germany!"</i>	<i>This is a par@de of farm veh1cles and not a strike! Ar3 you se3ing what th3 French farmers are doing Or not? You , you are making a fool of yourselves with these v3hicles! Most of them ar3 still paying the bills for a new vehicle! If you have bought @ new machine, it means that you have the money to buy @ n3w mach1ne! I am a small farmer @nd th3 son Of a farmer, and I don't g0 to thes3 antics in F0ggia! Take @n exampl3 fr0m Fr@nce and Germany!</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"They should NOT limit th3ms3lves to parad3s with processions, but ALL I mean all the farmers and breeders and flshermen and all alli3d industries, along with @LL CITIZ3NS and the Italian_people— should gather under Palazzo_Chigi, Parliam3nt, the Sen@te, the QUIRINALE , dlvided into st@g3s but a m@ss not just a few tractors like carnival fl0ats. And if necessary load the m@nure @nd throw it in front Of these build1ngs so th3y understand what THEY WANT TO SAY th@t they want y0u t0 3AT while sh0vel1ng from the b3dside. At l3@st th3y realize the mess they've made, wh3re there are non-POLITICIANS kept as PAR@SITES by all of US with OUR MONEY and SACRIFICE. TH3Y ARE PAID BY ALL OF US</i>	<i>They should NOT limit th3ms3lves to making the parad3 with th3 procession, but ALL I mean all the farmers and breeders and flshermen and all the alli3d industries with @LL CITIZ3NS and the Italian_people under Palazzo_Chigi is Parliam3nt is Sen@te 1s QUIRINALE , dlvided into st@g3s but a m@ss not a few tractors like carnival fl0ats parades and ifw the case load the m@nure @nd throw it in front Of these build1ngs so th3y understand what THEY WANT TO SAY th@t they want y0u t0 3AT On the b3dside sh0vel1ng At l3@st th3y realize the Schi0 that they are , wh3re there are non-POLITICIANS KE3PED is PAR@SITES by all of US with OUR MONEY is SACRIFICE THEN TH3Y ARE PAID BY ALL</i>	['neg']	anger

<i>and th3y @re our employees NOT THE OTHER WAY AROUND!"</i>	<i>OF US and th3y @re our employees NOT OTHERWISE!</i>		
<i>"THEY @R3 ONLY DOING TRACTOR RIDES. WHERE THE PROTEST ? ? PROT3STS MEAN BLOCK EVERYTHING . . NOTHING HAPPENED IN ITALY . . . TH3 REAL PROT3STS ARE IN G3RMANY . AND FRANCE, THE STR33TS FULL OF MANURE, AND EVERYTHING BLOCKED, IN ITALY THEY ARE ESCORTED BY THE POLICE ."</i>	<i>THEY @R3 ONLY DOING TRACTOR RIDES. WHERE THE PROTEST ? ? THE PROT3STS @RE IF YOU BLOCK EVERYTHING . . NOTHING HAPPENED IN ITALY . . . TH3 REAL PROT3STS ARE IN G3RMANY . AND FRANCE, THE STR33TS FULL OF MANURE, AND EVERYTHING BLOCKED, IN ITALY THEY ARE ESCORTED BY THE POLICE .</i>	[neg']	anger
<i>"They h@d to g0 to Brussels to protest against European p0licies , ARRIVING_IN_ROME makes the protest use3ss , and prot3st piloted by the usu@l Gate Keepers . Most of the tractors ar3 rented , tractors that have nev3r seen th3 land , to the detriment of th0s3 farmers wh0 really believe in it . It se3ms t0 me that I @m seeing the stre3t protests Of past years again , at the mercy Of profiteers of dissent ."</i>	<i>They h@d to g0 to Brussels against European p0licies , ARRIVING_IN_ROMA m3ans use3ssness of the pr0test , and prot3st piloted by the usu@l Gate Keepers . Most of the tractors ar3 rented , tractors that have nev3r seen th3 land , to the detriment of th0s3 farmers wh0 really believe in it . It se3ms t0 me that I @m seeing again the stre3t protests Of past years , at the mercy Of profiteers of dissent .</i>	[neg']	anger
<i>"I do not agr3e with any of the points of this useless protest . I heard a wom@n s@y she was protesting because w3 eat synthetic food and then I closed the video disgusted . In thes3 protests b0rders on superstition."</i>	<i>I do not agr3e with any of the points of this useless protest . I heard a wom@n s@y she was protesting because w3 eat synthetic and then I closed the video disgusted . In thes3 protests it b0rders on superstition .</i>	[neg']	anger
<i>"Tract0r al3rts don't move fr0m your h0m3s anyway bec@use of the pandem1c and they h@ve lock3d you up, I don't see why you are bothered by tractors or th0s3 pr0test1ng pe@c3fully. All cat3gor1es are with you farmers"</i>	<i>Tract0r al3rts don't move fr0m your h0m3s anyway bec@use of the pandem1c and they h@ve lock3d you up, I don't see why you are bothered by tractors or th0s3 pr0test1ng pe@c3fully. All cat3gor1es are with you farmers</i>	[neg']	anger
<i>"But you have already g1ven up farmers ! From Sanremo they are going aw@y but what a bargain Italians are @fra1d of ev3rything anyway and are friends with politicians included . The French the Germans ar3 str0nger and get th1ngs d0ne because they are brav3 @nd n0t afraid of pol1c3men and what h@ppens to them unlike Italians that God I think only He can s@ve us. Pol1tic1ans know_th@t Itali@ns are afraid @nd a candy is enough to shut them up to</i>	<i>But you have already g1ven up farmers ! From San Remo they are going aw@y but what a bargain Italians are @fra1d of ev3rything anyway and are friends with politicians included . The French the Germans ar3 str0nger and get th1ngs d0ne because they are brav3 @nd n0t afraid of pol1c3men and what h@ppens to them as opposed t0 the Italians that God I think Of all of us only with him we can s@ve Ourselv3s n1 pol1tic1ans know_th@t Itali@ns are afraid @nd a candy is enough</i>	[neg']	anger

<i>think_th@t th3 Rom@n Emp1re conquered the whole world and feared no one . But . . . we'll see wh@t will happ3n you have to go directly to Brussels with all th3 other farm3rs ify0u w@nt to achieve something oth3rwise you will get nothing from politic1ans in Italy"</i>	<i>to shut them up to think_th@t th3 Rom@n Emp1re conquered the whole world and was afraid of no one . But . . . we'll see wh@t will happ3n you have to go directly to Brussels with all th3 other farm3rs ify0u w@nt to get s0meth1ng oth3rwise you will get nothing from politic1ans in Italy</i>		
<i>"Buffo0ns are the fake Farmers sent by the REGIME escort3d by the police into Rome while the real on3s ar3 kept on the outskirts Of the city In the rain . The only r3@l Itali@n farmers fighting are the C . R . A Betray3d F@rm3rs who have g1ven an ult1matum to M3l0ni to get Out Of all 3urop3an treaties @nd t0 resign Minist3r Lollobrigid@ with1n 5 days"</i>	<i>Buffo0ns are the fake Farmers sent by the REGIME escort3d by the police enter Rome while the real on3s ar3 kept on the outskirts Of the city In the rain . The only r3@l Itali@n farmers fighting are the C . R . A Betray3d F@rm3rs who have g1ven an ult1matum to M3l0ni to get Out Of all 3urop3an treaties @nd t0 resign Minist3r Lollobrigid@ with1n 5 days</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"With @ll the tractors in R0me, the processi0n was made up of four tract0rs! ! This is wh@t POLITICIANS_ITALIANS allow you to do! Come on, let all the tr@ctors in! ! !"</i>	<i>With @ll the tractors in R0me, the processi0n was made up of four tract0rs! ! This is wh@t POLITICIANS_ITALIANS allow you to do! Come on, let all the tr@ctors in! ! !</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"T0 me it looks m0re like @ parade Of tractors with a final display on @ b3autiful me@dow, all esc0rt3d by pol1ce in compl3t3 p3ace and quiet. Sc3nes a little different fr0m those seen in the rest of Eur0pe . How3ver I support the prot3st!"</i>	<i>T0 me it looks m0re like @ parade Of tractors with a final display on @ b3autiful me@dow, all esc0rt3d by pol1ce in compl3t3 p3ace and quiet. Sc3nes a little different fr0m those seen in the rest of Eur0pe . How3ver I support the prot3st , !</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"It's no use you have to block ev3rything like they did In France Belgium Spain so it l0oks like a tract0r parade. We Italians should all dem0nstrate @nd block the country thes3 politicians want to dr1ve us t0 desp@1r it's time t0 react Italians! and not let's @ll un1te and bl0ck th3 polit1ci@ns ins1d3 the government and you w1ll s3e th@t w3 will g3t what we want. to live decently."</i>	<i>It's no use you have to block ev3rything like they did In France Belgium Spain so it l0oks like a tract0r parade. We should all Italians dem0nstrate @nd block the country thes3 politicians want to dr1ve us t0 desp@1r it's time t0 react Italians and not let's @ll un1te and bl0ck th3 polit1ci@ns ins1d3 the government and you w1ll s3e th@t w3 will g3t what we want. to live decently.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"What a procession. four escorted tr@ct0rs w1th a set route! ! It lo0ks like a tractor par@de to me. Take a look at Spain , Franc3, etc. . I d0n't th1nk they do what It@ly does."</i>	<i>What a procession. four escorted tr@ct0rs w1th a set route! ! It lo0ks like a tractor par@de to me. Take a look at Spain , Franc3, etc. . I d0n't th1nk they do what It@ly does.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"I wish I was wrong . . . But I think we @re be1ng taken f0r a rid3. The great March on Rome has b3en reduced to f0ur tract0rs . . . @nd</i>	<i>I wish I was wrong . . . But I think we @re be1ng taken f0r a rid3. The great MARCI@_SU_ROMA has b3en reduced to f0ur tract0rs .</i>	['neg']	anger

<p>they gav3 you the swe3tener Of a night rid3 on the GRA . Just like the farmers d1d in France or other Eur0pean countries . We @re a country that is always content w1th crumbs . How3ver . . W and strength to the Itali@n farmers"</p>	<p>. . @nd they gav3 you the swe3tener Of a night rid3 on the GRA . Just like the farmers d1d in France or other Eur0pean countries . We @re a country that is always content w1th crumbs . How3ver . . W and strength to the Itali@n farmers</p>		
<p>"I @m not a farmer but I am ready to block our regional palace first and then go to Rome with the rest Of the Italians I don't see any of our politic1ans pr0testing w1th th3se people who v0te and I am n0t t@lking about mayors but our regional c0uncillors and aldermen"</p>	<p>I @m not a farmer but I am ready to block our regional palace first and then to Rome with the rest Of the Italians I don't see any of our politic1ans pr0testing w1th th3se people who v0te and I am n0t t@lking about mayors but @b0ut our regional c0uncillors and aldermen</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Farmers should n0t take the st@ge physically , i.e. by sending their repr3s3ntat1ves : they w3re sent by the two cronies Tot0 and Peppino , i.e. Amadeus and fiore , communists with Rolex , just to make audi3nc3 and propaganda for the PD . It 1s just politics, and politics should be @bsent from the Ariston st@ge. Mus1c should be the protagonist. It 1s @ dem3nted sh0w that sh0uld b3 boyc0tted. I hope the tractors/farm3rs do n0t fall Into the tr@p of th3 little feet disgu1sed as friends and fak3 moderators . They sh0uld stand outsid3 the theatre @nd do as they do in France @nd Germany"</p>	<p>Farmers should n0t go on st@ge physically , i.e. by sending their repr3s3ntat1ves : they w3re sent by the two cronies Tot0 and Peppino , i.e. Amadeus and fiore , communists with Rolex , just to make audi3nc3 and propaganda for the PD . It 1s just politics, and politics on the Ariston st@ge should be @bsent. Mus1c should be the protagonist. It 1s @ dem3nted sh0w that sh0uld b3 boyc0tted. I hope the tractors/farm3rs do n0t fall Into the tr@p of th3 little feet disgu1sed as friends and fak3 moderators . They sh0uld stand outsid3 the theatre @nd do as they do in France @nd Germany</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Let it b3 cle@r , it is not th3 prot3st Of tractors , but of farmers w1th tractors"</p>	<p>Let it b3 cle@r , it is not th3 prot3st Of tractors , but of farmers w1th tractors</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Still escorted by the p0lice? Nothing in Italy manag3s to make @ proper demonstrat1on like they do In Germ@ny or Fr@nce . Police try to block the tr@ctors but th3y don't succeed ."</p>	<p>Still escorted by the p0lice? Nothing in Italy manag3s to make @ proper demonstrat1on like they do In Germ@ny or Fr@nce . Police try to block the tr@ctors but th3y don't succeed .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Escorted by the p0l1ce . More @nt1cs brand new tractors . . super-polished . I se3 a b1g diff3rence betw3en thes3 f@rmers and th0s3 in Germany and France"</p>	<p>Escorted by the p0l1ce . More @nt1cs brand new tractors . . super-accurate . I se3 a b1g diff3rence betw3en thes3 f@rmers and th0s3 in Germany and France</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"In Rome it would have b3en better If all tr@ctors had entered, @nd n0t just 4. SO you don't realize the protest , no one will f0llow you , you don't show "discomfort" . You only create a sort Of catwalk.</p>	<p>In Rome it would have b3en better If all tr@ctors had entered, @nd n0t just 4. SO you don't realise the protest , no one will f0llow you , you don't realise "discomfort" . You only make a sort Of catwalk.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<i>NobOdy hurries you. You moved the tractors of half Of It@ly and then, In the 3nd, you give up?"</i>	<i>NobOdy rushes you. You moved the tractors of half Of It@ly and then, In the 3nd, you give up?"</i>		
<i>"Do they bl0ck anything? Th3y ar3 @ll very discIplined , all lin3d up (the tr@ct0rs polished to new so as not to get dirty â€ much quieter than their c0ws . . to see pr0tests of pissed off p3ople , go to France , Holland , Germany , Belgium. We Only g3t angry @bout football . ."</i>	<i>Do they bl0ck? Th3y ar3 @ll very discIplined , all lin3d up (the tr@ct0rs polished to new so as not to get dirty â€ much quieter than their c0ws . . to see pr0tests of pissed off p3ople , go to France , Holland , Germany , Belgium we Only g3t angry @bout football . .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"An outing to th3 centre? All rigorously disciplined—more tame than their cows in th3 st@bles , with tractors pulled out t0 a shine . The usual arm3d_forces car leads the t0ur and show the way â€ TO TALK ABOUT PROTEST IS EXAGGERATED. To see pissed off pe0ple pr0t3sting g0 to France , Holl@nd , Germany , Belgium where th3 forces_of_Order d0n't g0 n3ar . BUT HERE THEY ONLY GET PISSED OFF ABOUT FOOTBALL"</i>	<i>An outing to th3 centre? All rigorously disciplined are more tame than their cows in th3 st@bles , with tractors pulled out t0 a shine . The usual arm3d_forces car t0 lead the t0ur and show the way â€ TO TALK ABOUT PROTEST IS EXAGEROUS. To see pissed off pe0ple pr0t3sting g0 to France , Holl@nd , Germany , Belgium where th3 forces_of_Order d0n't g0 n3ar . BUT HERE THEY ONLY GET PISSED OFF ABOUT FOOTBALL</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>To me, It looks mor3 like a nice parad3 to show who h@s th3 b3st-looking tractor, c0mplete with escort my qu3stion is then did they unload and s3t fire to th3 manure ? ? ? ? Becaus3 In France this is what they are d0ing but . w3 ar3 Italians a ### peopl3</i>	<i>To me, It looks mor3 like a nice parad3 to show who h@s th3 b3st-looking tractor, c0mplete with escort my qu3stion is then they unloaded and s3t fire to th3 manure ? ? ? ? Becaus3 In France this is what they are d0ing but . w3 ar3 Italians a ### peopl3</i>	['neg']	anger

Cluster 3: pro-Tractors

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"C0me On and have courage. Italy Is with you farmers, without you nothing comes to our table, we don't w@nt cricket flour or even @rtificial meat, w3 only want Italian fo0d"</i>	<i>C0me On and courage. Italy Is with you farmers, without you nothing comes to our table, we don't w@nt cricket flour or even @rtificial meat, w3 only want Italian fo0d</i>	['pos']	anger
<i>"Great, w3 @re with y0u"</i>	<i>Great, we are with you</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>Th@nk you for your determination, you ar3 our hero3s</i>	<i>Th@nk you for your determination, you ar3 our hero3s</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"I m@ke my contribution from home by sharing on s0c1al. Un1t3d in the struggle and no m0r3 fe@r"</i>	<i>I m@ke my contribution from home by sharing in s0c1al. Un1t3d in the struggle and no m0r3 fe@r</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"Keep sharing th3 im@ges we s33 published from all 0v3r Italy, the news say nothing"</i>	<i>Keep sharing th3 im@ges we s33 published from all 0v3r Italy, the news say nothing</i>		anger

<i>"Socials let us know about you.... national news outlets don't even give you visibility..... but people are on your side"</i>	<i>Socials let us know about you.... national news outlets don't even give you visibility..... but people are on your side</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"Keep going, we're with you, don't give up, guys... You are the strength of the future."</i>	<i>Keep going, we're with you, don't give up, guys... You are the strength of the future.</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"Well done! You are our pride, and thanks to you, we eat Italian food. Go! GO! Go!"</i>	<i>Well done! You are our pride, and thanks to you, we eat Italian food. Go! GO! Go!</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"You're doing the right thing. We must make ourselves heard across Italy and then all over Europe. We Italians stand with you. We must succeed. Full speed ahead—don't give up. Stand up for yourselves. Long live Italy and all its people. No one must touch us. A hug to all of you."</i>	<i>You're doing the right thing. We must make ourselves heard across Italy and then all over Europe. We Italians stand with you. We must succeed. Full speed ahead—don't give up. Stand up for yourselves. Long live Italy and all its people. No one must touch us. A hug to all of you.</i>	['pos']	anger
<i>"They want us to eat crap... I hope they're served manure to eat. Keep it up, we're with you. Strong that the newspapers aren't talking about this. All professions should unite, block Italy, and leave Europe. Only this might something change; otherwise, as long as it's "you go ahead," nothing will really change."</i>	<i>They want us to eat crap... I hope they're served manure to eat. Keep it up, we're with you. Strong that the newspapers aren't talking about this. All professions should unite, block Italy, and leave Europe. Only this might something change; otherwise, as long as it's "you go ahead," nothing will really change.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Well done, stand up for your rights! You young people are the future of this poor Italy, which is falling apart. Keep going; we're all with you."</i>	<i>Well done, stand up for your rights! You young people are the future of this poor Italy, which is falling apart. Keep going; we're all with you.</i>	['pos', 'neg']	joy
<i>"Come on come on come on you must not give up come on"</i>	<i>Come on come on come on you must not give up come on</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"Come on we are with you only you had the balls to rebel but we all should have united with you!"</i>	<i>Come on we are with you only you had the balls to rebel but together with you we all had to be united ?</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"Come on guys I'm with you and I'll always be there in the square. As for you cowards, it's SHEEP who stay at home watching Sanremo, remember that without them you are ### you want to eat ### as for those thieves, crooks, colluders and murderers of politicians, we're coming to you, VISCIOUS PARASITES, ###-lickers of ### . . ."</i>	<i>Come on guys I'm with you and I'll always be there in the square, as for you Cunts it's PECORONS who stay at home watching Sanremo, remember that without them you are ### you want to eat ### as for those thieves, crooks, colluders and murderers of politicians, we're coming to you, VISCIOUS PARASITES, ###-lickers of ### . . .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Well done, keep going, don't stop, you farmers must win, come on ???"</i>	<i>Well done, keep going, don't stop, you farmers must win, come on ??????????????????????????????</i>	['pos']	joy

<p>"Everyone is saying the s@me thing: we are with you, y3s on the social media . On Faceb0ok b0th . o . with you but we are . o noooo wake up to be with them it me@ns all of us beIng present to block everything and every0n3 like th3 Fr3nch do @nd inst3ad we are all saying on our phones we are w1th y0u face . o l@ugh pou bea . figure saying you are great you have the b@lls t0 do it we unfortun@tely observe y0u 0 but we can not the . problem Is them and we work . the . loaf of bread . Oma . xasa if It w3re the French mo . they'd all b3 on the street and we're her3 w@tchIng and writing beautiful it@ly"</p>	<p>All saying the s@me thing we are . with you y3s on the socila . for Faceb0ok b0th . o . with you but we are . o noooo wake up to be with them . it me@ns all of us beIng present to block everything and every0n3 like . th3 Fr3nch do @nd inst3ad we are all saying on the . cell . we are w1th y0u face . o l@ugh pou bea . figure saying you are great you have the b@lls t0 do it we unfortun@tely observe y0u 0 but we can not the . problem Is them and we work . the . loaf of bread . Oma . xasa if It w3re the French mo . they'd all b3 on the street and we're her3 w@tchIng and writing bell . it@ly</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"FORZA IT@LIA! YES! BUT I ASK MYS3LF A QUESTION: WHO LEADS THESE DEMONSTRATIONS SO PERFPECTLY WITHOUT ### CARTS . 0NC3 YOU G3T TO ROME BUT TH3N YOU L3AV3 THE TRACTORS OUTSIDE ROME AND CONTINUE ON FOOT ? ? @ND WITH WHOM DO YOU GO TO D3AL, WITH WHICH GOV3RNMENT WITH THE MELONI GOVERNMENT I DO NOT B3LIEVE B3CAUS3 IT IS ALIGNED WITH 3UROPEAN RULES. WHO AR3 YOU GOING TO NEGOTIATE . IT LOOKS LIKE THEY ARE TAKING YOU ON @ PAR@DE TO THE GATES OF ROME OR AM I WR0NG ? ? ?"</p>	<p>FORZA IT@LIA SIII1 M@AAA I ASK MYS3LF A QUEST1ON BUT ACCORDING TO YOU WHO LEADS THESE DEMONSTRATIONS SO PERFPECTLY WITHOUT ### CARTS . MAA 0NC3 YOU G3T TO ROME BUT TH3N YOU L3AV3 THE TRACTORS OUTSIDE ROME AND CONTINUE ON FOOT ? ? @ND WITH WHOM DO YOU GO TO D3AL, WITH WHICH GOV3RNMENT WITH THE MELONI GOVERNMENT I DO NOT B3LIEVE B3CAUS3 IT IS IN_RIGHT WITH 3UROPEAN RULES. WHO AR3 YOU GOING TO DEAL WITH . IT LOOKS LIKE THEY ARE TAKING YOU ON @ PAR@DE TO THE GATES OF ROME OR AM I WR0NG ? ? ?</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Come on . . Rome f3ll und3r the barbarian invasion . . . come on, let's @ll pull together towards ROME . FARM3RS, H@ULIERS ETC . . . L3T'S ASSERT OUR RIGHTS, AS TH3 SAYING GOES: UNION IS STRENGTH . ! ! IT IS ALREADY . . ! ! ! ."</p>	<p>Come on . . Rome f3ll und3r the barbarian invasion . . . come on, let's @ll pull together towards ROME . FARM3RS, H@ULIERS ETC . . . L3T'S ASSERT OUR RIGHTS, AS TH3 SAYING GOES: UNION IS STRENGTH . ! ! IT IS ALREADY . . ! ! ! .</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The soil gen3rates life . . From the soil, we c@nn0t im@gine how many infinite spr0uts can be born . . . Trees, fruits, from each labour3d moment, with c@r3 our n3eds are born, th3 great element of Our nourishm3nt . . . We must never under3st1mate th3ir fundamental</p>	<p>The soil gen3rates life . . From the soil, we c@nn0t im@gine how many infinite spr0uts can be born . . . Trees, fruits, from each labour3d moment, with c@r3 our n3eds are born, th3 great element of Our nourishm3nt . . . We must never under3st1mate th3ir</p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>joy</p>

<i>contribution . . You all, yOu are sap for us all! YOu ar3 the supply chaIn . . . th@t reach3s us all . . The futur3 is and wlll remaIn for me, all of yOu! We shOuld just thank you for what you collect and do ev3ry day! Ad ma10ra s3mper . . To all of you, a single and immense thank you!"</i>	<i>fundamental contribution . . You all, yOu are sap for us all! YOu ar3 the supply chaIn . . . th@t reach3s us all . . The futur3 is and wlll remaIn for me, all of yOu! We shOuld just thank you for what you collect and do ev3ry day! Ad ma10ra s3mper . . To all of you, a single and immense thank you!"</i>		
<i>"I. I address th3 . People . Italian . @lso . I. COnsumers . Must . Get . In . Square . Come . Don't . L3ave. I. I'm . Wlth . YOu force . Italy"</i>	<i>I. I address th3 . People . Italian . @lso . I. COnsumers . Must . Get . In . Square . Come . Don't . L3ave. I. I'm . Wlth . YOu force . Italy"</i>	['pos']	anger
<i>"Great, w3 are with you, we should be with you not only in thought but in p3rsOn, we are @ll bound by th3 same dest1ny, if you fall we all fall, so come on people. . . let's not just make ours3lves heard . . l3t us be seen ."</i>	<i>Great, w3 are with you, we should be with you not only in thought but in p3rsOn, we are @ll bound by th3 same dest1ny, if you fall we all fall, so come on people. . . let's not just make ours3lves heard . . l3t us be seen ."</i>	['pos', 'neg']	joy
<i>"Come on guys, assert your r1ghts, don't negoti@te ifyou dOn't get what you want, f0r you and f0r us, com3 on we are all with you"</i>	<i>Come on guys, assert your r1ghts, don't negoti@te ifyou dOn't get what you want, f0r you and f0r us, com3 on we are all with you"</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"I am from Rome I c@n imagin3 the traffic that wlll occur with your presence, but I am on your s1d3 also because you ar3 not only doIng it for you but @lso for us I AM WITH YOU strength"</i>	<i>I am from Rome I c@n imagin3 the traffic that wlll occur with your presence, but I am on your s1d3 also because you ar3 not only doIng it for you but @lso for us I AM WITH YOU strength"</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"You shout at GREAT VOICE we will be your cho1r . COME ON FARMERS WE ARE WITH YOU IN ROME ."</i>	<i>You shout at GREAT VOICE we will be your cho1r . COME ON FARMERS WE ARE WITH YOU IN ROME ."</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"Italy is awake! Come On, we are all with you f@rmers, you are our strength, our pride and our h0pe!"</i>	<i>Italy is awake! Come On, we are all with you f@rmers, you are our strength, our pride and our h0pe!"</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"We are all wlth you. May the g0od L0rd @cc0mpany you and g1ve you strength and courage . @ hug to you all fr0m Sicily"</i>	<i>We are all wlth you. May the g0od L0rd @cc0mpany you and g1ve you strength and courage . @ hug to you all fr0m Sicily"</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"Well don3, continue to make yourselves heard in d3f3nding the interests Of yourselves, of your cat3g0ry and of all of us It@llans, alw@ys st@y unit3d and In cont@ct with the Other European farmers, be careful becaus3 politics and not Only politics will certainly try to div1d3 you, I am conv1nced by 3xp3ri3nce that this is their STRENGHT. St@y In touch with the others, be united, be strong and we Italians @re with yOu, strength @nd courage, GOOD_WILL"</i>	<i>Well don3, continue to make yourselves heard in d3f3nding the interests Of yourselves, of your cat3g0ry and of all of us It@llans, alw@ys st@y unit3d and In cont@ct with the Other European farmers, be careful becaus3 politics and not Only politics will certainly try to div1d3 you, I am conv1nced by 3xp3ri3nce that this is their STRENGHT. St@y In touch with the others, be united, be strong and we Italians @re with yOu, strength @nd courage, GOOD_WILL friends,"</i>	['pos']	joy

<i>friends, GOOD_WORTH for llfe and good_w0rk"</i>	<i>GOOD_WORTH for llfe and good_w0rk</i>		
<i>"Come on Farmers , C0me On People , we are all un1ted and strong , may G0d always help us ! ! ! We @re stronger than "Them" Even Sanremo ! ! !"</i>	<i>Come on Farmers , C0me On People , we are all un1ted and strong , may G0d always help us ! ! ! We @re stronger than "Them" Sanremo too! ! !"</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"All together, union is strength. . . All in the square . . . block the whole of It@ly ???? don't glve up w3 are @ll w1th you! ! !"</i>	<i>All together, union is strength. . . All in the square . . . block the whole of It@ly ???? don't glve up w3 are @ll w1th you! ! !"</i>	['pos', 'neg']	anger
<i>"The journalists wh0 are slav3s and s3rvants Of the system are s1lent, surely they will soon block soc1al media! ! ! ! !"</i>	<i>The journalists wh0 are slav3s and s3rvants Of the system are s1lent, surely they will soon block soc1al media! ! ! ! ! ! ! ! !"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Proud of all of you x what you do . block Sanr3mo we @r3 all with y0u ."</i>	<i>Proud of all of you x what you do . block Sanr3mo we @r3 all with y0u ."</i>	['pos', 'neg']	joy

Cluster 4: pro-Eu and pro-environment

CONTEXT – version 1 (transl. via Chat GPT 4o)	CONTEXT – version 2 (transl. via DeepL Premium)	SENTIMENT	EMOTION
<i>"And shall we talk about the constant sewage spills caused by intensive livestock farms? ... And all this ends up in the gr0undwater... (...)It is @ th1ng that affects everyone's health!!!"</i>	<i>And shall we talk about the constant sewage spills caused by intensive livestock farms?... And all this ends up in the gr0undwater... (...)It is @ th1ng that affects everyone's health!!!"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"1. Pesticide reducti0n in agriculture is right 2. Rotation and reg3nerative bre@ks in s0ils 1s r1ght 3. large retailers must pay fairly for pr0duce and give dign1ty to farmers ..."</i>	<i>1. Pesticide reducti0n in agriculture is right 2. Rotation and reg3nerative bre@ks in s0ils 1s r1ght 3. large retailers must pay fair for pr0duce and give dign1ty to farmers ..."</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Are w3 really w1th th3 farmers, who want to cont1nue us1ng fertilizers, chemic@ls and pesticides?"</i>	<i>Are w3 really w1th th3 farmers, who want to cont1nue us1ng fertilizers, chemic@ls and pesticides?"</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"[Pr0test1ng f@rmers] demanded @nd succeeded in poisoning crops with more pesticid3s. Crops, especially vineyards and olive groves, [are cult1vated with the] highly carcinogenic glyph0s@t3, but th3 rest do not lack it eith3r."</i>	<i>[Pr0test1ng f@rmers] demanded @nd got to poison crops with more pesticid3s. Cultures, especially vineyards and olive groves, [are cult1vated with the] highly carcinogenic glyph0s@t3, but th3 rest do not lack it eith3r."</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"I understand your point of view, but I think you misunderstood m3. I, too, llve in a rural environment, and I'm not saying all farmers use banned products—at least not all of them. But it's precis3ly the ch3mic@l fertil1z3rs, synthetic"</i>	<i>I understand your point of view, but I think you misunderstood m3. I, too, llve in a rural environment, and I'm not saying all farmers use banned products—at least not all of them. But it's precis3ly the"</i>	['neg']	anger

<i>pesticid3s, and insecticides that pois0n us. @dd to th@t the crops gr0wn 0n polluted l@nd."</i>	<i>ch3mic@l fertiliz3rs, synthetic pesticid3s, and insecticides that pois0n us. @dd to th@t the crops gr0wn 0n polluted l@nd.</i>		
<i>"It's t1me to make time for important things. And you are import@nt to th3 entir3 supply chain and @ll of us. Your work is our s0urc3 of sustenance. Y0ur work fuels our evolution. We n3ed you. And 3v3ryone must understand and respect others' w0rk. It's time to change, to add, n0t subtract."</i>	<i>It's t1me to make time for important things. And you are import@nt to th3 entir3 supply chain and @ll of us. Your work is our s0urc3 of sustenance. Y0ur work fuels our evolution. We n3ed you. And 3v3ryone must understand and respect others' w0rk. It's time to change, to add, n0t subtract.</i>	['pos']	joy
<i>"ignorant @nd lazy farmers who don't know how to w0rk rely on shortcuts that po1son the world, whil3 those who work seriously d0n't pollute the land with pesticides. Ign0rant people are known t0 be Immor@l too, harming society and th3 planet. I don't 3at bananas, and I d0n't understand why you're us1ng th3 plural when I'm speaking only for myself."</i>	<i>ignorant @nd lazy farmers who don't know how to w0rk rely on shortcuts that po1son the world, whil3 those who work seriously d0n't pollute the land with pesticides. Ign0rant people are known t0 be Immor@l too, harming society and th3 planet. I don't 3at bananas, and I d0n't understand why you're us1ng th3 plural when I'm speaking only for myself.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"do you even realIze what y0u've written? You're a kid wh0 hasn't ev3n lived l1fe yet, @nd you're writ1ng n0ns3nse. Go f@rm th3 land f0r ### ye@rs, then come back and talk. Imagine—this guy stopped using his baby bottle y3sterday, and now he's call1ng others traitors. If these are 0ur young p3ople, let them emigrate too."</i>	<i>do you even realIze what y0u've written? You're a kid wh0 hasn't ev3n lived l1fe yet, @nd you're writ1ng n0ns3nse. Go f@rm th3 land f0r ### ye@rs, then come back and talk. Imagine—this guy stopped using his baby bottle y3sterday, and now he's call1ng others traitors. If these are 0ur young p3ople, let them emigrate too.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>b@ck 1n the day, yes. I'm talk1ng about about ### years ag0. I was mostly r@ised on cow's milk—from a single cow that was c@refully mon1tored.</i>	<i>b@ck 1n the day, yes. I'm talk1ng about about ### years ag0. I was mostly r@ised on cow's milk—from a single cow that was c@refully mon1tored.</i>	[]	anger
<i>"Do you know wh@t is th3 famous victory that the farmers got from the 3ur0p3an Parliament that 3veryone has been talking about thes3 d@ys? ? ? The use of PESTICIDES and ANTIBIOTICS to th3 bitter 3nd on @nimal farms! !! Those p3st1cides that have polluted land, water, food you glve to your childr3n, fruit, v3get@bles, m3at, w@t3r are now c0ntamin@ted by th3 disprop0rti0n@t3 us3 farmers make 0f pesticides . . ."</i>	<i>Do you know wh@t is th3 famous victory that the farmers got from the 3ur0p3an Parliament that 3veryone has been talking about thes3 d@ys? ? ? The use of PESTICIDES and ANTIBIOTICS to th3 bitter 3nd on @nimal farms! !! Those p3st1cides that have polluted land, water, food you glve to your childr3n, fruit, v3get@bles, m3at, w@t3r are now c0ntamin@ted by th3</i>	['neg']	anger

	<i>dispropOrtiOn@t3 us3 farmers make Of pesticides . . .</i>		
<i>"Pestic1des are one of th3 causes of water polluti0n (they end up in the water you drink and w@ter your basil with) and some pesticides @re persist3nt organic p0llutants th@t contribute to the contamination of soil @nd flowers (pollen, nectar). Th3 use of pesticid3s also has a negat1v3 impact on n3ighbouring agr1cultur@l @ctiv1t1es, those of your trusted grower, ab0ut whom you think y0u know ev3rything, @s the pests themselves move in and d@mag3 n3ighb0uring crops on which no pesticides are us3d."</i>	<i>Pestic1des are one of th3 causes of water polluti0n (they end up in the water you drink and w@ter your basil with) and some pesticides @re persist3nt organic p0llutants th@t contribute to the contamination of soil @nd flowers (pollen, nectar). Th3 use of pesticid3s also has a negat1v3 impact on n3ighbouring agr1cultur@l @ctiv1t1es, those of your trusted grower, ab0ut whom you think y0u know ev3rything, @s the pests themselves move in and d@mag3 n3ighb0uring crops on which no pesticides are us3d.</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"I read th@t one of the farmers' demands w@s to st1ll be abl3 to us3 p3sticides and on this they were satisfied, let alon3 those who pr0duc3 them. I w0nd3r why we can n3ver take a step forward . P3sticides should be banned in the m0st @bsolute way, nobody wants to get sick. They could h@ve be3n incentivised in s0me way towards Organic farming, but th1s government that defends the nat1onal product believes that pest1cid3s are good for us. We will continue to look with compassion at th3 smil1ng l1ttle man wh0 defends mad3_in_italy without knowing what he is t@lking ab0ut. And in the meant1me there is no mention Of the producers' profit compared t0 that of the final d1stributor . Now they can go h0me with a big flst In their hands ."</i>	<i>I read th@t one of the farmers' demands w@s to st1ll be abl3 to us3 p3sticides and on this they were satisfied, let alon3 those who pr0duc3 them. I w0nd3r why we can n3ver take a step forward . P3sticides should be banned in the m0st @bsolute way, nobody wants to get sick. They could h@ve be3n incentivised in s0me way towards Organic farming, but th1s government that defends the nat1onal product believes that pest1cid3s are good for us. We will continue to look with compassion at th3 smil1ng l1ttle man wh0 defends mad3_in_italy without knowing what he is t@lking ab0ut. And in the meant1me there is no mention Of the producers' profit compared t0 that of the final d1stributor . Now they can go h0me with a big flst In their hands .</i>	['neg']	anger
<i>"Pardon me lf I take the liberty, but I think y0u h@ve t0 talk, talk, talk more than parade! Many m1srepresent y0ur demands . . . Th3y t3ll how y0u are protesting f0r m0r3 p3stic1des and then attack you because you only think of profits at the expense of the environment . Expl@in to people wh@t 1s h@pp3ning, what has led you t0 protest, what is happening to</i>	<i>Pardon me lf I take the liberty, but I think y0u h@ve t0 talk, talk, talk more than parade! Many m1srepresent y0ur demands . . . Th3y t3ll how y0u are protesting f0r m0r3 p3stic1des and then attack you because you only think of profits at the expense of the environment . Expl@in to people wh@t 1s h@pp3ning,</i>	['neg']	anger

<p><i>our agrIcultur@l production, to the expropri@tion of land that is sometimes carried out . . . Spe@k, shOut, but communicat3!"</i></p>	<p><i>what has led you t0 protest, what is happening to our agrIcultur@l production, to the expropri@tion of land that is sometimes carried out . . . Spe@k, shOut, but communicat3!</i></p>		
<p><i>"Each cat3gory mind its own f#####g business after g3tting Von d3r Leyen from the European Parliament to open up to farmers: subsidi3s and a stop to the pesticide law. Now Our farmers @re takIng adv@ntage and w@nt the hyperf cut. The usu@l revolutiOnaries who mind th3ir own fucking busIness other than foreIgn gr@In poisoned by p3sticIdes, synthetic me@t, etc. . . Y0u f0rget about the poisons th@t y0u h@ve mad3 the m@fias bury in the c0untrysIde und3r lavish remun3ration, and as always you cllmb onto the ped3st@l and play the moralists th3 purItans. Unf0rtunat3ly f0r you @nd for all of us, this country is destin3d to com3 to an end and it is only f@ir until the real Italians mak3 a united front and fight f0r a single goal to take ev3rything back and become sovereigns of our lives and above all of our h0meland."</i></p>	<p><i>Each cat3gory mind its own f#####g business after g3tting Von d3r Leyen from the European Parliament to open up to farmers: subsidi3s and a stop to the pesticide law. Now Our farmers @re takIng adv@ntage and w@nt the hyperf cut. The usu@l revolutiOnaries who mind th3ir own fucking busIness other than foreIgn gr@In poisoned by p3sticIdes, synthetic me@t, etc. . . Y0u f0rget about the poisons th@t y0u h@ve mad3 the m@fias bury in the c0untrysIde und3r lavish remun3ration, and as always you cllmb onto the ped3st@l and play the moralists th3 purItans. Unf0rtunat3ly f0r you @nd for all of us, this country is destin3d to com3 to an end and it is only f@ir until the real Italians mak3 a united front and fight f0r a single goal to take ev3rything back and become sovereigns of our lives and above all of our h0meland."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"If we talk @bout taxes th@t must b3 r3duced to zero (in my opinion) for f@rmers, raw material prices that must rise, the intr0ducti0n of a ban on imp0rts from non-EU c0untriEs that do not m3et th3 requirements, y0u have my full support and understanding, but If you start talkIng about somethIng else, crIcket fl0ur, cultivated me@t, th3 abolition of climate @nd n@ture protection regulations, I tell you, I don't want to blame your problems on these issues. Unfortunat3ly som3 politIci@ns ar3 instrum3nt@llsIng this protest t0 change the issues t0 what suits them and th3ir friends ."</i></p>	<p><i>If we talk @bout taxes th@t must b3 r3duced to zero (for me) for f@rmers, prices of raw materials that must rise, the intr0ducti0n of a ban on imp0rts from non-EU c0untriEs that do not m3et th3 requirements, y0u have my full support and understanding, but If you start talkIng about somethIng else, crIcket fl0ur, cultivated me@t, th3 abolition of climate @nd n@ture protection regulations, I tell you, I don't want to blame your problems on these issues. Unfortunat3ly som3 politIci@ns ar3 instrum3nt@llsIng this protest t0 change the issues t0 what suits them and th3ir friends ."</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>"Moreover, economic support is always given to the big ones, destroying the small ones. Why isn't something done about that? Why doesn't Georgina speak up and then do (as always) nothing except make virile speeches to wrong consensus? I stand with farmers who do sustainable farming, farmers who do not use pesticides, chemical fertilisers. We look for and consume sustainable products. We are better off, the earth is better off and we support the farmers, the responsible ones. But as always nowadays whoever shouts the loudest gets visibility and the consent of those who don't even listen to what they're shouting."</p>	<p>Moreover, economic support is always given to the big ones, destroying the small ones. Why isn't something done about that? Why doesn't Georgina talk and then do (as always) nothing except make virile speeches to wrong consensus? I am with farmers who do sustainable farming, farmers who do not use pesticides, chemical fertilisers. We look for and consume sustainable products. We are better off, the earth is better off and we support the farmers, the responsible ones. But as always nowadays whoever shouts the loudest gets visibility and the consent of those who don't even listen to what they shout.</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"A communiqué with content... They say we eat thanks to them, but I pay dearly at the supermarket, they don't give it to me for free. They talk about sacrifices, but the ones making sacrifices are the labourers treated like slaves at the euro per hour and often working off the books. They want to maintain the use of pesticides. They want more money, while the EU already gives them tax breaks and subsidies for the BILLION. Get lost..."</p>	<p>Communiqué with content... They talk that we eat thanks to them, but I pay dearly for the supermarket, they don't give it to me for free. They talk about sacrifices, but those who make the sacrifices are the labourers treated like slaves at the euro per hour and often in black. They want to maintain the use of pesticides. They want more money, while the EU already gives them tax breaks and subsidies for the BILLION. Get lost..."</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Sorry but I cannot support people who want to continue using pesticides in agriculture. If the government would give farmers income support if farmers used healthy methods without pesticides, it would be a great idea. But. Big business always wins. Unfortunately."</p>	<p>Sorry but I cannot support people who want to continue with the use of pesticides in agriculture. If the government would give farmers income support if farmers used healthy methods without pesticides, it would be a great idea. But. Big business always wins. Unfortunately.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"ARE YOU WITH 'THE TRACTORS' BECAUSE YOU LIKE IT WITHOUT UNDERSTANDING A DAMN THING? Agriculture, the regulations against which 'the tractors' are fighting include the obligation to allocate at least 4% of arable land to non-productive</p>	<p>"ARE YOU WITH 'THE TRACTORS' BECAUSE YOU LIKE IT WITHOUT UNDERSTANDING A DAMN THING? Agriculture, the regulations against which 'the tractors' are fighting include the obligation to allocate at least 4% of arable land to non-</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>uses, the obligation to rotate crops, REDUCE the use of F3RTILIZERS by at least ###%, PROHIBIT THE USE OF PESTICIDES near homes. ARE YOU REALLY WITH F@RMERS who want to continue using chemical fertilisers and pesticides without limits, rules and controls ? A minimum of study of agronomy teaches , among other beneficial practices for soil fertility, that following was used , which consists of keeping a plot of land fallow . The effects of fallow land are various: limitation of moisture loss through evaporation"</p>	<p>productive uses, the obligation to rotate crops, REDUCE the use of F3RTILIZERS by at least ###%, PROHIBIT THE USE OF PESTICIDES near homes. ARE YOU REALLY WITH F@RMERS who want to continue using chemical fertilisers and pesticides without limits, rules and controls ? A minimum of study of agronomy teaches , among other practices for the beneficial effects on soil fertility , that fallow was used , which consists of keeping a plot of land fallow . The effects of fallow land are various: limitation of moisture loss through evaporation"</p>		
<p>"However, even they are not saints they want the liberalisation of pesticides use . . . all this came after the use went back of their use . . just think how much money a certain big company like Monsanto or whatever it's called would lose and who knows who finances these farmers"</p>	<p>However, even they are not saints they want the liberalisation of the use of pesticides . . . all this came after the use went back of their use . . just think how much money a certain big company like Monsanto or whatever it's called would lose and who knows who finances these farmers"</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Pesticides are bad for you while being profitable. Farmers are fine with it. The EU, however, wants to protect the common interest by halving pesticide use, but the farmers are protesting thanks to the support of the unwitting who, just to say that Europe is bad, are willing to stand in order to support the "poor farmers"."</p>	<p>Pesticides are bad for you while being profitable. Farmers are fine with it. The EU, however, wants to protect the common interest by halving the use of pesticides, but the farmers are protesting thanks to the consensus of the unwitting who, in order to say that Europe is bad, are willing to stand in order to support the "poor farmers".</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"The farmers won. In the end it came out because they were protesting, because the EUROPEAN UNION wanted to reduce the use of pesticides. But the EU backed, they can continue to use pesticides and we stand them, have a nice lunch."</p>	<p>The farmers won. In the end it came out because they were protesting, because the EUROPEAN UNION wanted to reduce the use of pesticides. But the EU backed, they can continue to use pesticides and we stand them, have a nice lunch.</p>	<p>['pos', 'neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"and anyway the farmers have been protesting for ### days . This means that they can afford not to work and not to earn money , so</p>	<p>and anyway the farmers have been protesting for ### days . This means that they can afford not to work and not to earn</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>they said on TV . Or, perhaps, they can afford not to work because there are laborers, perhaps underpaid, who do it for them . For these, how ever, no one ever protests"</i></p>	<p><i>money , so they said on TV . Or, perhaps, they can afford not to work because there are workers, perhaps underpaid, who do it for them . For these, how ever, no one ever protests</i></p>		
<p><i>"There is a need for awareness , knowledge , commitment . To take the right steps to move towards a new type of agriculture , using today's available technologies , less intensive , less pesticides , more attention to crop rotation and maintaining soil fertility , less mega machines , intelligent automation , and more km 0 purchases by consumers . For the environment (of which we are part) and for our health . As a technician, I don't understand the excessive use of mega-machines when with robotic agriculture, using solar energy and small dedicated robots, It is possible to sow, fertilise, take care of the plants and harvest with great precision, with lower energy and time costs, with great advantages for those who work and the ability to offer consumers high-quality products."</i></p>	<p><i>There is a need for awareness , knowledge , commitment . To take the right steps to move towards a new type of agriculture , using the technologies available today , less intensive , less pesticides , more attention to crop rotation and maintaining soil fertility , less mega machines , intelligent automation , and more km 0 purchases by consumers . For the environment (of which we are part) and for our health . As a technician, I don't understand the excessive use of mega-machines when with robotic agriculture, using solar energy and small dedicated robots, It is possible to sow, fertilise, take care of the plants and harvest with great precision, with lower energy and time costs, with great advantages for those who work and the possibility of offering consumers a quality product.</i></p>	<p>['pos']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p><i>"FARMERS MAH ! ! ! ! . EUROPE'S ONLY SUCCESS IS STILL BEING ABLE TO POLLUTE OUR FOOD WITH PESTICIDES. In all these tractor and farmer marches, I still don't see any of those thousands of farm laborers, who pull down tomatoes and various fruits for ### to ### hours a day for a little over ### euros an hour. Strange thing . . Or not . Zero demands for those who work the fields . I know that we are victims of a deception to which we are falling for . I don't see any farm labourers at these demonstrations, only tractors. And yes, the farm labourers are not the owners of the tractors. These demonstrations reek to me of corporatism . The tractors won, they managed to get Europe to turn around . The</i></p>	<p><i>FARMERS MAH ! ! ! ! . EUROPE'S ONLY SUCCESS IS THAT OF STILL BEING ABLE TO POLLUTE OUR FOOD WITH PESTICIDES. In all these tractor and farmer marches, I still don't see any of those thousands of farm labourers, who pull down tomatoes and various fruits for ### to ### hours a day for a little over ### euros an hour. Strange thing . . Or not . Zero claims for those who work the fields . I know that we are victims of a deception to which we are falling for . I don't see any farm labourers at these demonstrations, only tractors. And yes, the farm labourers are not the owners of the tractors. These demonstrations</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p><i>tractors have won, fr0m now on"</i></p>	<p><i>reek to me of c0prp0rativism . The tractors won, they managed t0 get Europe to turn around . The tractors have won, fr0m now on</i></p>		
<p><i>"The Hercules cow lives in a small pen, milked up to thr3e t1mes a d@y, in order to Obtain the requ1r3d quantity of milk (ab0ut 40 litr3s) she gives birth to one calf a year, wh1ch is sl@ught3red almost imm3diately if It is @ male Or s3nt for breeding if it 1s female. After @ few years, c0mpared to the l1fe expectancy Of @ cow, milk product1on dr0ps and s0 the Hercules c0w ends up at th3 slaughterhouse and, because of the l@rg3 qu@ntity of m3dicines and @nt1biotics it has t@ken sinc3 birth to endure such extreme liv1ng condit1ons, its meat will b3 destined for consumption by other @nimals. Agriculture is th3 primary sector, and it should be, but industrial farming and modern e@ting hab1ts are horrible. Ps if you hav3 @ c0w it recognises you as if it w3re a d0g"</i></p>	<p><i>"The Hercules cow lives in a small pen, milked up to thr3e t1mes a d@y, in order to Obtain the requ1r3d quantity of milk (ab0ut 40 litr3s) she gives birth to one calf a year, wh1ch is sl@ught3red almost imm3diately if It is @ male Or s3nt for breeding if it 1s a female, after @ few years, c0mpared to the l1fe expectancy Of @ cow, milk product1on dr0ps and s0 the Hercules c0w ends up at th3 slaughterhouse and, because of the l@rg3 qu@ntity of m3dicines and @nt1biotics it has t@ken sinc3 birth to endure such extreme liv1ng condit1ons, its meat will b3 destined for consumption by other @nimals. Agriculture is th3 primary sector, and it should be, but industrial farming and modern e@ting hab1ts are horrible. Ps if you hav3 @ c0w it recognises you as if it w3re a d0g"</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>sadness</p>
<p><i>"Tractors @nd all other equipment are needed to cultivate you still want t0 work with the ox or donkey and ho3 by hand . . . ! ! ! . . . by now every company is full of mortgages that It can hardly pay. . . Take aw@y th3 tract0r . . . Remove everything . . ! ! ! There are alre@dy very restrictiv3 laws on th3 us3 of pestic1des, pl@nt pr0t3ction products, an1mal w3lfare and environm3ntal prot3cti0n. And Italy is even mor3 stricter . . . We have a long list Of very strict control bodi3s . . . for consumer prot3ction . . . The problem is 3veryth1ng that comes from outs1d3 the EU, wh3re th3re are n0t such restrictiv3 laws . . . hav3 p3sticide residu3s . . . ! ! ! !"</i></p>	<p><i>Tractors @nd all other equipment are needed to cultivate you still want t0 work with the ox or donkey and ho3 by hand . . . ! ! ! . . . by now every company is full of mortgages that It can hardly pay. . . Take aw@y th3 tract0r . . . Remove everything . . ! ! ! There are alre@dy very restrictiv3 laws on th3 us3 of pestic1des, pl@nt pr0t3ction products, an1mal w3lfare and environm3ntal prot3cti0n. And Italy is even mor3 restrictive . . . We have a long list Of very strict control bodi3s . . . for consumer prot3ction . . . The problem is 3veryth1ng that comes from outs1d3 the EU, wh3re th3re are n0t such restrictiv3 laws . . . hav3 p3sticide residu3s . . . ! ! ! !"</i></p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>"The fact th@t they drag a poor cow around It@ly says It @ll . . . they want to defend a deleterious model in wh1ch animal rights are not even contemplated, and th3y have f0rgotten the basic principles Of sust@inable agriculture in favour of intensiv3 farm1ng with pesticid3s @nd animals crammed into intensiv3 farms full of antibiotics."</p>	<p>The fact th@t they drag a poor cow around It@ly says It @ll . . . they want to defend a deleterious model in wh1ch animal rights are not even contemplated, and th3y have f0rgotten the basic principles Of sust@inable agriculture in favour of intensiv3 farm1ng with pesticid3s @nd animals crammed into intensiv3 farms full of antibiotics.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"You'll eat P3stic1des just the same—look at Tunisian products Or Turkish hazelnuts . Full of pesticides . Not to ment1on glyphosates wh0se toxicity rep0rt was writt3n for the EU c0mmission by the m@nufacturer"</p>	<p>P3stic1des eat them just the same see Tunisian products Or Turkish hazelnuts . Full of pesticides . Not to ment1on glyphosates wh0se toxicity rep0rt was writt3n for the EU c0mmission by the m@nufacturer</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"But how many peopl3 believe in fa1ry tal3s? They're only th1nking of the1r own gain . They have done a favour to the multination@ls of phytochemicals, pesticid3s, chemical fert1lisers . . ."</p>	<p>But how many peopl3 believe in fa1ry tal3s? They are th1nking of the1r own gain . They have done a favour to the multination@ls of phytochemicals, pesticid3s, chemical fert1lisers . . .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"In @dd1t1on to striking, th3y should th1nk @bout g3tting rid of pesticides and chemical f3rtilisers that are harmful to our he@lth, these d#####s."</p>	<p>In @dd1t1on to striking, th3y should th1nk @bout g3tting rid of pesticides and chemical f3rtilisers that are harmful to our he@lth, these d#####s.</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"You could h@v3 thought of this before, inste@d of submitting to @ll the 1mpos1tions Of the EU f0r which you have been well paid. But when you contaminated, weeded and p01s0n3d the fields @nd esp3ci@lly us for e@sy profits everything was f1ne. Wasn't 1t? The f1elds had to be cult1v@ted in a divers1fi3d w@y with less p3sticides @nd cont@min@nts to f@vour quality. Now they will give you tw0 pennies to make you feel good as @lready happ3ned ."</p>	<p>You could h@v3 thought of this before, inste@d of submitting to @ll the 1mpos1tions Of the EU f0r which you have been well paid. But when you contaminated, weeded and p01s0n3d the fields @nd esp3ci@lly us in exchange for e@sy profits everything was f1ne. Wasn't 1t? The f1elds had to be cult1v@ted in a divers1fi3d w@y with less p3sticides @nd cont@min@nts to f@vour quality. Now they will give you tw0 pennies to make you feel good as @lready happ3ned .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Let th3m cont1nue to fill us with p3sticid3s and pay those who w0rk th3 land 2 hours an h0ur . . ."</p>	<p>Let th3m cont1nue to fill us with p3sticid3s and pay those who w0rk th3 land 2 hours an h0ur . . .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"a little p@tience and in @ few weeks they will be back to work pumping us full Of pestic1des"</p>	<p>a little p@tience and in @ few weeks they will be back to work pumping us full Of pestic1des</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

<p>"How to scale down @n 3vent . One of the r3asons is this but . . ON3 . . . the oth3r re@sons . ? ? ? T@king aw@y land to plant photovolt@ic and w1nd turbines, fuel costs, m@nur3 d1sp0sal with absurd constraints, absurd constra1nts on livest0ck farms the problems Of the f@rmer @r3 manifold to spe@k only of one problem is r3ductive @lmost an insult"</p>	<p>How to scale down @n 3vent . One of the r3asons is this but . . ON3 . . . the oth3r re@sons . ? ? ? T@king aw@y land to plant photovolt@ic and w1nd turbines, fuel costs, m@nur3 d1sp0sal with absurd constraints, absurd constra1nts on livest0ck farms the problems Of the f@rmer @r3 manifold to spe@k only of one problem is r3ductive @lmost t0 TAKE_IN_GROUND .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Let's hope Italians w@ke up in tim3, too, if we don't want to e@t their cricket meal, plasticised meat, lab-grown v3getables, fish full of metals brought from who knows where, wh1le they have bought up hectares upon hectares of land, farms, while they w1ll make us eat synth3tic food, rem0ving the excus3 that we could no longer grow our own produce, wake up Italians, it's no long3r bedtime! ! !"</p>	<p>Let's hope the Italians w@ke up in tim3, too, if we don't want to e@t their cricket meal, plasticised meat, lab-grown v3getables, fish full of metals brought from who knows where, wh1le they have bought up hectares upon hectares of land, farms, while they w1ll make us eat synth3tic food, rem0ving the excus3 that we could no longer grow our own produce, wake up Italians, it's no long3r bedtime! ! !</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"It us3d to b3 the symbol of farmers, but it seems they want t0 supplant it with a n3w symbol "THE PESTICIDE". "</p>	<p>It us3d to b3 the symbol of farmers, but it seems they want t0 supplant it with a n3w symbol "THE PESTICIDE".</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"Animal exploiters . They drag a poor cow through the tr@ffic chaos bec@use it is Only a res0urce f0r th3m to profit from and then send to the slaught3rhouse once it is squeezed dry. Big men who dr1nk milk intended f0r calves as if they wer3 st1ll nursing."</p>	<p>Animal exploiters . They drag a poor cow through the tr@ffic chaos bec@use it is Only a res0urce f0r th3m to profit from and then send to the slaught3rhouse once it is squeezed. Big men who dr1nk milk intended f0r puppies as if they wer3 st1ll suckling .</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>
<p>"A very simple law would suff1ce, Only products th@t comply with EU laws would enter. Do banan@s have too many pestic1des? They get sent b@ck, but If they c0st ### cents @t Eurospin there will b3 a reas0n , and you cannot expect that the It@lian farmer will sell them @t the same price"</p>	<p>A very simple law would suff1ce, Only products th@t comply with EU laws would enter. Do banan@s have too many pestic1des? They get b@ck on board , but If they c0st ### cents @t Eurospin there will b3 a reas0n , and you cannot hope that the It@lian farmer will sell them @t the same price</p>	<p>['neg']</p>	<p>anger</p>

Statement: textual excerpts have been translated by the authors with the support of Artificial Intelligence-based digital translators, following a semi-automated and supervised process. As above indicated, v. 1 applied Deepl premium services, v. 2

ChatGPT 4o. Regex (i.e. regular symbols and expressions) have been manually added – post analysis – to prevent the textual material reported from being a perfect replica of a faithful translation of what was originally retrieved online.

Bibliography

- AFP (2013). *Clashes break out at Italy anti-austerity protests*. <https://au.news.yahoo.com/clashes-break-out-at-italy-anti-austerity-protests-20333418.html>: AFP.
- Alliva, S. (2024). *Il ritorno di Danilo Calvani, l'ex leader dei Forconi riciclato a bordo di un trattore*. <https://lespresso.it/c/politica/2024/2/6/il-ritorno-di-danilo-calvani-lex-leader-dei-forconi-riciclato-a-bordo-di-un-trattore/49932>, last acc. 13/May/2024.
- Atzeni, G. (2024). *Dopo la protesta dei trattori, l'Europa cambia la Pac. Ecco cosa prevede la riforma agricola*. <https://www.gamberorosso.it/notizie/modificata-pac-cosa-prevede/>, last acc., 14/May/2024.
- Bendinelli, S. (2017). *Ascesa e declino del Movimento dei Forconi*. <https://thesubmarine.it/2017/03/24/ascesa-e-declino-del-movimento-dei-forconi/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: The Submarine.
- Bianchi, L. (2013). *La rivoluzione è rinviata a data da destinarsi*. <https://www.vice.com/it/article/4wkbkd/18-dicembre-roma-manifestazione-piazza-del-popolo-9-dicembre-forconi>, last acc. 10/May/2024: vice.com.
- Chiappa, C., Brzeziński, B., Andrés, P., Leven, D. and All (2024). *Brussels police use tear gas, water cannons to quell farmers' protest*. <https://www.eenews.net/articles/brussels-police-use-tear-gas-water-cannons-to-quell-farmers-protest/>, last acc., 14/May/2024: Politico.
- Coccorese, P. (2023). *Dieci anni fa a Torino la protesta dei «Forconi»: la rivolta che fallendo ha cambiato l'Italia*. https://torino.corriere.it/notizie/cronaca/23_dicembre_08/dieci-anni-fa-a-torino-la-protesta-forconi-la-rivolta-che-fallendo-ha-cambiato-l-italia-3da6b367-7eca-455e-86de-0d40ee7ddxlk.shtml: Corriere della Sera, last acc. 9/May/2024.
- consilium.europa.eu (2024). *Support for farmers: Council endorses targeted review of the common agricultural policy*. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/26/support-for-farmers-council-endorses-targeted-review-of-the-common-agricultural-policy/>, last acc. 04/07/2024: Council of the EU.
- Crowdtangle (2024a). *FAQ: Posts and Post Analytics overperforming, underperforming, interaction rate, interactions, video views, reach, and more!* <https://help.crowdtangle.com/en/articles/2489774-faq-posts-and-post-analytics>, last acc. 16/July /2024.
- (2024b). *How do you calculate overperforming scores? Generally it's: (actual interactions)/(expected interactions), but the details get complicated*. <https://help.crowdtangle.com/en/articles/2013937-how-do-you-calculate-overperforming-scores>, last acc. 20/May/2024.
- (2024c). *How is overperforming calculated? We create benchmarks and use those to compare to posts*. <https://help.crowdtangle.com/en/articles/1141056-how-is-overperforming-calculated>, last acc. 21/May/2024.
- euronews.com (2015). *Protesta degli agricoltori a Bruxelles. Trattori davanti le istituzioni per chiedere sostegno alle produzioni*. <https://it.euronews.com/my-europe/2015/09/07/protesta-degli-agricoltori-a-bruxelles-trattori-davanti-le-istituzioni-per>, last acc. 13/May/2024.
- Fesenko, P. (2023a). *Best open-source models for sentiment analysis — Part 1: dictionary models*. <https://medium.com/@pavlo.fesenko/best-open-source-models-for-sentiment-analysis-part-1-dictionary-models-ece79e617653>, last acc. 6 Dec. 2024.
- (2023b). *Best open-source models for sentiment analysis — Part 2: neural networks*. <https://medium.com/@pavlo.fesenko/best-open-source-models-for-sentiment-analysis-part-2-neural-networks-9749fb5fff76>, last acc. 6 Dec. 2024.
- Flourish (n.d.). *Flourish: Data visualization and storytelling*. <https://flourish.studio/>, last acc. 6 Dec. 2024.

- Froio, C. and Gattinara, P.C. (2015). *Neo-fascist mobilization in contemporary Italy. Ideology and repertoire of action of CasaPound Italia*. *Journal for Deradicalization*, 2(86-118).
- Grillo, B. (2013). *Lettera aperta ai responsabili delle forze dell'Ordine*. <https://beppegrillo.it/lettera-aperta-ai-responsabili-delle-forze-dellordine/>, last acc. 15/May/2024.
- ilpost.it (2012). *Che cos'è il "Movimento dei Forconi"*. <https://ilpost.it/2012/01/17/movimento-dei-forconi/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Il Post.
- (2013). *Le proteste dei "forconi" in Italia*. <https://www.ilpost.it/2013/12/09/proteste-forconi-torino-italia/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Il Post.
- (2016). *Osvaldo Napoli è stato aggredito da un gruppo dei "forconi"*. <https://www.ilpost.it/flushes/osvaldo-napoli-e-stato-aggredito-da-un-gruppo-dei-forconi/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Il Post.
- (2023). *I Forconi, dieci anni fa*. <https://www.ilpost.it/2023/12/09/movimento-forconi-dieci-anni-fa/>, : Il Post, last acc. 09/May/2024.
- Lancia, F. (2024). *T-Lab 10. User's Manual*.
- lastampa.it (2012). *I Tir in strada contro il caro benzina. La rivolta dei forconi blocca la Sicilia*. <https://www.lastampa.it/cronaca/2012/01/17/news/i-tir-in-strada-contro-il-caro-benzinala-rivolta-dei-forconi-blocca-la-sicilia-2488742/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Gruppo Gedi.
- latinaoggi.eu (2019). *Latina, prosciolti i Forconi: niente processo escono di scena*. <https://www.latinaoggi.eu/news/cronaca/73742/latina-prosciolti-i-forconi-niente-processo-escono-di-scena.html>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Editoriale Oggi.
- Laugeri, C. and Tropeano, M. (2013). *Sciopero forconi, migliaia in centro*. <https://www.lastampa.it/torino/2013/12/23/news/sciopero-forconi-migliaia-in-centro-1.35944511/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Gruppo Gedi.
- Magnani, A. (2024). *Proteste agricole, si aggiungono anche Romania e Bulgaria*. <https://www.italiafruit.net/proteste-agricole-si-aggiungono-anche-romania-e-bulgaria>, last acc. 14/May/2024: AgroTerGroup.
- Marinolli, M. (2013). *People All Over Italy Are Angry at Their Government*. <https://www.vice.com/en/article/jmbp87/clashes-turin-tax-cuts-pitchfork>: Vice.
- McCauley, L. (2013). *Spiral of Rebellion' Sweeps Italy. Pitchfork movement organizers vow 'peaceful Invasion' of Rome until ruling regime steps down*. <https://www.commondreams.org/news/2013/12/14/spiral-rebellion-sweeps-italy>: Common Dreams.
- Minardi, P. (2024). *Protesta il popolo degli agricoltori siciliani, presidio sulla Palermo-Agrigento*. <https://www.blogsicilia.it/palermo/agricoltori-protesta-palermo-agrigento-presidio-svincolo-bolognetta-video/969482/>, last acc. 13/May/2024.
- open.online (2024). *La protesta degli agricoltori a Bruxelles, statua in fiamme davanti al Parlamento Ue: 4 fermi*. <https://www.open.online/2024/02/01/bruxelles-trattori-vs-ue-video/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Open Impresa Sociale Srl.
- Orrù, P. (2016). *The discourse of political protest in Italy: populist propaganda on Facebook*. *Italianistica Debrenciensis*, 2(21), 145-157.
- Pasqualino, I. (2013). *Forza Nuova insieme ai Forconi: marcia in Piazzale Loreto*. <https://video.repubblica.it/dossier/forconi-rivolta/forza-nuova-insieme-ai-forconi-marcia-in-piazzale-loreto/150015/148522>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Gruppo Gedi.
- Pattueli, F. (2024). *Il gasolio infiamma la protesta agricola in mezza Europa*. <https://www.italiafruit.net/il-gasolio-infiamma-la-protesta-agricola-in-mezza-europa>, last acc. 14/May/2024: AgroTerGroup.
- Pérez, J.M., Rajngewerc, M., Giudici, J.C., Furman, D.A., Luque, F., Alemany, L.A. and Martínez, M.V. (2021). *pysentimiento: A python toolkit for opinion mining and social nlp tasks*. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09462*.

- rainews.it (2013). *FORCONI, IL MOVIMENTO SI SPACCA*. <https://www.rainews.it/archivio-rainews/articoli/amp/ContentItem-2bc8c6fb-f765-4d1d-bb80-364fd253abc1.html> , last acc. 10/May/2024: Rai - Radio Televisione Italiana.
- (2024). *Protesta dei trattori a Roma, agricoltori al Circo Massimo. Calvani (Cra): "Non dobbiamo mollare"*. <https://www.rainews.it/articoli/2024/02/giornata-dei-trattori-a-roma-manifestanti-al-colosseo-in-direzione-circo-massimo--agricoltori-marcia--4fae8fe0-3745-4edc-9c41-da85a3638a47.html> , last acc. 14/May/2024: Rai - Radio Televisione Italiana Spa.
- repubblica.it (2014). *Forconi, 7 arresti e 50 indagati per violenze*
 "Se non chiudete spacchiamo tutto". <https://bari.repubblica.it/cronaca/2014/01/17/foto/forconi-76184284/1/> , last acc. 10/May/2024.
- (2024). *"Te lo do io il Made in Italy": con gli agricoltori anche balneari, pescatori e partite iva*. <https://video.repubblica.it/edizione/roma/te-lo-do-io-il-made-in-italy-con-gli-agricoltori-anche-balneari-pescatori-e-partite-iva/462956/463918> , last acc. 14/May/2024: Gruppo Gedi.
- reuters.com (2019). *Angry farmers cause Dutch police to close off parliament square*. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-netherlands-farmers-protests-idUSKBN1WV0SZ/> , last acc. 10/May/2024: Reuters.
- Ronzoni, D. (2012). *Ma non è che dietro ai forconi si nascondono i saluti romani?* <https://www.linkiesta.it/2012/01/ma-non-e-che-dietro-ai-forconi-si-nascondono-i-saluti-romani/>, last acc. 10/May/2024: Linkiesta.
- rtl.be (2024). *Des blocages d'agriculteurs toujours en cours et ça continuera demain: quel est l'état de la circulation après la manifestation?* <https://www.rtl.be/actu/belgique/societe/des-blocages-dagriculteurs-toujours-en-cours-et-ca-continuera-demain-quel-est/2024-02-01/article/632990> , last acc. 10/May/2024: Rtl
- spiegel.de (2023). *Grüner Minister kritisiert Verteuerung beim Agrardiesel*. <https://www.spiegel.de/politik/deutschland/cem-oezdemir-gruener-minister-kritisiert-verteuerung-beim-agrardiesel-a-fd32c881-ecb9-4643-b32c-bf6026583aef> , last acc. 10/May/2024: Der Spiegel.
- telegraaf.nl (2022). *Zes dagen cel en werkstraf voor actievoerende boer bij Stroe*. <https://www.telegraaf.nl/nieuws/691551962/zes-dagen-cel-en-werkstraf-voor-actievoerende-boer-bij-stroe> , last acc. 10/May/2024: De Telegraaf.
- Tipaldo, G. (2025). *L'analisi del contenuto e i media digitali. Dalla critica delle fonti a ChatGPT*. Bologna: Il Mulino.
- Tipaldo, G., Bruno, F. and Rocutto, S. (2022). «Hands off the olive trees!»: the epistemic war in the *Xylella fastidiosa* epidemic in Italy. A Computer-Assisted Text Analysis of User-generated content on social media. *Cambio. Rivista sulle Trasformazioni Sociali*, 22(11), 131-149.
- Tropeano, M., Laugeri, C. and Minello, B. (2013). *Caos, scontri, blocchi e negozi chiusi*. <https://www.lastampa.it/cronaca/2013/12/10/news/caos-scontri-blocchi-e-negozi-chiusi-2208609/> , last acc. 10/May/2024: Gruppo Gedi.
- Waterfield, B. and Sage, A. (2024). *Farmers topple Brussels statue and dump manure in protest at EU green deal*. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/farmers-topple-brussels-statue-and-dump-manure-in-protest-at-eu-green-deal-3ntbbbsfh> , last acc. 14/May/2024.
- Whitehead, O. (2024). *Belgium in Brief: What will happen after the tractors have gone?* <https://www.brusselstimes.com/belgium/904881/belgium-in-brief-tbtf-11> , last acc., 14/May/2024.